

CMIP5 Model Standard Output

Variable Definitions and Output Requested from Experiments

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Summary:

This document defines the variables saved from the collection of CMIP5 experiments². It expands on variables defined and collected in the previous project phase, CMIP3³. Each variable is defined and placed into an appropriate table in the first part of the document (first 19 tables). The tables differ by the frequency and the method specified for temporal sampling, but sometimes also indicate the primary realm within the climate system associated with the variables. A table may include variables from multiple realms, but sometimes all variables belong to a single primary realm (atmosphere, ocean, land, sea ice, land ice, or aerosol). The last 5 of these 19 tables list variables specially requested by Phase 2 of the Cloud Feedback Model Intercomparison Project (CFMIP-2)⁴.

The second part of the document (the final two tables) defines the subsets of variables requested for each CMIP5 experiment.

There is also an informational page (page 1) that provides general information concerning the grids on which variables were reported and methods for computing variables. Priorities assigned to requested variables are also identified and discussed. The color key indicates when modifications were made in the subsequent tables. Highlighting changes was necessary to alert modeling groups whose simulations were underway that a change had been made to the standard output.

The contents of this document were encoded into the [CMIP5 CMOR tables](#) in a format readable by the [CMOR2 software](#) used by many modeling groups to produce model output files conforming to the [CMIP5 output requirements](#).

Note that although this document may be printed, the font is tiny. A better option is to view it on a wide screen or work with the spread sheet workbook that originally hosted the tables on the [CMIP5 website](#) and which is now also accessible from the same location as this document.

¹ K. E. Taylor collected, curated, and created these tables, but the list of variables and the experiments they were requested from should be credited to the efforts of dozens of scientists responsible for CMIP5 experiment design and scientists before them who had contributed to the lists of standard output collected from CMIP3 and earlier CMIP phases. Paul J. Durack was instrumental in putting the tables in a form that could be understood without the further context provided by the CMIP5 website (<https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/mips/cmip5>).

² Taylor, K.E., R.J. Stouffer, G.A. Meehl: An overview of CMIP5 and the experiment design, *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **93**, 485-498, <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-11-00094.1>, 2012.

³ Taylor, K.E., P. J. Gleckler, R.J. Stouffer, G.A. Meehl, K. AchutaRao, C. Covey, M. Fiorino, M. Latif, J. Mitchel, T. J. Phillips, and K.R. Sperber: CMIP3 Model Standard Output. In *Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison Project Working Papers*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12765214>, 2009

⁴ Bony, S., M. Webb, C. Bretherton, S. Klein, P. Siebesma, G. Tselioudis, and M. Zhang: CFMIP: Towards a better evaluation and understanding of clouds and cloud feedbacks in CMIP5 models, *CLIVAR Exchanges*, 56, 20-24, <https://www.clivar.org/sites/default/files/documents/Exchanges56.pdf#Page=4>, Publisher: CLIVAR, 2011.

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General information

Except as otherwise noted near each table and summarized in the last two spreadsheets ("CFMIP output" and "other output"), each output field should be saved for the entire duration of each and every run.

The specifications for archiving model output, as described in the following tables, assume the following (please advise us if the assumptions are incorrect):

1. Sea ice fields and ocean biogeochemistry fields will be archived on the same grid as ocean fields.
2. Land fields (including ice and snow on land) and land biogeochemistry fields will be archived on the same grid as the atmosphere.

The following rules and recommendations for how to calculate quantities should be followed unless a different method is explicitly indicated in the notes that appear in the following tables.

1. It is recommended that ocean and sea-ice output (including Oclim, Oyr, Omon, and Olmon) be reported on the ocean's native grid. Unless noted otherwise in the tables, all other output should be reported on the atmospheric grid.
2. Unless otherwise specified, the ocean and sea-ice output (including Oclim, Oyr, Omon, and Olmon) represents a mean over only the sea portion of each grid cell (i.e., it is interpreted as "where ocean over ocean"), and a value of 0.0 should be reported where the sea fraction is 0.
3. Unless otherwise specified, the land output (in the Lmon and LImon tables) represents a mean over only the land portion of each grid cell (i.e., it is interpreted as "where land over land"), and a value of 0.0 should be reported where the land fraction is 0.
4. The default interpretation of a Olmon field is that the quantity is averaged over the entire ocean portion of each grid-cell (with a value of zero applying anywhere the quantity is absent in this portion of the cell) and then averaged in time.
4. The default interpretation of a LImon field is that the quantity is averaged over the entire land portion of each grid-cell (with a value of zero applying anywhere the quantity is absent in this portion of the cell) and then averaged in time.

A note on priorities.

The priorities noted in the tables have been largely set by scientists who have participated in model intercomparison activities and have needed these variables in their own research. Since the priorities in different tables were set by different groups of scientists, the priorities in one table may have a different meaning from the priorities in another table. We hope that the vast majority of fields listed in all the tables will be archived by all the modeling groups, but in many cases where a group has not saved a particular field in the past, this may require non-trivial effort. The priorities listed here, along with the participating group's expert judgement should be considered when deciding which fields to save. Please make every effort to save as many of the fields as possible. For lower priority variables, if you can't save them for all the experiments and realizations, please consider saving them for a subset that you think might be of most interest.

Key
 questions

	modified between 10 June 2011 and 27 July 2011
	modified between 27 July 2011 and 26 January 2012
	modified between 26 January 2012 and 12 March 2012
	modified 15 July 2013
	modified 15 August 2013

dims

CMOR Dimensions

CMOR table(s)	CMOR dimension	output dimension name	description	standard name	long name	axis	units	index axis?	coords attrib	bounds?	stored direction	valid_min	valid_max	type	positive	value	bounds values	requested	bounds requested	tol_on_requests: variance from requested values that is tolerated	grid?
fx, Amon, Lmon, LImon, Olmon, aéro, day, 6hrLev, 6hrPlev, 3hr, Oclim, Oyr, Omon, cMon, cFOff, cfDay, cf3hr	longitude	lon		longitude	longitude	X	degrees_east			yes	increasing	0	360	double							
fx, Amon, Lmon, LImon, Olmon, aéro, day, 6hrLev, 6hrPlev, 3hr, Oclim, Oyr, Omon, cMon, cFOff, cfDay, cf3hr	latitude	lat		latitude	latitude	Y	degrees_north			yes	increasing	-90	90	double							
Amon	plevs	plev	There are 17 mandatory levels and up to 6 additional levels requested of models with sufficient resolution in the stratosphere.	air_pressure	pressure	Z	Pa			no	decreasing			double	down		10000. 92500. 85000. 70000. 60000. 50000. 40000. 30000. 25000. 20000. 15000. 10000. 7000. 5000. 3000. 2000. 1000.			0.001	
day	plev8	plev		air_pressure	pressure	Z	Pa			no	decreasing			double	down		100000. 85000. 70000. 50000. 25000. 10000. 5000. 1000.			0.001	
6hrPlev	plev3	plev		air_pressure	pressure	Z	Pa			no	decreasing			double	down		85000. 50000. 25000.			0.001	
cMon, cfDay	plev7	plev	7 pressure layers defined by ISCCP simulator	air_pressure	pressure	Z	Pa			yes	decreasing			double	down		90000. 74000. 62000. 50000. 37500. 24500. 9000.	10000. 8000. 8000. 6800. 6800. 5600. 5600. 4400. 4400. 3100. 3100. 1800. 1800. 0.		0.001	
cfDay	p500	plev	500 hPa	air_pressure	pressure	Z	Pa			no	decreasing		50000.	double	down		70000.				
cfDay	p700	plev	700 hPa	air_pressure	pressure	Z	Pa			no	decreasing		70000.	double	down						
cMon, cfOff, cf3hr	p220	plev	pressure layer of high-level cloud in ISCCP simulator	air_pressure	pressure	Z	Pa			no	decreasing			double	down	22000.	44000. 0.0				
cMon, cfOff, cf3hr	p560	plev	pressure layer of mid-level cloud in ISCCP simulator	air_pressure	pressure	Z	Pa			no	decreasing			double	down	56000.	68000. 44000.				
cMon, cfOff, cf3hr	p840	plev	pressure layer of low-level cloud in ISCCP simulator	air_pressure	pressure	Z	Pa			no	decreasing			double	down	84000.	100000. 68000.				
Amon, aéro, 6hrLev, cMon, cfDay, cf3hr, cfSites	alevel	lev	generic atmospheric model vertical coordinate (nondimensional or dimensional)		atmospheric model level	Z		ok		yes				double	up						
Amon, cMon, cfDay, cf3hr, cfSites	alevhalf	lev	atmospheric model "half" level		atmospheric model half-level	Z		ok		no				double	up						
aéro	alev1	lev	atmospheric model's lowest level		lowest atmospheric model level	Z		ok		yes				double							
cMon, cfOff, cfDay, cf3hr	alt40	alt40	CloudSat vertical coordinate heights	altitude	altitude	Z	m			yes	increasing			double	up		240. 720. 1200. 1680. 2160. 2640. 3120. 3600. 4080. 4560. 5040. 5520. 6000. 6480. 6960. 7440. 7920. 8400. 8880. 9360. 9840. 10320. 10800. 11280. 11760. 12240. 12720. 13200. 13680. 14160. 14640. 15120. 15600. 16080. 16560. 17040. 17520. 18000. 18480. 18960.	0. 480. 480. 960. 960. 1440. 1440. 1920. 1920. 2400. 2400. 2880. 2880. 3360. 3360. 3840. 3840. 4320. 4320. 4800. 4800. 5280. 5280. 5760. 5760. 6240. 6240. 6720. 6720. 7200. 7200. 7680. 7680. 8160. 8160. 8640. 8640. 9120. 9120. 9600. 9600. 10080. 10080. 10560. 10560. 11040. 11040. 11520. 11520. 12000. 12000. 12480. 12480. 12960. 12960. 13440. 13440. 13920. 13920. 14400. 14400. 14880. 14880. 15360. 15360. 15840. 15840. 16320. 16320. 16800. 16800. 17280. 17280. 17760. 17760. 18240. 18240. 18720. 18720. 19200.		0.001	
Oyr, Amon, Lmon, LImon, Olmon, aéro, day, 3hr, Omon, cMon, cfOff, cfDay, cf3hr	time	time	for time-mean fields	time	time	T	days since ?			yes	increasing			double							
6hrLev, 6hrPlev, 3hr, cf3hr, cfSites	time1	time	synoptic times (for fields that are not time-means)	time	time	T	days since ?			no	increasing			double							
Oclim, Amon	time2	time	climatological times	time	time	T	days since ?			yes	increasing			double							
Amon, day, 3hr, cf3hr, cfSites	height2m	height	-2 m standard surface air temperature and surface humidity height	height	height	Z	m			no	increasing	1	10	double	up	2.					
Amon, day, 3hr, cf3hr, cfSites	height10m	height	-10 m standard wind speed height	height	height	Z	m			no	increasing	1	30	double	up	10.					
Lmon, LImon	sdepth	depth	coordinate values for soil layers (depth)	depth	depth	Z	m			yes	increasing	0	200	double	down						
Lmon, day, 3hr	sdepth1	depth	coordinate value for topmost 0.1 meter layer of soil	depth	depth	Z	m			yes	increasing	0	0.2	double	down	0.05	0.0 0.1				
cMon, cfDay	tau	tau	isccp optical depth categories	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_cloud	cloud optical thickness			1		yes	increasing			double			0.15 0.8 2.45 6.5 16.2 41.5 100.	0.0 0.3 0.3 1.3 1.3 3.6 3.6 9.4 9.4 23.0 23.0 60.0 60.0 100000.		0.001	
cfOff, cf3hr	scatratio	scatratio	15 bins of scattering ratio for the CALLIPSO simulator CFAD	backscattering_ratio	lidar backscattering ratio			1		yes	increasing			double			0.001 0.005 0.005 2.1 4. 6. 8. 5 12.5 17.5 22.5 27.5 35. 45. 55. 70. 50040.	0.0 0.1 0.01 1.2 1.2 3. 3. 5. 5. 7. 7. 10. 10. 15. 15. 20. 20. 25. 25. 30. 30. 40. 40. 50. 50. 60. 60. 80. 80. 100000.		0.001	
cfOff, cf3hr	dbze	dbze	15 bins of radar reflectivity for CloudSat simulator CFAD	equivalent_reflectivity_factor	CloudSat simulator equivalent radar reflectivity factor		dBZ			yes	increasing			double			-47.5 -42.5 -37.5 -32.5 -27.5 -22.5 -17.5 -12.5 -7.5 -2.5 -50. -45. -45. -40. -40. -35. -35. -30. -30. -25. -25. -20. -20. -15. -15. -10. -10. -5. -5. 0. 0. 5. 5. 10. 10. 15. 15. 20. 20. 25.			0.001	
cMon, cfOff, cfDay, cf3hr	sza5	sza	5 solar zenith angles for PARASOL reflectances	solar_zenith_angle	solar zenith angle		degree			no	increasing			double			0. 20. 40. 60. 80.			0.001	
cfSites	site	site	an integer assigned to each of 119 stations (standard) and 73 stations (aquaplanet)		site index			ok		no				integer							yes
Omon	basin	basin		region	ocean basin				region	no				character			atlantic_arctic_ocean indian_pacific_ocean global_ocean				
Omon	rho	rho	potential density referenced to 2000 dbar	sea_water_potential_density	potential density referenced to 2000 dbar	Z	kg m ⁻³			yes	increasing			double	down						
fx, Oclim, Oyr, Omon	olevel	lev	generic ocean model vertical coordinate (nondimensional or dimensional)		ocean model level	Z		ok		yes				double	down						
Omon	oline	line	opening, passage, strait, channel, etc.	region	ocean passage				passage	no				character			barents_opening bering_strait canadian_archipelago denmark_strait drake_passage english_channel pacific_equatorial_undercurrent faroe_scotland_channel florida_bahamas_strait fram_strait iceland_faroe_channel indonesian_throughflow mozambique_channel taiwan_luzon_straits windward_passage				

dims

cf3hr	location	loc	COSP profile in instantaneous curtain mode	location index	ok	no	increasing	integer	yes						
Lmon	vegtype	type	plant functional type. Several plant functional types have been defined in the area_type table available at: cf-pcmdi.llnl.gov/documents/cf-standard-names/area-type-table/current/	area_type	plant functional type	type_description	no	character							
Lmon	typebare	type		area_type	surface type	type_description	no	character	bare ground						
Lmon	typesdec	type		area_type	surface type	type_description	no	character	primary_deciduous_trees						
Lmon	typesever	type		area_type	surface type	type_description	no	character	primary_evergreen_trees						
Lmon	typesdec	type		area_type	surface type	type_description	no	character	secondary_deciduous_trees						
Lmon	typesever	type		area_type	surface type	type_description	no	character	secondary_evergreen_trees						
Lmon	typec3pft	type		area_type	surface type	type_description	no	character	c3_plant_functional_types						
Lmon	typec4pft	type		area_type	surface type	type_description	no	character	c4_plant_functional_types						
Omon	olayer100m	depth	coordinate for 100 m ocean surface layer	depth	depth	Z	m	no	increasing	0	100	double	down	50.	0. 100.
Omon	depth100m	depth	coordinate value for 100 m ocean depth	depth	depth	Z	m	no	increasing	80	120	double	down	100.	
Omon	depth0m	depth	vertical coordinate for ocean surface	depth	depth	Z	m	no	increasing	0	100	double	down	0.	

CMOR Table fx: Time-Invariant Fields

fx

fx

on atmospheric grid

Atmospheric and land fields may be submitted on a (single) grid of the modeling group's choosing. We expect most groups will elect to save output on the native grid. If data is "interpolated" to a different grid, it is important to preserve certain global mean properties (e.g., the total surface fluxes of heat, momentum, and water mass).

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Atmosphere Grid-Cell Area	m ²		For atmospheres with more than 1 mesh (e.g., staggered grids), report areas that apply to surface vertical fluxes of energy.	areacella	cell_area	m2			real	longitude latitude	areacella	atmos land				
1	Surface Altitude	m	height above the geoid, as defined here, "the geoid" is a surface of constant geopotential that, if the ocean were at rest, would coincide with mean sea level. Under this definition, the geoid changes as the mean volume of the ocean changes (e.g., due to glacial melt, or global warming of the ocean). Reported here is the height above the present-day geoid (0.0 over ocean).		orog	surface_altitude	m			real	longitude latitude	orog	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Land Area Fraction	%		For atmospheres with more than 1 mesh (e.g., staggered grids), report areas that apply to surface vertical fluxes of energy.	stflf	land_area_fraction	%			real	longitude latitude	stflf	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Fraction of Grid Cell Covered with Glacier	%	fraction of grid cell occupied by "permanent" ice (i.e., glaciers).	For atmospheres with more than 1 mesh (e.g., staggered grids), report areas that apply to surface vertical fluxes of energy.	sflgif	land_ice_area_fraction	%			real	longitude latitude	sflgif	land		area: areacella		
1	Capacity of Soil to Store Water	kg m ⁻²	reported "where land": divide the total water holding capacity of all the soil in the grid cell by the land area in the grid cell; reported as "missing" where the land fraction is 0.		mrsofc	soil_moisture_content_at_field_capacity	kg m-2			real	longitude latitude	mrsofc	land		area: areacella		
1	Maximum Root Depth	m	report the maximum soil depth reachable by plant roots (if defined in model), i.e., the maximum soil depth from which they can extract moisture; report as "missing" where the land fraction is 0.		rootd	root_depth	m			real	longitude latitude	rootd	land		area: areacella		

on ocean grid

The WGOMD has recommended that all ocean fields be saved on the model's native ocean grid. Many groups will also elect to save the sea ice fields on the ocean grid. (The alternative is to save sea ice fields on the atmosphere grid.) If data is "interpolated" from its native grid, it is important to preserve certain global mean properties (e.g., the total surface fluxes of heat, momentum, and water mass into the ocean).

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Sea Floor Depth	m	Ocean bathymetry. Reported here is the sea floor depth for present day. Reported as missing for land grid cells.		deptho	sea_floor_depth_below_geoid	m			real	longitude latitude	deptho	ocean		area: areacello		
1	Ocean Grid-Cell Volume	m ³	grid-cell volume ca. 2000.	a 3-d field; For oceans with more than 1 mesh, report on grid that applies to temperature	volcello	ocean_volume	m3			real	longitude latitude olevel	volcello	ocean				
1	Ocean Grid-Cell Area	m ²		For oceans with more than 1 mesh (e.g., staggered grids), report areas that apply to surface vertical fluxes of energy.	areacello	cell_area	m2			real	longitude latitude	areacello	ocean				
1	Sea Area Fraction	%	This is the area fraction at the ocean surface.	Should this be recorded as a function of depth? Report on the same grid that ocean fields are reported (i.e., the ocean native grid, or the grid that ocean data has been provided to CMIP. For completeness, provide this even if the ocean grid is the same as the atmospheric grid. Report on the same grid as the temperature field. flag_values=0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10 corresponding to flag_meanings=global_land, southern_ocean, atlantic_ocean, pacific_ocean, arctic_ocean, indian_ocean, mediterranean_sea, black_sea, hudson_bay, baltic_sea.	sstof	sea_area_fraction	%			real	longitude latitude	sstof	ocean		area: areacello		
1	Region Selection Index	1		Report on the same grid as the temperature field. flag_values=0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10 corresponding to flag_meanings=global_land, southern_ocean, atlantic_ocean, pacific_ocean, arctic_ocean, indian_ocean, mediterranean_sea, black_sea, hudson_bay, baltic_sea.	basin	region	1			integer	longitude latitude	basin	ocean		area: areacello	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10	global_land southern_ocean atlantic_ocean pacific_ocean arctic_ocean indian_ocean mediterranean_sea black_sea hudson_bay baltic_sea red_sea
2	Upward Geothermal Heat Flux at Sea Floor	W m ⁻²		If this field is time-dependent then save it instead as one of your Omon fields (see the Omon table)	hfgeou	upward_geothermal_heat_flux_at_sea_floor	W m-2	area: mean where sea	up	real	longitude latitude	hfgeou	ocean		area: areacello		
2	Ocean Model Cell Thickness	m		If this field is time-dependent then save it instead as one of your Omon fields (see the Omon table)	thkcello	cell_thickness	m	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel	thkcello	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		

Oclim

CMOR Table Oclim: Monthly Mean Ocean Climatology (Jan. 1986-Dec. 2005 of historical run)
(All Saved on the Ocean Grid)

Oclim

monClim

Further explanation of the fields in the following tables (except the last field, zlayer) can be found in Griffies et al., available at http://www.climvar.org/sites/default/files/imported/organization/wgond/references/WGOMD_CMIP5_ocean_fields.pdf. Some of the information in that document will be transcribed into the "comment" column of this spreadsheet.

In CMOR Table Oclim: WGOMD Table 2.9

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
3	Ocean Vertical Heat Diffusivity	m ² s ⁻¹			difvho	ocean_vertical_heat_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difvho	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Vertical Salt Diffusivity	m ² s ⁻¹			difvso	ocean_vertical_salt_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difvso	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Vertical Tracer Diffusivity due to Background	m ² s ⁻¹			difvrbo	ocean_vertical_tracer_diffusivity_due_to_background	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difvrbo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Vertical Tracer Diffusivity due to Tides	m ² s ⁻¹			difvtrto	ocean_vertical_tracer_diffusivity_due_to_tides	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difvtrto	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Tendency of Ocean Potential Energy Content	W m ⁻²			tpoec	tendency_of_ocean_potential_energy_content	W m-2	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	tpoec	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Tendency of Ocean Potential Energy Content due to Tides	W m ⁻²			tpoect	tendency_of_ocean_potential_energy_content_due_to_tides	W m-2	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	tpoect	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Tendency of Ocean Potential Energy Content due to Background	W m ⁻²			tpoecb	tendency_of_ocean_potential_energy_content_due_to_background	W m-2	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	tpoecb	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Vertical Momentum Diffusivity	m ² s ⁻¹			difvmo	ocean_vertical_momentum_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difvmo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Vertical Momentum Diffusivity due to Background	m ² s ⁻¹			difvmb	ocean_vertical_momentum_diffusivity_due_to_background	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difvmb	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Vertical Momentum Diffusivity due to Tides	m ² s ⁻¹			difvmt	ocean_vertical_momentum_diffusivity_due_to_tides	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difvmt	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Vertical Momentum Diffusivity due to Form Drag	m ² s ⁻¹			difvmfd	ocean_vertical_momentum_diffusivity_due_to_form_drag	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difvmfd	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Kinetic Energy Dissipation Per Unit Area due to Vertical Friction	W m ⁻²			dispkvfo	ocean_kinetic_energy_dissipation_per_unit_area_due_to_vertical_friction	W m-2	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	dispkvfo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		

In CMOR Table Oclim: WGOMD Table 2.10

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
3	Ocean Tracer Bolus Laplacian Diffusivity	m ² s ⁻¹		3-d time dependent field	difrblo	ocean_tracer_bolus_laplacian_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difrblo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Tracer Bolus Biharmonic Diffusivity	m ⁴ s ⁻¹		3-d time dependent field	difrbbo	ocean_tracer_bolus_biharmonic_diffusivity	m4 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difrbbo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Tracer Epineutral Laplacian Diffusivity	m ² s ⁻¹		3-d time dependent field	difrelo	ocean_tracer_epineutral_laplacian_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difrelo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Tracer Epineutral Biharmonic Diffusivity	m ⁴ s ⁻¹		3-d time dependent field	difrebo	ocean_tracer_epineutral_biharmonic_diffusivity	m4 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difrebo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Tracer XY Laplacian Diffusivity	m ² s ⁻¹		3-d time dependent field	difrxlo	ocean_tracer_xy_laplacian_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difrxlo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Tracer XY Biharmonic Diffusivity	m ⁴ s ⁻¹		3-d time dependent field	difrxbo	ocean_tracer_xy_biharmonic_diffusivity	m4 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difrxbo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Tendency of Ocean Eddy Kinetic Energy Content due to Bolus Transport	W m ⁻²		3-d time dependent field	tketbo	tendency_of_ocean_eddy_kinetic_energy_content_due_to_bolus_transport	W m-2	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	tketbo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Momentum XY Laplacian Diffusivity	m ⁴ s ⁻¹		3-d time dependent field	difmxylo	ocean_momentum_xy_laplacian_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difmxylo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Momentum XY Biharmonic Diffusivity	m ⁴ s ⁻¹		3-d time dependent field	difmxybo	ocean_momentum_xy_biharmonic_diffusivity	m4 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	difmxybo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Kinetic Energy Dissipation Per Unit Area due to XY Friction	W m ⁻²		3-d time dependent field	dispkxyfo	ocean_kinetic_energy_dissipation_per_unit_area_due_to_xy_friction	W m-2	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	dispkxyfo	ocean		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Tracer Bolus Laplacian Diffusivity	m ² s ⁻¹		2-d time dependent field	difrblo	ocean_tracer_bolus_laplacian_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude time2	difrblo2d	ocean		area: areacello		
3	Ocean Tracer Bolus Biharmonic Diffusivity	m ⁴ s ⁻¹		2-d time dependent field	difrbbo	ocean_tracer_bolus_biharmonic_diffusivity	m4 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude time2	difrbbo2d	ocean		area: areacello		
3	Ocean Tracer Epineutral Laplacian Diffusivity	m ² s ⁻¹		2-d time dependent field	difrelo	ocean_tracer_epineutral_laplacian_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude time2	difrelo2d	ocean		area: areacello		

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3	Ocean Tracer Epineutral Biharmonic Diffusivity	$m^4 s^{-1}$		2-d time dependent field	difrebo	ocean_tracer_epineutral_biharmonic_diffusivity	m4 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	longitude latitude time2	difrebo2d	ocean	area: areacello
3	Ocean Tracer XY Laplacian Diffusivity	$m^2 s^{-1}$		2-d time dependent field	difrxyl0	ocean_tracer_xy_laplacian_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	longitude latitude time2	difrxyl02d	ocean	area: areacello
3	Ocean Tracer XY Biharmonic Diffusivity	$m^4 s^{-1}$		2-d time dependent field	difrxybo	ocean_tracer_xy_biharmonic_diffusivity	m4 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	longitude latitude time2	difrxybo2d	ocean	area: areacello
3	Tendency of Ocean Eddy Kinetic Energy Content due to Bolus Transport	$W m^{-2}$		2-d time dependent field	tnkcbto	tendency_of_ocean_eddy_kinetic_energy_content_due_to_bolus_transport	W m-2	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	longitude latitude time2	tnkcbto2d	ocean	area: areacello
3	Ocean Momentum XY Laplacian Diffusivity	$m^2 s^{-1}$		2-d time dependent field	difmxylo	ocean_momentum_xy_laplacian_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	longitude latitude time2	difmxylo2d	ocean	area: areacello
3	Ocean Momentum XY Biharmonic Diffusivity	$m^4 s^{-1}$		2-d time dependent field	difmxybo	ocean_momentum_xy_biharmonic_diffusivity	m4 s-1	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	longitude latitude time2	difmxybo2d	ocean	area: areacello
3	Ocean Kinetic Energy Dissipation Per Unit Area due to XY Friction	$W m^{-2}$		2-d time dependent field	dispkxyfo	ocean_kinetic_energy_dissipation_per_unit_area_due_to_xy_friction	W m-2	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	longitude latitude time2	dispkxyfo2d	ocean	area: areacello

Ocean layer depth field requested only from models where it can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored in the file.

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell_methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell_measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Depth Below Geoid of Ocean Layer	m		This 3-d time dependent field should only be saved for models where it can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored in the file.	zfull	depth_below_geoid	m	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	zfull	ocean		area: areacello		
1	Depth Below Geoid of Interfaces Between Ocean Layers	m		This 3-d time dependent field should only be saved for models where it can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored in the file.	zhalf	depth_below_geoid	m	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude olevel time2	zhalf	ocean		area: areacello		

CMOR Table Oyr: Annual Mean Ocean Fields, Including Biogeochemical Fields

Oyr

yr

(All Saved on the Ocean Grid)

In CMOR Table Oyr: 3-D Marine Biogeochemical Tracer Fields

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Dissolved Inorganic Carbon Concentration	mol m ⁻³	Dissolved inorganic carbon (CO ₃ +HCO ₃ +H ₂ CO ₃) concentration		disic	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_inorganic_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	disic	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
2	Dissolved Organic Carbon Concentration	mol m ⁻³			dissoc	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_organic_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	dissoc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
2	Phytoplankton Carbon Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of phytoplankton carbon component concentrations. In most (all?) cases this is the sum of phydiat and phymisc (i.e., "Diatom Carbon Concentration" and "Non-Diatom Phytoplankton Carbon Concentration")		phyc	mole_concentration_of_phytoplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	phyc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
2	Zooplankton Carbon Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of zooplankton carbon component concentrations		zooc	mole_concentration_of_zooplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	zooc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Bacterial Carbon Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of bacterial carbon component concentrations		bacc	mole_concentration_of_bacteria_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	bacc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
2	Detrital Organic Carbon Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of detrital organic carbon component concentrations		detoc	mole_concentration_of_organic_detritus_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	detoc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
2	Calcite Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of particulate calcite component concentrations (e.g. Phytoplankton, Detrital, etc.)		calc	mole_concentration_of_calcite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	calc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
2	Aragonite Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of particulate aragonite components (e.g. Phytoplankton, Detrital, etc.)		arag	mole_concentration_of_aragonite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	arag	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Mole Concentration of Diatoms expressed as Carbon in Sea Water	mol m ⁻³	carbon from the diatom phytoplankton component concentration alone		phydiat	mole_concentration_of_diatoms_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	phydiat	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Mole Concentration of Diazotrophs Expressed as Carbon in Sea Water	mol m ⁻³	carbon concentration from the diazotrophic phytoplankton component alone		phydiaz	mole_concentration_of_diazotrophs_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	phydiaz	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Mole Concentration of Calcareous Phytoplankton expressed as Carbon in Sea Water	mol m ⁻³	carbon concentration from calcareous (calcite-producing) phytoplankton component alone		phycalc	mole_concentration_of_calcareous_phytoplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	phycalc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Mole Concentration of Picophytoplankton expressed as Carbon in Sea Water	mol m ⁻³	carbon concentration from the picophytoplankton (<2 um) component alone		phypico	mole_concentration_of_picophytoplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	phypico	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Mole Concentration of Miscellaneous Phytoplankton expressed as Carbon in Sea Water	mol m ⁻³	carbon concentration from additional phytoplankton component alone		phymisc	mole_concentration_of_miscellaneous_phytoplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	phymisc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Mole Concentration of Microzooplankton expressed as Carbon in Sea Water	mol m ⁻³	carbon concentration from the microzooplankton (<20 um) component alone		zmicro	mole_concentration_of_microzooplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	zmicro	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Mole Concentration of Mesozooplankton expressed as Carbon in Sea Water	mol m ⁻³	carbon concentration from mesozooplankton (20-200 um) component alone		zmeso	mole_concentration_of_mesozooplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	zmeso	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Other Zooplankton Carbon Concentration	mol m ⁻³	carbon from additional zooplankton component concentrations alone (e.g. Micro, meso). Since the models all have different numbers of components, this variable has been included to provide a check for intercomparison between models since some phytoplankton groups are supersets.		zoocmisc	mole_concentration_of_miscellaneous_zooplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	zoocmisc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
1	Total Alkalinity	mol m ⁻³	total alkalinity equivalent concentration (including carbonate, nitrogen, silicate, and borate components)		talk	sea_water_alkalinity_expressed_as_mole_equivalent	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	talk	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
1	pH	1	negative log of hydrogen ion concentration with the concentration expressed as mol H kg ⁻¹ .		ph	sea_water_ph_reported_on_total_scale	1	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	ph	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
1	Dissolved Oxygen Concentration	mol m ⁻³			o2	mole_concentration_of_molecular_oxygen_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	o2	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
1	Dissolved Nitrate Concentration	mol m ⁻³			no3	mole_concentration_of_nitrate_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	no3	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
2	Dissolved Ammonium Concentration	mol m ⁻³			nh4	mole_concentration_of_ammonium_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	nh4	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
1	Dissolved Phosphate Concentration	mol m ⁻³			po4	mole_concentration_of_phosphate_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	po4	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
1	Dissolved Iron Concentration	mol m ⁻³	dissolved iron in sea water is meant to include both Fe ²⁺ and Fe ³⁺ ions (but not, e.g., particulate detrital iron)		dfe	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_iron_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	dfe	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
1	Dissolved Silicate Concentration	mol m ⁻³			si	mole_concentration_of_silicate_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	si	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
1	Total Chlorophyll Mass Concentration	kg m ⁻³	sum of chlorophyll from all phytoplankton group concentrations. In most models this is equal to chldiat+chlmisc, that is the sum of "Diatom Chlorophyll Mass Concentration" plus "Other Phytoplankton Chlorophyll Mass Concentration"		chl	mass_concentration_of_phytoplankton_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water	kg m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	chl	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Diatom Chlorophyll Mass Concentration	kg m ⁻³	chlorophyll from diatom phytoplankton component concentration alone		chldiat	mass_concentration_of_diatoms_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water	kg m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	chldiat	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Mass Concentration of Diazotrophs Expressed as Chlorophyll in Sea Water	kg m ⁻³	chlorophyll concentration from the diazotrophic phytoplankton component alone		chldiaz	mass_concentration_of_diazotrophs_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water	kg m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	chldiaz	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Mass Concentration of Calcareous Phytoplankton expressed as Chlorophyll in Sea Water	kg m ⁻³	chlorophyll concentration from the calcite-producing phytoplankton component alone		chlcalc	mass_concentration_of_calcareous_phytoplankton_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water	kg m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	chlcalc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Mass Concentration of Picophytoplankton expressed as Chlorophyll in Sea Water	kg m ⁻³	chlorophyll concentration from the picophytoplankton (<2 um) component alone		chlpcico	mass_concentration_of_picophytoplankton_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water	kg m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	chlpcico	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Other Phytoplankton Chlorophyll Mass Concentration	kg m ⁻³	chlorophyll from additional phytoplankton component concentrations alone		chlmisc	mass_concentration_of_miscellaneous_phytoplankton_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water	kg m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	chlmisc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Particulate Organic Nitrogen Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of particulate organic nitrogen component concentrations		pon	mole_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_nitrogen_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	pon	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Particulate Organic Phosphorus Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of particulate organic phosphorus component concentrations		pop	mole_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_phosphorus_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	pop	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Particulate Biogenic Iron Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of particulate organic iron component concentrations		bfe	mole_concentration_of_particulate_matter_expressed_as_iron_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	bfe	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Particulate Biogenic Silica Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of particulate silica component concentrations		bsi	mole_concentration_of_particulate_matter_expressed_as_silicon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	bsi	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Phytoplankton Nitrogen Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of phytoplankton nitrogen component concentrations		phyn	mole_concentration_of_phytoplankton_expressed_as_nitrogen_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	phyn	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		
3	Phytoplankton Phosphorus Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of phytoplankton phosphorus components		phyp	mole_concentration_of_phytoplankton_expressed_as_phosphorus_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	phyp	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volocello		

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3	Phytoplankton Iron Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of phytoplankton iron component concentrations	phyfe	mole_concentration_of_phytoplankton_expressed_as_iron_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	phyfe	ocnBgchem	area: areacello volume: volcello
3	Phytoplankton Silica Concentration	mol m ⁻³	sum of phytoplankton silica component concentrations	physi	mole_concentration_of_phytoplankton_expressed_as_silicon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	physi	ocnBgchem	area: areacello volume: volcello
3	Dimethyl Sulphide Concentration	mol m ⁻³		dms	mole_concentration_of_dimethyl_sulfide_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	dms	ocnBgchem	area: areacello volume: volcello
2	Mole Concentration of Carbonate expressed as Carbon in Sea Water	mol m ⁻³		co3	mole_concentration_of_carbonate_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	co3	ocnBgchem	area: areacello volume: volcello
2	Mole Concentration of Calcite expressed as Carbon in Sea Water at Saturation	mol m ⁻³		co3satcalc	mole_concentration_of_calcite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_at_saturation	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	co3satcalc	ocnBgchem	area: areacello volume: volcello
2	Mole Concentration of Aragonite expressed as Carbon in Sea Water at Saturation	mol m ⁻³		co3satarg	mole_concentration_of_aragonite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_at_saturation	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	co3satarg	ocnBgchem	area: areacello volume: volcello

In CMOR Table Oyr: Marine Biogeochemical 3-D Fields: Rates of Production and Removal

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell_methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell_measures	flag_values	flag_meanings
3	Primary Carbon Production by Phytoplankton	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	total primary (organic carbon) production by phytoplankton		pp	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_net_primary_production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	pp	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Primary Carbon Production by Phytoplankton due to Nitrate Uptake Alone	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Primary (organic carbon) production by phytoplankton due to nitrate uptake alone		pntrate	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_nitrate_utilization	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	pntrate	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Biogenic Iron Production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹			pbfe	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_iron_in_sea_water_due_to_biological_production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	pbfe	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Biogenic Silica Production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹			pbsi	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_silicon_in_sea_water_due_to_biological_production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	pbsi	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Calcite Production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹			pealc	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_calcite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_biological_production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	pealc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Aragonite Production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹			parag	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_aragonite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_biological_production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	parag	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Sinking Particulate Organic Carbon Flux	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			expc	sinking_mole_flux_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude olevel time	expc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Sinking Particulate Organic Nitrogen Flux	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			expn	sinking_mole_flux_of_particulate_organic_nitrogen_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude olevel time	expn	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Sinking Particulate Organic Phosphorus Flux	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			expp	sinking_mole_flux_of_particulate_organic_phosphorus_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude olevel time	expp	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Sinking Particulate Iron Flux	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			expfc	sinking_mole_flux_of_particulate_iron_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude olevel time	expfc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Sinking Particulate Silica Flux	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			expsi	sinking_mole_flux_of_particulate_silicon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude olevel time	expsi	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Sinking Calcite Flux	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			expalc	sinking_mole_flux_of_calcite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude olevel time	expalc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Sinking Aragonite Flux	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			exparg	sinking_mole_flux_of_aragonite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude olevel time	exparg	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Calcite Dissolution	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹			dcalc	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_calcite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_dissolution	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	dcalc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Aragonite Dissolution	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹			darag	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_aragonite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_dissolution	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	darag	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Diatom Primary Carbon Production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Primary (organic carbon) production by the diatom component alone		pdi	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_net_primary_production_by_diatoms	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	pdi	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Tendency of Mole Concentration of Organic Carbon in Sea Water due to Net Primary Production by Diazotrophs	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Primary (organic carbon) production by the diazotrophic phytoplankton component alone		dpocddiaz	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_net_primary_production_by_diazotrophs	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	dpocddiaz	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Tendency of Mole Concentration of Organic Carbon in Sea Water due to Net Primary Production by Calcareous Phytoplankton	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Primary (organic carbon) production by the calcite-producing phytoplankton component alone		dpocdcalc	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_net_primary_production_by_calcareous_phytoplankton	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	dpocdcalc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Tendency of Mole Concentration of Organic Carbon in Sea Water due to Net Primary Production by Picophytoplankton	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Primary (organic carbon) production by the picophytoplankton (<2 um) component alone		dpocdpico	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_net_primary_production_by_picophytoplankton	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	dpocdpico	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Other Phytoplankton Carbon Production	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Primary (organic carbon) production by other phytoplankton components alone	I think this variable might be unnecessary since it can be gotten by subtracting diatom primary carbon production from pp.	phypmisc	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_net_primary_production_by_miscellaneous_phytoplankton	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	phypmisc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Rate of Change of Dissolved Inorganic Carbon due to Biological Activity	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Net of biological terms in time rate of change of dissolved inorganic carbon		bdddic	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_dissolved_inorganic_carbon_in_sea_water_due_to_biological_processes	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	bdddic	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Rate of Change of Nitrogen Nutrient due to Biological Activity	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Net of biological terms in time rate of change of nitrogen nutrients (e.g. NO3-NH4)		bdddin	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_dissolved_inorganic_nitrogen_in_sea_water_due_to_biological_processes	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	bdddin	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Rate of Change of Dissolved Phosphate due to Biological Activity	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Net of biological terms in time rate of change of dissolved phosphate		bdddip	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_dissolved_inorganic_phosphate_in_sea_water_due_to_biological_processes	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	bdddip	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Rate of Change of Dissolved Inorganic Iron due to Biological Activity	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Net of biological terms in time rate of change of dissolved inorganic iron		bdddifc	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_dissolved_inorganic_iron_in_sea_water_due_to_biological_processes	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	bdddifc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Rate of Change of Dissolved Inorganic Silicate due to Biological Activity	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Net of biological terms in time rate of change of dissolved inorganic silicate		bdddisi	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_dissolved_inorganic_silicate_in_sea_water_due_to_biological_processes	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	bdddisi	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Rate of Change of Alkalinity due to Biological Activity	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Net of biological terms in time rate of change of alkalinity		bddtalk	tendency_of_sea_water_alkalinity_expressed_as_mole_equivalent_due_to_biological_processes	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	bddtalk	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Nonbiogenic Iron Scavenging	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Dissolved Fe removed through nonbiogenic scavenging onto particles		fescav	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_dissolved_iron_in_sea_water_due_to_scavenging_by_inorganic_particles	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	fescav	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Particle Source of Dissolved Iron	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Dissolution, remineralization and desorption of iron back to the dissolved phase		fecdis	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_dissolved_iron_in_sea_water_due_to_dissolution_from_inorganic_particles	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	fecdis	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		
3	Total Grazing of Phytoplankton by Zooplankton	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹			graz	tendency_of_mole_concentration_of_dissolved_iron_in_sea_water_due_to_grazing_of_phytoplankton	mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	graz	ocnBgchem		area: areacello volume: volcello		

Ocean layer depth field requested only from models where it can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored in the file.

Oyr

<i>Priority</i>	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Depth Below Geoid of Ocean Layer	m		This 3-d time dependent field should only be saved for models where it can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored in the file.	zfull	depth_below_geoid	m	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	zfull	ocean		area: areacello		
1	Depth Below Geoid of Interfaces Between Ocean Layers	m		This 3-d time dependent field should only be saved for models where it can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored in the file.	zhalf	depth_below_geoid	m	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude olevel time	zhalf	ocean		area: areacello		

Amon

CMOR Table Amon: Monthly Mean Atmospheric Fields and Some Surface Fields

Amon

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(All Saved on the Atmospheric Grid)

In CMOR Table Amon: 2-D fields on atmospheric grid

priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Near-Surface Air Temperature	K		normally, the temperature should be reported at the 2 meter height	tas	air_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height2m	tas	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Temperature	K	"skin" temperature (i.e., SST for open ocean)		ts	surface_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	ts	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Daily Minimum Near-Surface Air Temperature	K	monthly mean of the daily-minimum near-surface air temperature.	normally, this should be reported at the 2 meter height.	tasmin	air_temperature	K	time: minimum within days time: mean over days		real	longitude latitude time height2m	tasmin	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Daily Maximum Near-Surface Air Temperature	K	monthly mean of the daily-maximum near-surface air temperature.	normally, this should be reported at the 2 meter height.	tasmax	air_temperature	K	time: maximum within days time: mean over days		real	longitude latitude time height2m	tasmax	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Sea Level Pressure	Pa	not, in general, the same as surface pressure		psl	air_pressure_at_sea_level	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	psl	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Air Pressure	Pa	not, in general, the same as mean sea-level pressure		ps	surface_air_pressure	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	ps	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Eastward Near-Surface Wind	m s ⁻¹		normally, the wind component should be reported at the 10 meter height	uas	eastward_wind	m s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height10m	uas	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Northward Near-Surface Wind	m s ⁻¹		normally, the wind component should be reported at the 10 meter height	vas	northward_wind	m s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height10m	vas	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Near-Surface Wind Speed	m s ⁻¹	This is the mean of the speed, not the speed computed from the mean u and v components of wind	normally, the wind should be reported at the 10 meter height	sfcWind	wind_speed	m s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height10m	sfcWind	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Near-Surface Relative Humidity	%	This is the relative humidity with respect to liquid water for T> 0 C, and with respect to ice for T< 0 C.	express as a percentage. Normally, the relative humidity should be reported at the 2 meter height	hurs	relative_humidity	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height2m	hurs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Near-Surface Specific Humidity	1		Normally, the specific humidity should be reported at the 2 meter height	huss	specific_humidity	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height2m	huss	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Precipitation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface; includes both liquid and solid phases from all types of clouds (both large-scale and convective)		pr	precipitation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	pr	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Snowfall Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface; includes precipitation of all forms of water in the solid phase		prsn	snowfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	prsn	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Convective Precipitation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface; includes both liquid and solid phases.		prc	convective_precipitation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	prc	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Evaporation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface; flux of water into the atmosphere due to conversion of both liquid and solid phases to vapor (from underlying surface and vegetation)		evspsbl	water_evaporation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	evspsbl	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Snow and Ice Sublimation Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	The snow and ice sublimation flux is the loss of snow and ice mass from the surface resulting from their conversion to water vapor that enters the atmosphere.	This differs from sbl appearing in table Limon in that the flux is averaged over the entire grid cell, not just the land portion.	sbl	surface_snow_and_ice_sublimation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	sbl	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downward Eastward Wind Stress	Pa			tauu	surface_downward_eastward_stress	Pa	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	tauu	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downward Northward Wind Stress	Pa			tauv	surface_downward_northward_stress	Pa	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	tauv	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upward Latent Heat Flux	W m ⁻²	includes both evaporation and sublimation		hfls	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfls	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upward Sensible Heat Flux	W m ⁻²			hfs	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rlds	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rlds	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rlus	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rlus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsds	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsds	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsus	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsdscs	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsdscs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsuscs	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsuscs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rlsdcs	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rlsdcs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Incident Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	at the top of the atmosphere		rsdt	toa_incoming_shortwave_flux	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsdt	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Outgoing Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	at the top of the atmosphere		rsut	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsut	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Outgoing Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	at the top of the atmosphere (to be compared with satellite measurements)		rlut	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rlut	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Outgoing Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rlutes	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rlutes	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Outgoing Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsutes	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsutes	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Water Vapor Path	kg m ⁻²	vertically integrated through the atmospheric column for the whole atmospheric column, as seen from the surface or the top of the atmosphere. Include both large-scale and convective cloud.		prw	atmosphere_water_vapor_content	kg m-2	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	prw	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Total Cloud Fraction	%			clt	cloud_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clt	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Condensed Water Path	kg m ⁻²	mass of condensed (liquid + ice) water in the column divided by the area of the column (not just the area of the cloudy portion of the column). Includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeor affects the calculation of radiative transfer in model.		clwvi	atmosphere_cloud_condensed_water_content	kg m-2	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clwvi	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Ice Water Path	kg m ⁻²	mass of ice water in the column divided by the area of the column (not just the area of the cloudy portion of the column). Includes precipitating frozen hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeor affects the calculation of radiative transfer in model.		clivi	atmosphere_cloud_ice_content	kg m-2	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clivi	atmos		area: areacella		

Amon

1	Net Downward Flux at Top of Model	W m ⁻²	i.e., at the top of that portion of the atmosphere where dynamics are explicitly treated by the model. This is reported only if it differs from the net downward radiative flux at the top of the atmosphere.		rtmt	net_downward_radiative_flux_at_top_of_atmosphere_model	W m ⁻²	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rtmt	atmos	area: areacella
1	Air Pressure at Convective Cloud Base	Pa			ccb	air_pressure_at_convective_cloud_base	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	ccb	atmos	area: areacella
1	Air Pressure at Convective Cloud Top	Pa			cct	air_pressure_at_convective_cloud_top	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	cct	atmos	area: areacella
1	Fraction of Time Convection Occurs	1	Fraction of time that convection occurs in the grid cell		ci	convection_time_fraction	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	ci	atmos	area: areacella
1	Fraction of Time Shallow Convection Occurs	1	Fraction of time that shallow convection occurs in the grid cell.	For models with a distinct shallow convection scheme only.	sci	shallow_convection_time_fraction	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	sci	atmos	area: areacella
1	Carbon Mass Flux into Atmosphere Due to All Anthropogenic Emissions of CO ₂	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	This is requested only for the emission-driven coupled carbon climate model runs. Does not include natural fire sources but, includes all anthropogenic sources, including fossil fuel use, cement production, agricultural burning, and sources associated with anthropogenic land use change excluding forest regrowth.		fo2amt	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_carbon_dioxide_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_anthropogenic_emission	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	fo2amt	atmos	area: areacella
1	Carbon Mass Flux into Atmosphere Due to Fossil Fuel Emissions of CO ₂	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	This is the prescribed anthropogenic CO ₂ flux from fossil fuel use, including cement production, and flaring (but not from land-use changes, agricultural burning, forest regrowth, etc.)	This is requested only for the emission-driven coupled carbon climate model runs.	fo2fos	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_carbon_dioxide_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_emission_from_fossil_fuel_combustion	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	fo2fos	atmos	area: areacella
1	Surface Carbon Mass Flux into the Atmosphere Due to Natural Sources	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	This is what the atmosphere sees (on its own grid). This field should be equivalent to the combined natural fluxes of carbon (requested in the L _{mon} and O _{mon} tables) that account for natural exchanges between the atmosphere and land or ocean reservoirs (i.e., "net ecosystem biospheric productivity", for land, and "air to sea CO ₂ flux", for ocean.)	Report from all simulations (both emission-driven and concentration-driven) performed by models with fully interactive and responsive carbon cycles.	fo2nat	surface_upward_mass_flux_of_carbon_dioxide_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_emission_from_natural_sources	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	fo2nat	atmos	area: areacella

In CMOR Table Amon: Atmospheric 3-D fields on standard pressure levels, except 4 cloud fields which are on model levels.

Include the following mandatory pressure levels (which are available from all available reanalyses and CMIP3): 1000, 925, 850, 700, 600, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 20, and 10 hPa; Also include, when appropriate, output on the following additional pressure levels: 7, 5, 3, 2, 1 and 0.4 hPa.

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Cloud Area Fraction	%	Includes both large-scale and convective cloud.	Report on model layers (not standard pressures).	cl	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude arealv time	cl	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Mass Fraction of Cloud Liquid Water	1	Includes both large-scale and convective cloud. Calculate as the mass of cloud liquid water in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cells. Precipitating hydrometeors are included ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.	Report on model layers (not standard pressures).	clw	mass_fraction_of_cloud_liquid_water_in_air	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude arealv time	clw	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Mass Fraction of Cloud Ice	1	Includes both large-scale and convective cloud. This is calculated as the mass of cloud ice in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. It includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.	Report on model layers (not standard pressures).	cli	mass_fraction_of_cloud_ice_in_air	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude arealv time	cli	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Convective Mass Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	The net mass flux should represent the difference between the updraft and downdraft components. The flux is computed as the mass divided by the area of the grid cell.	Report on model half-levels (i.e., model layer bounds and not standard pressures).	mc	atmosphere_net_upward_convective_mass_flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude areahalf time	mc	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Air Temperature	K			ta	air_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plevs time	ta	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Eastward Wind	m s ⁻¹			ua	eastward_wind	m s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plevs time	ua	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Northward Wind	m s ⁻¹			va	northward_wind	m s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plevs time	va	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Specific Humidity	1			hus	specific_humidity	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plevs time	hus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Relative Humidity	%	This is the relative humidity with respect to liquid water for T > 0 C, and with respect to ice for T < 0 C; commonly referred to as "omega", this represents the vertical component of velocity in pressure coordinates (positive down)		hur	relative_humidity	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plevs time	hur	atmos		area: areacella		
1	omega (=dp/dt)	Pa s ⁻¹			wap	lagrangian_tendency_of_air_pressure	Pa s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plevs time	wap	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Geopotential Height	m			zg	geopotential_height	m	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plevs time	zg	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Mole Fraction of O ₃	1e-9		If this does not change over time (except possibly to vary identically over each annual cycle), report instead the variable described in the next table entry. Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)	tro3	mole_fraction_of_ozone_in_air	1e-9	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plevs time	tro3	atmos atmosChem		area: areacella		
1	Mole Fraction of O ₃	1e-9		If O ₃ does not vary from one year to the next, report 12 months, starting with January. (Note: include all 12 months even if the values don't vary seasonally.) When calling CMOR, identify this variable as tro3Clim, not tro3. If the O ₃ varies from one year to the next, then report instead the field described in the previous table entry. Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)	tro3	mole_fraction_of_ozone_in_air	1e-9	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude plevs time2	tro3Clim	atmos atmosChem	monClim	area: areacella		

Amon

1	Mole Fraction of CO2	1e-6	For some simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), this will not vary from one year to the next, and so report instead the variable described in the next table entry. If spatially uniform, omit this field, but report Total Atmospheric Mass of CO2 (see the table entry after the next one). Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)?	co2	mole_fraction_of_carbon_dioxide_in_air	1e-6	time: mean	real	longitude latitude plevs time	co2	atmos	area: areacella
1	Mole Fraction of CO2	1e-6	Report only for simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), in which the CO2 does not vary from one year to the next. Report 12 monthly values, starting with January, even if the values don't vary seasonally. When calling CMOR, identify this variable as co2Clim, not co2. If CO2 is spatially uniform, omit this field, but report Total Atmospheric Mass of CO2 (see the table entry after the next). Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)?	co2	mole_fraction_of_carbon_dioxide_in_air	1e-6	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	longitude latitude plevs time2	co2Clim	atmos	monClim area: areacella
1	Total Atmospheric Mass of CO2	kg	For some simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), this will not vary from one year to the next, and so report instead the variable described in the next table entry. If CO2 is spatially nonuniform, omit this field, but report Mole Fraction of CO2 (see the table entry before the previous one).	co2mass	atmosphere_mass_of_carbon_dioxide	kg	time: mean	real	time	co2mass	atmos	
1	Total Atmospheric Mass of CO2	kg	Report only for simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), in which the CO2 does not vary from one year to the next. Report 12 monthly values, starting with January, even if the values don't vary seasonally. When calling CMOR, identify this variable as co2massClim, not co2mass. If CO2 is spatially nonuniform, omit this field, but report Mole Fraction of CO2 (see the table entry before the previous one).	co2mass	atmosphere_mass_of_carbon_dioxide	kg	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	time2	co2massClim	atmos	monClim
1	Mole Fraction of CH4	1e-9	For some simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), this will not vary from one year to the next, and so report instead the variable described in the next table entry. If CH4 is spatially uniform, omit this field, but report Global Mean Mole Fraction of CH4 (see the table entry after the next one). Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)?	ch4	mole_fraction_of_methane_in_air	1e-9	time: mean	real	longitude latitude plevs time	ch4	atmos atmosChem	area: areacella
1	Mole Fraction of CH4	1e-9	Report only for simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), in which the CH4 does not vary from one year to the next. Report 12 monthly values, starting with January, even if the values don't vary seasonally. When calling CMOR, identify this variable as ch4global, not ch4. If CH4 is spatially uniform, omit this field, but report Global Mean Mole Fraction of CH4 (see the table entry after the next). Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)?	ch4	mole_fraction_of_methane_in_air	1e-9	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	longitude latitude plevs time2	ch4Clim	atmos atmosChem	monClim area: areacella
1	Global Mean Mole Fraction of CH4	1e-9	For some simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), this will not vary from one year to the next, and so report instead the variable described in the next table entry. If CH4 is spatially nonuniform, omit this field, but report Mole Fraction of CH4 (see the table entry before the previous one). Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)?	ch4global	mole_fraction_of_methane_in_air	1e-9	time: mean	real	time	ch4global	atmos atmosChem	
1	Global Mean Mole Fraction of CH4	1e-9	Report only for simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), in which the CH4 does not vary from one year to the next. Report 12 monthly values, starting with January, even if the values don't vary seasonally. When calling CMOR, identify this variable as ch4globalClim, not ch4global. If CH4 is spatially nonuniform, omit this field, but report Global Mean Mole Fraction of CH4 (see the table entry before the previous one). Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)?	ch4global	mole_fraction_of_methane_in_air	1e-9	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	time2	ch4globalClim	atmos atmosChem	monClim
1	Mole Fraction of N2O	1e-9	For some simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), this will not vary from one year to the next, and so report instead the variable described in the next table entry. If N2O is spatially uniform, omit this field, but report Global Mean Mole Fraction of N2O (see the table entry after the next one). Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)?	n2o	mole_fraction_of_nitrous_oxide_in_air	1e-9	time: mean	real	longitude latitude plevs time	n2o	atmos atmosChem	area: areacella
1	Mole Fraction of N2O	1e-9	Report only for simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), in which the N2O does not vary from one year to the next. Report 12 monthly values, starting with January, even if the values don't vary seasonally. When calling CMOR, identify this variable as n2oglobal, not n2o. If N2O is spatially uniform, omit this field, but report Global Mean Mole Fraction of N2O (see the table entry after the next). Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)?	n2o	mole_fraction_of_nitrous_oxide_in_air	1e-9	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	longitude latitude plevs time2	n2oClim	atmos atmosChem	monClim area: areacella

For some simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), this will not vary from one year to the next, and so report instead the variable described in the next table entry. If N2O is spatially nonuniform, omit this field, but report Mole Fraction of N2O (see the table entry before the previous one). Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)

Report only for simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), in which the N2O does not vary from one year to the next. Report 12 monthly values, starting with January, even if the values don't vary seasonally. When calling CMOR, identify this variable as ch4globalClim, not ch4global. If N2O is spatially nonuniform, omit this field, but report Global Mean Mole Fraction of N2O (see the table entry before the previous one). Are these the preferred units or should it be a unitless fraction? Should this field be reported instead on model levels? Or should we also require either the vertically integrated mole fraction (or mass?) of this species or the vertically integrated globally averaged mole fraction (or mass?)

Please let me know what (if any) other trace gas concentrations should be included. If assumed spatially uniform, report only time-series of the single value. For some simulations (e.g., prescribed concentration pi-control run), this will not vary from one year to the next, and so report values for only 12 months (starting with January). (Note: include all 12 months even if the values don't vary seasonally.)

1	Global Mean Mole Fraction of N2O	1e-9			n2oglobal	mole_fraction_of_nitrous_oxide_in_air	1e-9	time: mean	real	time	n2oglobal	atmos atmosChem				
1	Global Mean Mole Fraction of N2O	1e-9			n2oglobal	mole_fraction_of_nitrous_oxide_in_air	1e-9	time: mean within years time: mean over years	real	time2	n2oglobalClim	atmos atmosChem	monClim			
3	Global Mean Mole Fraction of CFC11	1e-12			cfc11global	mole_fraction_of_cfc11_in_air	1e-12	time: mean	real	time	cfc11global	atmos atmosChem				
3	Global Mean Mole Fraction of CFC12	1e-12			cfc12global	mole_fraction_of_cfc12_in_air	1e-12	time: mean	real	time	cfc12global	atmos atmosChem				
3	Global Mean Mole Fraction of HCFC22	1e-12			hfc22global	mole_fraction_of_hfc22_in_air	1e-12	time: mean	real	time	hfc22global	atmos atmosChem				
3	Global Mean Mole Fraction of CFC113	1e-12			cfc113global	mole_fraction_of_cfc113_in_air	1e-12	time: mean	real	time	cfc113global	atmos atmosChem				
1	Mole Fraction of Other Radiatively Important Trace Gases (That Are Evolving in Time)	1					1		real	longitude latitude plevs time	0	atmos atmosChem		area: areacella		

In CMOR Table Amon: *Climatological atmospheric 3-D pressure fields*

These field are requested *only for models in which the pressure can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored already for each variable*. Thus, the pressures on each model level are needed for height or theta-coordinate models, for example, but not sigma- or eta-coordinate models. The annual cycle climatology (computed from an appropriate segment of the pre-industrial control run) should be reported on model levels and half levels. **DO NOT REPORT ALL MONTHS FOR ALL EXPERIMENTS: Report only 12 months of data representing the climatology of the pre-industrial control run.**

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Pressure on Model Levels	Pa			pfull	air_pressure	Pa	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude alevl time2	pfull	atmos	monClim	area: areacella		
1	Pressure on Model Half-Levels	Pa			phalf	air_pressure	Pa	time: mean within years time: mean over years		real	longitude latitude alevhalf time2	phalf	atmos	monClim	area: areacella		

In CMOR Table Amon: *2-D bias-corrected fields on atmospheric grid*

These fields are derived from fields in the first table above. They have been "bias-corrected" to remove some of the unrealistic behavior caused by the initialization procedure. See recommendations for how this should be done at http://www.wcrp-climate.org/decadal/references/DCPP_Bias_Correction.pdf (Also see <http://www.wcrp-climate.org/decadal/>) *These fields should be reported only for decadal hindcast/forecast experiments.*

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Bias-Corrected Near-Surface Air Temperature	K		normally, the temperature should be reported at the 2 meter height	tasAdjust	air_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height2m	tasAdjust	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Bias-Corrected Surface Temperature	K	"skin" temperature (i.e., SST for open ocean)		tsAdjust	surface_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	tsAdjust	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Bias-Corrected Sea Level Pressure	Pa	not, in general, the same as surface pressure		pslAdjust	air_pressure_at_sea_level	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	pslAdjust	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Bias-Corrected Precipitation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface; includes both liquid and solid phases from all types of clouds (both large-scale and convective)		prAdjust	precipitation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	prAdjust	atmos		area: areacella		

CMOR Table Omon: Monthly Mean Ocean Fields, Including Biogeochemical Fields

Omon

mon

(All Saved on the Ocean Grid)

In CMOR Table Omon: Marine Biogeochemical 2-D Fields

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
2	(long name taken from 1st table in Oyr) + "	mol m ⁻³ or kg m ⁻³ or 1, consistent with first table in Oyr	(copied from 3D tracer list)	Concentrations of all 3D tracers in the uppermost ocean layer. See first table in Oyr for a complete list of these tracers. "Tracer" concentrations should be reported even if they are diagnosed rather than prognostically calculated.	include Oyr 3D tracers	(copied from 1st table in Oyr)	mol m ⁻³ or kg m ⁻³ or 1, consistent with first table in Oyr	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time depth0m	ocnBgchem			area: areacello		
1	Primary Organic Carbon Production by All Types of Phytoplankton	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Vertically integrated total primary (organic carbon) production by phytoplankton. This should equal the sum of intpdiat+intpphysic, but those individual components may be unavailable in some models.		intpp	net_primary_mole_productivity_of_carbon_by_phytoplankton	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intpp	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
2	Primary Organic Carbon Production by Phytoplankton Based on Nitrate Uptake Alone	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Vertically integrated primary (organic carbon) production by phytoplankton based on nitrate uptake alone		intpntrate	net_primary_mole_productivity_of_carbon_due_to_nitrate_utilization	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intpntrate	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
2	Primary Organic Carbon Production by Diatoms	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Vertically integrated primary (organic carbon) production by the diatom phytoplankton component alone		intpdiat	net_primary_mole_productivity_of_carbon_by_diatoms	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intpdiat	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Net Primary Mole Productivity of Carbon by Diazotrophs	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			intpdiaz	net_primary_mole_productivity_of_carbon_by_diazotrophs	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intpdiaz	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Net Primary Mole Productivity of Carbon by Calcareous Phytoplankton	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			intpcalc	net_primary_mole_productivity_of_carbon_by_calcareous_phytoplankton	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intpcalc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Net Primary Mole Productivity of Carbon by Picophytoplankton	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			intppico	net_primary_mole_productivity_of_carbon_by_picophytoplankton	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intppico	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Primary Organic Carbon Production by Other Phytoplankton	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Vertically integrated total primary (organic carbon) production by other phytoplankton components alone		intpmisc	net_primary_mole_productivity_of_carbon_by_miscellaneous_phytoplankton	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intpmisc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Iron Production	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Vertically integrated biogenic iron production		intpbfec	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_iron_due_to_biological_production	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intpbfec	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Silica Production	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Vertically integrated biogenic silica production		intpbsi	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_silicon_due_to_biological_production	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intpbsi	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Calcite Production	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Vertically integrated calcite production		intpcalcite	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_calcite_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_biological_production	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intpcalcite	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Aragonite Production	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Vertically integrated aragonite production		intparag	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_aragonite_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_biological_production	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intparag	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
1	Downward Flux of Particle Organic Carbon	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹		at 100 m depth.	epc100	sinking_mole_flux_of_particulate_organic_matter_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time depth100m	epc100	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Downward Flux of Particulate Iron	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹		at 100 m depth.	epfi100	sinking_mole_flux_of_particulate_iron_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time depth100m	epfi100	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Downward Flux of Particulate Silica	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹		at 100 m depth.	epsil100	sinking_mole_flux_of_particulate_silicon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time depth100m	epsil100	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
1	Downward Flux of Calcite	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹		at 100 m depth.	epcalc100	sinking_mole_flux_of_calcite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time depth100m	epcalc100	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
1	Downward Flux of Aragonite	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹		at 100 m depth.	eparag100	sinking_mole_flux_of_aragonite_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time depth100m	eparag100	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
2	Dissolved Inorganic Carbon Content	kg m ⁻³	Vertically integrated DIC		intdic	ocean_mass_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_carbon	kg m ⁻²	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intdic	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
1	Surface Aqueous Partial Pressure of CO2	Pa			speco2	surface_partial_pressure_of_carbon_dioxide_in_sea_water	Pa	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	speco2	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Delta PCO2	Pa		Difference between atmospheric and oceanic partial pressure of CO2 (positive meaning ocean > atmosphere)	dpeco2	surface_carbon_dioxide_partial_pressure_difference_between_sea_water_and_air	Pa	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time	dpeco2	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Delta PO2	Pa		Difference between atmospheric and oceanic partial pressure of O2 (positive meaning ocean > atmosphere)	dpo2	surface_molecular_oxygen_partial_pressure_difference_between_sea_water_and_air	Pa	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	dpo2	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
1	Surface Downward CO2 Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Gas exchange flux of CO2 (positive into ocean)		fgco2	surface_downward_mass_flux_of_carbon_dioxide_expressed_as_carbon	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	fgco2	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
1	Surface Downward O2 Flux	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Gas exchange flux of O2 (positive into ocean)		fgo2	surface_downward_mole_flux_of_molecular_oxygen	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	fgo2	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Surface Upward DMS Flux	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Gas exchange flux of DMS (positive into atmosphere)		fgdms	surface_upward_mole_flux_of_dimethyl_sulfide	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea	up	real	longitude latitude time	fgdms	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Flux of Carbon Into Ocean Surface by Runoff and Sediment Dissolution	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Carbon supply to ocean through runoff and sediment dissolution (neglects gas exchange)		fic	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_carbon_due_to_runoff_and_sediment_dissolution	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	fic	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Downward Carbon Flux at Ocean Bottom	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Carbon loss to sediments		frc	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_carbon_due_to_sedimentation	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	frc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Nitrogen Fixation Rate in Ocean	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Vertically integrated nitrogen fixation		intpn2	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_elemental_nitrogen_due_to_fixation	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	intpn2	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Surface Downward Net Flux of Nitrogen	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			fn	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_elemental_nitrogen_due_to_deposition_and_fixation_and_runoff	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	fn	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Nitrogen Loss to Sediments and through Denitrification	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			frn	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_elemental_nitrogen_due_to_denitrification_and_sedimentation	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	frn	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Surface Downward Net Flux of Iron	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Iron supply through deposition flux onto sea surface, runoff, coasts, sediments, etc		fife	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_iron_due_to_deposition_and_runoff_and_sediment_dissolution	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	fife	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Iron Loss to Sediments	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹			frfe	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_iron_due_to_sedimentation	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	frfe	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Oxygen Minimum Concentration	mol m ⁻³			o2min	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_molecular_oxygen_in_sea_water_at_shallowest_local_minimum_in_vertical_profile	mol m ⁻³	time: mean area: where sea depth: minimum		real	longitude latitude time	o2min	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Depth of Oxygen Minimum Concentration	m	Depth of vertical minimum concentration of dissolved oxygen gas (if two, then the shallower)		zo2min	depth_at_shallowest_local_minimum_in_vertical_profile_of_mole_concentration_of_dissolved_molecular_oxygen_in_sea_water	m	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	zo2min	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Calcite Saturation Depth	m	Depth of calcite saturation horizon (0 if < surface, "missing" if > bottom, if two, then the shallower)		zsatcalc	minimum_depth_of_calcite_undersaturation_in_sea_water	m	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time	zsatcalc	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Aragonite Saturation Depth	m	Depth of aragonite saturation horizon (0 if < surface, "missing" if > bottom, if two, then the shallower)		zsatara	minimum_depth_of_aragonite_undersaturation_in_sea_water	m	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	zsatara	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		
3	Rate of Change of Net Dissolved Inorganic Carbon	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹		integral over upper 100 m only.	fdiddic	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_carbon	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: where sea		real	longitude latitude time olayer100m	fdiddic	ocnBgchem		area: areacello		

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3	Rate of Change of Net Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	Net time rate of change of nitrogen nutrients (e.g. NO ₃ -NH ₄)	integral over upper 100 m only.	fddtdin	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_nitrogen	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fddtdin	ocnBgchem	area: araccello
3	Rate of Change of Net Dissolved Inorganic Phosphate	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	vertical integral of net time rate of change of phosphate	integral over upper 100 m only.	fddtdip	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_phosphorus	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fddtdip	ocnBgchem	area: araccello
3	Rate of Change of Net Dissolved Inorganic Iron	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	vertical integral of net time rate of change of dissolved inorganic iron	integral over upper 100 m only.	fddtdife	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_iron	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fddtdife	ocnBgchem	area: araccello
3	Rate of Change of Net Dissolved Inorganic Silicate	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	vertical integral of net time rate of change of dissolved inorganic silicate	integral over upper 100 m only.	fddtdisi	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_silicon	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fddtdisi	ocnBgchem	area: araccello
3	Rate of Change of Alkalinity	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	vertical integral of net time rate of change of alkalinity	integral over upper 100 m only.	fddtdalk	integral_wrt_depth_of_tendency_of_sea_water_alkalinity_expressed_as_mole_equivalent_y_expressed_as_mole_equivalent	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fddtdalk	ocnBgchem	area: araccello
3	Rate of Change of Dissolved Inorganic Carbon due to Biological Activity	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	vertical integral of net biological terms in time rate of change of dissolved inorganic carbon	integral over upper 100 m only.	fbdddic	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_carbon_due_to_biological_processes	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fbdddic	ocnBgchem	area: araccello
3	Rate of Change of Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen due to Biological Activity	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	vertical integral of net biological terms in time rate of change of nitrogen nutrients (e.g. NO ₃ -NH ₄)	integral over upper 100 m only.	fbddtdin	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_nitrogen_due_to_biological_processes	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fbddtdin	ocnBgchem	area: araccello
3	Rate of Change of Dissolved Inorganic Phosphate due to Biological Activity	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	vertical integral of net biological terms in time rate of change of phosphate	integral over upper 100 m only.	fbddtdip	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_phosphorus_due_to_biological_processes	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fbddtdip	ocnBgchem	area: araccello
3	Rate of Change of Dissolved Inorganic Iron due to Biological Activity	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	vertical integral of net biological terms in time rate of change of dissolved inorganic iron	integral over upper 100 m only.	fbddtdife	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_iron_due_to_biological_processes	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fbddtdife	ocnBgchem	area: araccello
3	Rate of Change of Dissolved Inorganic Silicate due to Biological Activity	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	vertical integral of net biological terms in time rate of change of dissolved inorganic silicate	integral over upper 100 m only.	fbddtdisi	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_dissolved_inorganic_silicon_due_to_biological_processes	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fbddtdisi	ocnBgchem	area: araccello
3	Rate of Change of Biological Alkalinity due to Biological Activity	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	vertical integral of net biological terms in time rate of change of alkalinity	integral over upper 100 m only.	fbddtdalk	integral_wrt_depth_of_tendency_of_sea_water_alkalinity_expressed_as_mole_equivalent_due_to_biological_processes	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time ocean	fbddtdalk	ocnBgchem	area: araccello

Further explanation of the fields in the following tables can be found in Griffies et al., available at http://www.climvar.org/sites/default/files/imported/organization/wgombd/references/WGOMB_CMIP5_ocean_fields.pdf.

In CMOR Table Omon: *WGOMB Table 2.2*

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Sea Water Mass	kg			masso	sea_water_mass	kg	time: mean area: sum where sea		real	time	masso	ocean				
1	Sea Water Pressure at Sea Floor	dbar			pbo	sea_water_pressure_at_sea_floor	dbar	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	pbo	ocean		area: araccello		
2	Sea Water Pressure at Sea Water Surface	dbar			pso	sea_water_pressure_at_sea_water_surface	dbar	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	pso	ocean		area: araccello		
1	Sea Water Volume	m ³			volo	sea_water_volume	m ³	time: mean area: sum where sea		real	time	volo	ocean				
1	Sea Surface Height Above Geoid	m			zos	sea_surface_height_above_geoid	m	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	zos	ocean		area: araccello		
3	Square of Sea Surface Height Above Geoid	m ²			zosq	square_of_sea_surface_height_above_geoid	m ²	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	zosq	ocean		area: araccello		
1	Global Average Sea Level Change	m			zosga	global_average_sea_level_change	m	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	time	zosga	ocean				
1	Global Average Steric Sea Level Change	m			zossqa	global_average_steric_sea_level_change	m	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	time	zossqa	ocean				
1	Global Average Thermocline Sea Level Change	m			zostoga	global_average_thermocline_sea_level_change	m	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	time	zostoga	ocean				
1	Sea Water Mass Per Unit Area	kg m ⁻²			masscello	sea_water_mass_per_unit_area	kg m ⁻²	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel time	masscello	ocean		area: araccello volume: volcello		
1	Ocean Model Cell Thickness	m			thkcello	cell_thickness	m	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel time	thkcello	ocean		area: araccello volume: volcello		
1	Sea Water Potential Temperature	K			thetao	sea_water_potential_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel time	thetao	ocean		area: araccello volume: volcello		
1	Global Average Sea Water Potential Temperature	K			thetaoga	sea_water_potential_temperature	K	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	time	thetaoga	ocean				
2	Sea Surface Temperature	K	this may differ from "surface temperature" in regions of sea ice.		tos	sea_surface_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	tos	ocean		area: araccello		
3	Square of Sea Surface Temperature	K ²			tossq	square_of_sea_surface_temperature	K ²	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	tossq	ocean		area: araccello		
1	Sea Water Salinity	psu			so	sea_water_salinity	psu	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel time	so	ocean		area: araccello volume: volcello		
1	Global Mean Sea Water Salinity	psu			soga	sea_water_salinity	psu	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	time	soga	ocean				
2	Sea Surface Salinity	psu			sos	sea_surface_salinity	psu	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	sos	ocean		area: araccello		
3	Sea Water Potential Density	kg m ⁻³			rhopot	sea_water_potential_density	kg m ⁻³	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel time	rhopot	ocean		area: araccello volume: volcello		
3	Sea Water Age Since Surface Contact	yr			agesc	sea_water_age_since_surface_contact	yr	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel time	agesc	ocean		area: araccello volume: volcello		
3	Moles Per Unit Mass of CFC-11 in Sea Water	mol kg ⁻¹			cfcl1	moles_of_cfc11_per_unit_mass_in_sea_water	mol kg ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel time	cfcl1	ocean		area: araccello volume: volcello		
3	Ocean Barotropic Mass Streamfunction	kg s ⁻¹	differs from CMIP3 because it includes mass.		msfbarot	ocean_barotropic_mass_streamfunction	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	msfbarot	ocean		area: araccello		
3	Ocean Mixed Layer Thickness Defined by Sigma T	m			mlotst	ocean_mixed_layer_thickness_defined_by_sigma_t	m	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	mlotst	ocean		area: araccello		
3	Square of Ocean Mixed Layer Thickness Defined by Sigma T	m ²			mlotstsq	square_of_ocean_mixed_layer_thickness_defined_by_sigma_t	m ²	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	mlotstsq	ocean		area: araccello		
3	Mean Daily Maximum Ocean Mixed Layer Thickness Defined by Mixing Scheme	m			omldamax	ocean_mixed_layer_thickness_defined_by_mixing_scheme	m	time: maximum within days time: mean over days		real	longitude latitude time	omldamax	ocean		area: araccello		
3	Monthly Maximum Ocean Mixed Layer Thickness Defined by Mixing Scheme	m			omlmax	ocean_mixed_layer_thickness_defined_by_mixing_scheme	m	time: maximum		real	longitude latitude time	omlmax	ocean		area: araccello		

In CMOR Table Omon: *WGOMB Table 2.3*

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Sea Water X Velocity	m s ⁻¹			uo	sea_water_x_velocity	m s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel time	uo	ocean				
1	Sea Water Y Velocity	m s ⁻¹			vo	sea_water_y_velocity	m s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel time	vo	ocean				
1	Upward Ocean Mass Transport	kg s ⁻¹	differs from CMIP3, which only had upward velocity.		wmo	upward_ocean_mass_transport	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude olevel time	wmo	ocean		area: araccello volume: volcello		

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1	Square of Upward Ocean Mass Transport	kg ² s ²		wmosq	square_of_upward_ocean_mass_transport	kg ² s ²	time: mean	real	longitude latitude olevel time	wmosq	ocean	area: areacello volume: volocello
2	Ocean Mass X Transport	kg s ¹		umo	ocean_mass_x_transport	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean	real	longitude latitude olevel time	umo	ocean	
2	Ocean Mass Y Transport	kg s ¹		vmo	ocean_mass_y_transport	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean	real	longitude latitude olevel time	vmo	ocean	
2	Ocean Meridional Overturning Mass Streamfunction	kg s ¹	differs from CMIP3 because it includes mass.	msfmyz	ocean_meridional_overturning_mass_streamfunction	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude olevel basin time	msfmyz	ocean	
2	Ocean Meridional Overturning Mass Streamfunction	kg s ¹		msfmrhov	ocean_meridional_overturning_mass_streamfunction	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude rho basin time	msfmrhov	ocean	
2	Ocean Y Overturning Mass Streamfunction	kg s ¹		msfyyz	ocean_y_overturning_mass_streamfunction	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude olevel basin time	msfyyz	ocean	
2	Ocean Y Overturning Mass Streamfunction	kg s ¹		msfyrhov	ocean_y_overturning_mass_streamfunction	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude rho basin time	msfyrhov	ocean	
3	Ocean Meridional Overturning Mass Streamfunction due to Bolus Advection	kg s ¹		msfmyzba	ocean_meridional_overturning_mass_streamfunction_due_to_bolus_advection	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude olevel basin time	msfmyzba	ocean	
3	Ocean Meridional Overturning Mass Streamfunction due to Bolus Advection	kg s ¹		msfmrhovba	ocean_meridional_overturning_mass_streamfunction_due_to_bolus_advection	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude rho basin time	msfmrhovba	ocean	
3	Ocean Y Overturning Mass Streamfunction due to Bolus Advection	kg s ¹		msfyyzba	ocean_y_overturning_mass_streamfunction_due_to_bolus_advection	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude olevel basin time	msfyyzba	ocean	
3	Ocean Y Overturning Mass Streamfunction due to Bolus Advection	kg s ¹		msfyrhovba	ocean_y_overturning_mass_streamfunction_due_to_bolus_advection	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude rho basin time	msfyrhovba	ocean	
2	Northward Ocean Heat Transport	W		hfnorth	northward_ocean_heat_transport	W	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	hfnorth	ocean	
3	Northward Ocean Heat Transport due to Bolus Advection	W	see note above.	hfnorthba	northward_ocean_heat_transport_due_to_bolus_advection	W	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	hfnorthba	ocean	
3	Northward Ocean Heat Transport due to Diffusion	W	see note above.	hfnorthdiff	northward_ocean_heat_transport_due_to_diffusion	W	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	hfnorthdiff	ocean	
2	Ocean Heat X Transport	W		hfx	ocean_heat_x_transport	W	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	hfx	ocean	
2	Ocean Heat Y Transport	W	For a model with a cartesian latlon grid, this is the same as the "Northward Ocean Heat Transport", listed a few lines above, which should be saved instead of this.	hfy	ocean_heat_y_transport	W	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	hfy	ocean	
3	Ocean Heat Y Transport due to Bolus Advection	W	see note above.	hfyba	ocean_heat_y_transport_due_to_bolus_advection	W	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	hfyba	ocean	
3	Ocean Heat Y Transport due to Diffusion	W	see note above.	hfydiff	ocean_heat_y_transport_due_to_diffusion	W	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	hfydiff	ocean	
3	Ocean Heat X Transport due to Bolus Advection	W		hfxba	ocean_heat_x_transport_due_to_bolus_advection	W	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	hfxba	ocean	
3	Ocean Heat X Transport due to Diffusion	W		hfxdiff	ocean_heat_x_transport_due_to_diffusion	W	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	hfxdiff	ocean	
2	Northward Ocean Heat Transport	W	This differs from a similar, previous entry in that northward transport across individual basins is called for, rather than the fully gridded fields.	hfbasin	northward_ocean_heat_transport	W	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude basin time	hfbasin	ocean	
3	Northward Ocean Heat Transport due to Bolus Advection	W		hfbasinba	northward_ocean_heat_transport_due_to_bolus_advection	W	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude basin time	hfbasinba	ocean	
3	Northward Ocean Heat Transport due to Diffusion	W		hfbasindiff	northward_ocean_heat_transport_due_to_diffusion	W	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude basin time	hfbasindiff	ocean	
2	Northward Ocean Heat Transport due to Gyre	W	function of latitude, basin	htovgyre	northward_ocean_heat_transport_due_to_gyre	W	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude basin time	htovgyre	ocean	
2	Northward Ocean Heat Transport due to Overturning	W	function of latitude, basin	htovovrt	northward_ocean_heat_transport_due_to_overturning	W	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude basin time	htovovrt	ocean	
2	Northward Ocean Salt Transport due to Gyre	kg s ¹	function of latitude, basin	stovgyre	northward_ocean_salt_transport_due_to_gyre	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude basin time	stovgyre	ocean	
2	Northward Ocean Salt Transport due to Overturning	kg s ¹	function of latitude, basin	stovovrt	northward_ocean_salt_transport_due_to_overturning	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean longitude: mean	real	latitude basin time	stovovrt	ocean	

In CMOR Table Omon: WGOMD Table 2.4

sea water transport through (or associated with) the following straits, openings, channels, passages, etc.: barents opening, bering_strait, canadian_archipelago, denmark_strait, drake_passage, english_channel, pacific_equatorial_undercurrent, faroe_scotland_channel, florida_bahamas_strait, fram_strait, iceland_faroe_channel, indonesian_throughflow, mozambique_channel, taiwan_luzon_straits, and windward_passage. For definitions see WGOMD document referenced above. All transports will be stored in a single variable with a dimension that covers the set of regions listed here.

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell_measures	flag values	flag meanings
2	Sea Water Transport	kg s ¹			info	sea_water_transport_across_line	kg s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	oline time	info	ocean				

In CMOR Table Omon: WGOMD Table 2.5

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell_measures	flag values	flag meanings
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2	Rainfall Flux where Ice Free Ocean over Sea	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	computed as the total mass of liquid water falling as liquid rain into the ice-free portion of the ocean divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.	pr	rainfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where ice_free_sea_over_sea	real	longitude latitude time	pr	ocean	area: areacello	
2	Snowfall Flux where Ice Free Ocean over Sea	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	computed as the total mass per unit time of solid-phase precipitation falling into the ice-free portion of the ocean divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell. (Snowfall flux includes all types of solid-phase precipitation.)	prsn	snowfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where ice_free_sea_over_sea	real	longitude latitude time	prsn	ocean	area: areacello	
2	Water Evaporation Flux Where Ice Free Ocean over Sea	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	computed as the total mass of water vapor evaporating from the ice-free portion of the ocean divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.	evs	water_evaporation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where ice_free_sea_over_sea	real	longitude latitude time	evs	ocean	area: areacello	
2	Water Flux into Sea Water From Rivers	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	computed as the river flux of water into the ocean divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.	friver	water_flux_into_sea_water_from_rivers	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time	friver	ocean	area: areacello	
2	Water Flux into Sea Water From Icebergs	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	computed as the iceberg melt water flux into the ocean divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.	faceberg	water_flux_into_sea_water_from_icebergs	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	faceberg	ocean	area: areacello	
2	Water Flux into Sea Water From Icebergs	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	computed as the iceberg melt water flux into the ocean divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.	faceberg	water_flux_into_sea_water_from_icebergs	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time	faceberg2d	ocean	area: areacello	
1	Water Flux into Sea Water due to Sea Ice Thermodynamics	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	computed as the sea ice thermodynamic water flux into the ocean divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.	fsitherm	water_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_sea_ice_thermodynamics	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time	fsitherm	ocean sealce	area: areacello	
2	Water Flux into Sea Water	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	computed as the water flux into the ocean divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell. This is the sum of the next two variables in this table.	wfo	water_flux_into_sea_water	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time	wfo	ocean	area: areacello	
2	Water Flux into Sea Water Without Flux Correction	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	computed as the water flux (without flux correction) into the ocean divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.	wfonocorr	water_flux_into_sea_water_without_flux_correction	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time	wfonocorr	ocean	area: areacello	
2	Water Flux Correction	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Positive flux implies correction adds water to ocean.	wfcorr	water_flux_correction	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	wfcorr	ocean	area: areacello

In CMOR Table Omon: *WGOMD Table 2.6*

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
2	Virtual Salt Flux into Sea Water due to Rainfall	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			vsfpr	virtual_salt_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_rainfall	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time		vsfpr	ocean		area: areacello		
2	Virtual Salt Flux into Sea Water due to Evaporation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			vsfevap	virtual_salt_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_evaporation	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time		vsfevap	ocean		area: areacello		
2	Virtual Salt Flux into Sea Water From Rivers	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			vsfriver	virtual_salt_flux_into_sea_water_from_rivers	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time		vsfriver	ocean		area: areacello		
1	Virtual Salt Flux into Sea Water due to Sea Ice Thermodynamics	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	This variable measures the virtual salt flux into sea water due to the melting of sea ice. It is set to zero in models which receive a real water flux.	The priority set by the WGOMD was 2 for this field. The sea-ice folks requested that the priority be raised to 1.	vsfsat	virtual_salt_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_sea_ice_thermodynamics	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time		vsfsat	ocean sealce		area: areacello		
2	Virtual Salt Flux into Sea Water	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		If this does not vary from one year to the next, report only a single year. Positive flux implies correction increases salinity of water. This includes all virtual salt flux, including that due to a salt flux correction.	vsf	virtual_salt_flux_into_sea_water	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time		vsf	ocean		area: areacello		
2	Virtual Salt Flux Correction	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			vsfcorr	virtual_salt_flux_correction	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time		vsfcorr	ocean		area: areacello		
1	Downward Sea Ice Basal Salt Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	This field is physical, and it arises since sea ice has a nonzero salt content, so it exchanges salt with the liquid ocean upon melting and freezing.	The priority set by the WGOMD was 2 for this field. The sea-ice folks requested that the priority be raised to 1.	sfdsi	downward_sea_ice_basal_salt_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time		sfdsi	ocean sealce		area: areacello		
2	Salt Flux into Sea Water from Rivers	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			sfriver	salt_flux_into_sea_water_from_rivers	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time		sfriver	ocean		area: areacello		

In CMOR Table Omon: *WGOMD Table 2.7*

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
2	Upward Geothermal Heat Flux at Sea Floor	W m ⁻²		If this field is time-invariant, then save it instead as one of your "fixed" fields (see the fx table)	hfgeou	upward_geothermal_heat_flux_at_sea_floor	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfgeou	ocean		area: areacello		
2	Temperature Flux due to Rainfall Expressed as Heat Flux into Sea Water	W m ⁻²	This is defined as "where ice_free_sea over sea", i.e., the total flux (considered here) entering the ice-free portion of the grid cell divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.		hfrainds	temperature_flux_due_to_rainfall_expressed_as_heat_flux_into_sea_water	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where ice_free_sea_over_sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	hfrainds	ocean		area: areacello		
2	Temperature Flux due to Evaporation Expressed as Heat Flux Out of Sea Water	W m ⁻²	This is defined as "where ice_free_sea over sea"		hfrevapds	temperature_flux_due_to_evaporation_expressed_as_heat_flux_out_of_sea_water	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where ice_free_sea_over_sea	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfrevapds	ocean		area: areacello		
2	Temperature Flux due to Runoff Expressed as Heat Flux into Sea Water	W m ⁻²		In general this should be reported as a function of depth, (i.e., it will be a function of the generic "XYZ" dimensions). Include enough depth levels to represent the non-zero values of this field everywhere on the globe.	hfrunoffds	temperature_flux_due_to_runoff_expressed_as_heat_flux_into_sea_water	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time		hfrunoffds	ocean		area: areacello		
2	Temperature Flux due to Runoff Expressed as Heat Flux into Sea Water	W m ⁻²		If only the vertically integrated runoff flux is available, report as this 2-d field; otherwise the row above should be used.	hfrunoffds	temperature_flux_due_to_runoff_expressed_as_heat_flux_into_sea_water	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time		hfrunoffds2d	ocean		area: areacello		
2	Heat Flux into Sea Water due to Snow Thermodynamics	W m ⁻²		In general this should be reported as a function of depth, (i.e., it will be a function of the generic "XYZ" dimensions). Include enough depth levels to represent the non-zero values of this field everywhere on the globe.	hfsntherm	heat_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_snow_thermodynamics	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time		hfsntherm	ocean		area: areacello		

2	Heat Flux into Sea Water due to Snow Thermodynamics	W m ⁻²		If only the vertically integrated heat flux is available, report as this 2-d field; otherwise the row above should be used.	hfsatherm2ds	heat_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_snow_thermodynamics	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time	hfsatherm2ds	ocean	area: areacello	
1	Heat Flux into Sea Water due to Frazil Ice Formation	W m ⁻²		As of May 2010, the WGOMD document recommends that this field should be saved instead of the field listed 2-lines below. In general this should be reported as a function of depth, (i.e., it will be a function of the generic "XYZ" dimensions). Include enough depth levels to represent the non-zero values of this field everywhere on the globe.	hfsifrazil	heat_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_freezing_of_frazil_ice	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	hfsifrazil	ocean seaice	area: areacello	
1	Heat Flux into Sea Water due to Frazil Ice Formation	W m ⁻²		If only the vertically integrated heat flux is available, report as this 2-d field; otherwise the row above should be used.	hfsifrazil	heat_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_freezing_of_frazil_ice	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time	hfsifrazil2d	ocean seaice	area: areacello	
1	Heat Flux into Sea Water due to Sea Ice Thermodynamics	W m ⁻²		The priority set by the WGOMD was 2 for this field. The sea-ice folks requested that the priority be raised to 1. As of May 2010, the WGOMD document recommends that instead of saving this field, the field listed 2-lines above should be saved instead. In general this should be reported as a function of depth, (i.e., it will be a function of the generic "XYZ" dimensions). Include enough depth levels to represent the non-zero values of this field everywhere on the globe.	hfsitherm2ds	heat_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_sea_ice_thermodynamics	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	hfsitherm2ds	ocean seaice	area: areacello	
1	Heat Flux into Sea Water due to Sea Ice Thermodynamics	W m ⁻²		If only the vertically integrated heat flux is available, report as this 2-d field; otherwise the row above should be used.	hfsitherm2ds	heat_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_sea_ice_thermodynamics	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time	hfsitherm2ds2d	ocean seaice	area: areacello	
2	Heat Flux into Sea Water due to Iceberg Thermodynamics	W m ⁻²		In general this should be reported as a function of depth, (i.e., it will be a function of the generic "XYZ" dimensions). Include enough depth levels to represent the non-zero values of this field everywhere on the globe.	hfbitherm2ds	heat_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_iceberg_thermodynamics	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	hfbitherm2ds	ocean	area: areacello	
2	Heat Flux into Sea Water due to Iceberg Thermodynamics	W m ⁻²		If only the vertically integrated heat flux is available, report as this 2-d field; otherwise the row above should be used.	hfbitherm2ds	heat_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_iceberg_thermodynamics	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time	hfbitherm2ds2d	ocean	area: areacello	
2	Surface Net Downward Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	This is defined as "where ice_free_sea over sea"		rlds	surface_net_downward_longwave_flux	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where ice_free_sea over sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	rlds	ocean	area: areacello
2	Surface Downward Latent Heat Flux	W m ⁻²	This is defined as "where ice_free_sea over sea"		hfls	surface_downward_latent_heat_flux	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where ice_free_sea over sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	hfls	ocean	area: areacello
2	Surface Downward Sensible Heat Flux	W m ⁻²	This is defined as "where ice_free_sea over sea"		hfs	surface_downward_sensible_heat_flux	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where ice_free_sea over sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	hfs	ocean	area: areacello
2	Net Downward Shortwave Radiation at Sea Water Surface	W m ⁻²	This is the flux into the surface of liquid sea water only. This excludes shortwave flux absorbed by sea ice, but includes any light that passes through the ice and is absorbed by the ocean.		rsnds	net_downward_shortwave_flux_at_sea_water_surface	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsnds	ocean	area: areacello
2	Downwelling Shortwave Radiation in Sea Water	W m ⁻²		In general the shortwave flux should be reported as a function of ocean depth, (i.e., it will be a function of the generic "XYZ" dimensions). Include enough depth levels to represent the non-zero values of this field everywhere on the globe.	rsdo	downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_sea_water	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude olevel time	rsdo	ocean	area: areacello
2	Heat Flux Correction	W m ⁻²		If this does not vary from one year to the next, report only a single year. Positive indicates correction adds heat to ocean.	hfcorr	heat_flux_correction	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	hfcorr	ocean	area: areacello
1	Downward Heat Flux at Sea Water Surface	W m ⁻²	This is the net flux of heat entering the liquid water column through its upper surface (excluding any "flux adjustment").		hfd	surface_downward_heat_flux_in_sea_water	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	hfd	ocean	area: areacello

In CMOR Table Omon: WGOMD Table 2.8

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
2	Surface Downward X Stress	N m ⁻²	This is the stress on the liquid ocean from overlying atmosphere, sea ice, ice shelf, etc.		tauo	surface_downward_x_stress	N m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	tauo	ocean				
2	Surface Downward Y Stress	N m ⁻²	This is the stress on the liquid ocean from overlying atmosphere, sea ice, ice shelf, etc.		tauvo	surface_downward_y_stress	N m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	tauvo	ocean				
2	Surface Downward X Stress Correction	N m ⁻²	This is the stress on the liquid ocean from overlying atmosphere, sea ice, ice shelf, etc.	If this does not vary from one year to the next, report only a single year.	taucorr	surface_downward_x_stress_correction	N m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	taucorr	ocean				
2	Surface Downward Y Stress Correction	N m ⁻²	This is the stress on the liquid ocean from overlying atmosphere, sea ice, ice shelf, etc.	If this does not vary from one year to the next, report only a single year.	tauvcorr	surface_downward_y_stress_correction	N m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	tauvcorr	ocean				

Ocean layer depth field requested only from models where it can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored in the file.

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
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1	Depth Below Geoid of Ocean Layer	m	This 3-d time dependent field should only be saved for models where it can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored in the file.	zfull	depth_below_geoid	m	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	zfull	ocean	area: areacello
1	Depth Below Geoid of Interfaces Between Ocean Layers	m	This 3-d time dependent field should only be saved for models where it can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored in the file.	zhalf	depth_below_geoid	m	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude olevel time	zhalf	ocean	area: areacello

Lmon

CMOR Table Lmon: Monthly Mean Land Fields, Including

Lmon

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Physical, Vegetation, Soil, and Biogeochemical Variables

(All fields should be saved on the atmospheric grid; unless otherwise indicated, values are averaged over only the land portion of each grid cell and report 0.0 where land fraction is 0.)

priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Moisture in Upper Portion of Soil Column	kg m ⁻²	the mass of water in all phases in a thin surface soil layer.	integrate over uppermost 10 cm	mrso	moisture_content_of_soil_layer	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time sdepth1	mrso	land		area: areacella		
1	Total Soil Moisture Content	kg m ⁻²	the mass per unit area (summed over all soil layers) of water in all phases.		mrso	soil_moisture_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	mrso	land		area: areacella		
1	Soil Frozen Water Content	kg m ⁻²	the mass (summed over all layers) of frozen water.		mrfso	soil_frozen_water_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	mrfso	land landIce		area: areacella		
1	Surface Runoff	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the total surface runoff leaving the land portion of the grid cell.		mrros	surface_runoff_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	mrros	land		area: areacella		
1	Total Runoff	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the total runoff (including "drainage" through the base of the soil model) leaving the land portion of the grid cell.		mrro	runoff_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	mrro	land		area: areacella		
2	Precipitation onto Canopy	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the precipitation flux that is intercepted by the vegetation canopy (if present in model) before reaching the ground.		prveg	precipitation_flux_onto_canopy	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	prveg	land		area: areacella		
1	Evaporation from Canopy	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the canopy evaporation+sublimation (if present in model).		evspblveg	water_evaporation_flux_from_canopy	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	evspblveg	land		area: areacella		
1	Water Evaporation from Soil	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	includes sublimation.		evspblsoi	water_evaporation_flux_from_soil	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	evspblsoi	land		area: areacella		
1	Transpiration	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			tran	transpiration_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	tran	land		area: areacella		
1	Water Content of Soil Layer	kg m ⁻²	in each soil layer, the mass of water in all phases, including ice. Reported as "missing" for grid cells occupied entirely by "sea".	If soil layer thicknesses vary from one location to another, interpolate to a standard set of depths. Ideally, the interpolation should preserve the vertical integral.	mrsl	moisture_content_of_soil_layer	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude sdepth time	mrsl	land		area: areacella		
2	Temperature of Soil	K	Temperature of each soil layer. Reported as "missing" for grid cells occupied entirely by "sea".	If soil layer thicknesses vary from one location to another, interpolate to a standard set of depths. Ideally, the interpolation should preserve the vertical integral.	tsl	soil_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude sdepth time	tsl	land		area: areacella		
1	Tree Cover Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by trees.	add scalar coordinate type tree and add "tree" to the CF area type table. Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).	treeFrac	area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	treeFrac	land		area: areacella		
1	Natural Grass Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by natural grass.	add scalar coordinate type grass and add "natural_grass" to the CF area type table. Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).	grassFrac	area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	grassFrac	land		area: areacella		
1	Shrub Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by shrub.	add scalar coordinate type shrub and add "shrub" to the CF area type table. Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).	shrubFrac	area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	shrubFrac	land		area: areacella		
1	Crop Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by crop.	add scalar coordinate type crop and add "crop" to the CF area type table. Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).	cropFrac	area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	cropFrac	land		area: areacella		
1	Anthropogenic Pasture Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by anthropogenic pasture.	add scalar coordinate type pasture and add "pasture" to the CF area type table. Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).	pastureFrac	area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	pastureFrac	land		area: areacella		
1	Bare Soil Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by bare soil.	Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).	baresoilFrac	area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time typebare	baresoilFrac	land		area: areacella		
1	Fraction of Grid Cell that is Land but Neither Vegetation-Covered nor Bare Soil	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is land and is covered by "non-vegetation" and "non-bare-soil" (e.g., urban, ice, lakes, etc.)	add scalar coordinate type land and "land" to the CF area type table.	residualFrac	area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	residualFrac	land		area: areacella		
1	Burnt Area Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by burnt vegetation.	add scalar coordinate type burnt and add "burnt_vegetation" to the CF area type table. Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).	burntArea	area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	burntArea	land		area: areacella		
Land Carbon & Biogeochemistry													land		area: areacella		
1	Carbon Mass in Vegetation	kg m ⁻²			cVeg	vegetation_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	cVeg	land		area: areacella		
1	Carbon Mass in Litter Pool	kg m ⁻²			cLitter	litter_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	cLitter	land		area: areacella		
1	Carbon Mass in Soil Pool	kg m ⁻²			cSoil	soil_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	cSoil	land		area: areacella		
1	Carbon Mass in Products of Land Use Change	kg m ⁻²			cProduct	carbon_content_of_products_of_anthropogenic_land_use_change	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	cProduct	land		area: areacella		
1	Leaf Area Index	l	a ratio obtained by dividing the total upper leaf surface area of vegetation by the (horizontal) surface area of the land on which it grows.	Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).	lai	leaf_area_index	l	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	lai	land		area: areacella		
1	Carbon Mass Flux out of Atmosphere due to Gross Primary Production on Land	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			gpp	gross_primary_productivity_of_carbon	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	down	real	longitude latitude time	gpp	land		area: areacella		
1	Carbon Mass Flux into Atmosphere due to Autotrophic (Plant) Respiration on Land	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			ra	plant_respiration_carbon_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	ra	land		area: areacella		
1	Carbon Mass Flux out of Atmosphere due to Net Primary Production on Land	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			npp	net_primary_productivity_of_carbon	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	down	real	longitude latitude time	npp	land		area: areacella		
1	Carbon Mass Flux into Atmosphere due to Heterotrophic Respiration on Land	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			rh	heterotrophic_respiration_carbon_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	rh	land		area: areacella		

Lmon

1	Carbon Mass Flux into Atmosphere due to CO2 Emission from Fire	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	CO2 emissions (expressed as a carbon mass flux) from natural fires + human ignition fires as calculated by the fire module of the DGVM, but excluding any CO2 flux from fire included in fLuc, defined below (CO2 Flux to Atmosphere from Land Use Change).	fFire	surface_upward_mass_flux_of_carbon_dioxide_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_emission_from_fires_excluding_anthropogenic_land_use_change	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	fFire	land	area: areacella
1	Carbon Mass Flux into Atmosphere due to Grazing on Land	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		fGrazing	surface_upward_mass_flux_of_carbon_dioxide_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_emission_from_grazing	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	fGrazing	land	area: areacella
1	Carbon Mass Flux into Atmosphere due to Crop Harvesting	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		fHarvest	surface_upward_mass_flux_of_carbon_dioxide_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_emission_from_crop_harvesting	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	fHarvest	land	area: areacella
1	Net Carbon Mass Flux into Atmosphere due to Land Use Change	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	human changes to land (excluding forest regrowth) accounting possibly for different time-scales related to fate of the wood, for example.	fLuc	surface_net_upward_mass_flux_of_carbon_dioxide_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_emission_from_anthropogenic_land_use_change	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	fLuc	land	area: areacella
1	Carbon Mass Flux out of Atmosphere due to Net Biospheric Production on Land	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	This is the net mass flux of carbon between land and atmosphere calculated as photosynthesis MINUS the sum of plant and soil respiration, carbon fluxes from fire, harvest, grazing and land use change. Positive flux is into the land.	nbp	surface_net_downward_mass_flux_of_carbon_dioxide_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_all_land_processes	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	down	real	longitude latitude time	nbp	land	area: areacella
1	Total Carbon Mass Flux from Vegetation to Litter	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		fVegLitter	litter_carbon_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	fVegLitter	land	area: areacella
1	Total Carbon Mass Flux from Litter to Soil	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		fLitterSoil	carbon_mass_flux_into_soil_from_litter	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	fLitterSoil	land	area: areacella
1	Total Carbon Mass Flux from Vegetation Directly to Soil	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	In some models part of carbon (e.g., root exudate) can go directly into the soil pool without entering litter.	fVegSoil	carbon_mass_flux_into_soil_from_vegetation_excluding_litter	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	fVegSoil	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass in Leaves	kg m ⁻²		cLeaf	leaf_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	cLeaf	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass in Wood	kg m ⁻²	including sapwood and hardwood.	cWood	wood_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	cWood	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass in Roots	kg m ⁻²	including fine and coarse roots.	cRoot	root_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	cRoot	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass in Other Living Compartments on Land	kg m ⁻²	e.g., labile, fruits, reserves, etc.	cMisc	miscellaneous_living_matter_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	cMisc	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass in Coarse Woody Debris	kg m ⁻²		cCwd	wood_debris_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	cCwd	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass in Above-Ground Litter	kg m ⁻²		cLitterAbove	surface_litter_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	cLitterAbove	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass in Below-Ground Litter	kg m ⁻²		cLitterBelow	subsurface_litter_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	cLitterBelow	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass in Fast Soil Pool	kg m ⁻²	fast is meant as lifetime of less than 10 years for reference climate conditions (20 C, no water limitations).	cSoilFast	fast_soil_pool_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	cSoilFast	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass in Medium Soil Pool	kg m ⁻²	medium is meant as lifetime of more than 10 years and less than 100 years for reference climate conditions (20 C, no water limitations)	cSoilMedium	medium_soil_pool_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	cSoilMedium	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass in Slow Soil Pool	kg m ⁻²	fast is meant as lifetime of more than 100 years for reference climate conditions (20 C, no water limitations)	cSoilSlow	slow_soil_pool_carbon_content	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	real	real	longitude latitude time	cSoilSlow	land	area: areacella
2	Plant Functional Type Grid Fraction	%	The categories may differ from model to model, depending on their PFT definitions. This may include natural PFTs anthropogenic PFTs, bare soil, lakes, urban areas, etc. Sum of all should equal the fraction of the grid-cell that is land.	landCoverFrac	area_fraction	%	time: mean	real	real	longitude latitude vegtype time	landCoverFrac	land	area: areacella
2	Total Primary Deciduous Tree Fraction	%	This is the fraction of the entire grid cell that is covered by "total primary deciduous trees."	treeFracPrimDec	area_fraction	%	time: mean	real	real	longitude latitude time typepdec	treeFracPrimDec	land	area: areacella
2	Total Primary Evergreen Tree Cover Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by primary evergreen trees.	treeFracPrimEver	area_fraction	%	time: mean	real	real	longitude latitude time typepever	treeFracPrimEver	land	area: areacella
2	Total Secondary Deciduous Tree Cover Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by secondary deciduous trees.	treeFracSecDec	area_fraction	%	time: mean	real	real	longitude latitude time typesdec	treeFracSecDec	land	area: areacella
2	Total Secondary Evergreen Tree Cover Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by secondary evergreen trees.	treeFracSecEver	area_fraction	%	time: mean	real	real	longitude latitude time typesever	treeFracSecEver	land	area: areacella
2	Total C3 PFT Cover Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by C3 PFTs (including grass, crops, and trees).	c3PftFrac	area_fraction	%	time: mean	real	real	longitude latitude time typec3pft	c3PftFrac	land	area: areacella
2	Total C4 PFT Cover Fraction	%	fraction of entire grid cell that is covered by C4 PFTs (including grass and crops).	c4PftFrac	area_fraction	%	time: mean	real	real	longitude latitude time typec4pft	c4PftFrac	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass Flux into Atmosphere due to Growth Autotrophic Respiration on Land	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		rGrowth	surface_upward_carbon_mass_flux_due_to_plant_respiration_for_biomass_growth	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	rGrowth	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass Flux into Atmosphere due to Maintenance Autotrophic Respiration on Land	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		rMaint	surface_upward_carbon_mass_flux_due_to_plant_respiration_for_biomass_maintenance	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	up	real	longitude latitude time	rMaint	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass Flux due to NPP Allocation to Leaf	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	This is the rate of carbon uptake by leaves due to NPP	nppLeaf	net_primary_productivity_of_carbon_accumulated_in_leaves	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	down	real	longitude latitude time	nppLeaf	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass Flux due to NPP Allocation to Wood	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	This is the rate of carbon uptake by wood due to NPP	nppWood	net_primary_productivity_of_carbon_accumulated_in_wood	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	down	real	longitude latitude time	nppWood	land	area: areacella
2	Carbon Mass Flux due to NPP Allocation to Roots	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	This is the rate of carbon uptake by roots due to NPP	nppRoot	net_primary_productivity_of_carbon_accumulated_in_roots	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land	down	real	longitude latitude time	nppRoot	land	area: areacella

need to explain how to define vegtype. To facilitate model comparison, it is also requested that the aggregated land cover types called for in lines 28 to 35 be archived (but not in this variable). Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing). Note that the "types" will be model dependent and for each type there should be a full description of the PFT (plant functional type).

Aggregation of model PFTs as defined in 1st priority to aid model intercomparison. Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).

Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).

Note that if this variable is independent of time, it should be stored only for a single time (of the user's choosing).

This flux and the one in the following row provide a breakdown of the higher priority "Autotrophic (Plant) Respiration" in an earlier row of this table; thus the sum should be identical to that.

This flux and the one in the previous row provide a breakdown of the higher priority "Autotrophic (Plant) Respiration" in an earlier row of this table; thus the sum should be identical to that.

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<p>Net Carbon Mass Flux out of Atmosphere due to Net Ecosystem Productivity on Land.</p>	<p>kg m⁻² s⁻¹</p>	<p>Natural flux of CO₂ (expressed as a mass flux of carbon) from the atmosphere to the land calculated as the difference between uptake associated with photosynthesis and the release of CO₂ from the sum of plant and soil respiration and fire. Positive flux is into the land. emissions from natural fires + human ignition fires as calculated by the fire module of the DCVM, but excluding any CO₂ flux from fire included in FLuc, defined below (CO₂ Flux to Atmosphere from Land Use Change).</p>	<p>nep</p>	<p>surface_net_downward_mass_flux_of_carbon_dioxide_expressed_as_carbon_due_to_all_land_processes_excluding_anthropogenic_land_use_change</p>	<p>kg m⁻² s⁻¹</p>	<p>time: mean area: mean where land</p>	<p>down</p>	<p>real</p>	<p>longitude latitude time</p>	<p>nep</p>	<p>land</p>	<p>area: areacella</p>
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CMOR Table LImon: Monthly Mean Land Cryosphere Fields

LImon mon

(All fields should be saved on the atmospheric grid; unless otherwise indicated, values are averaged over only the land portion of each grid cell and report 0.0 where land fraction is 0.)

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Snow Area Fraction	%	Fraction of each grid cell that is occupied by snow that rests on land portion of cell.		snc	surface_snow_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	snc	landIce land		area: areacella		
1	Surface Snow Amount	kg m ⁻²	Computed as the mass of surface snow on the land portion of the grid cell divided by the land area in the grid cell; reported as 0.0 where the land fraction is 0; excluded is snow on vegetation canopy or on sea ice.		saw	surface_snow_amount	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	saw	landIce land		area: areacella		
1	Snow Depth	m	where land over land, this is computed as the mean thickness of snow in the land portion of the grid cell (averaging over the entire land portion, including the snow-free fraction). Reported as 0.0 where the land fraction is 0.		snd	surface_snow_thickness	m	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	snd	landIce land		area: areacella		
2	Liquid Water Content of Snow Layer	kg m ⁻²	where land over land: this is computed as the total mass of liquid water contained interstitially within the snow layer of the land portion of a grid cell divided by the area of the land portion of the cell.		lwsnl	liquid_water_content_of_snow_layer	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	lwsnl	landIce land		area: areacella		
2	Snow Soot Content	kg m ⁻²	the entire land portion of the grid cell is considered, with snow soot content set to 0.0 in regions free of snow.		sootsn	soot_content_of_surface_snow	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	sootsn	landIce land		area: areacella		
1	Snow Age	day	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the mass of snow on the land portion of the grid cell, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing in regions free of snow on land.		agesno	age_of_surface_snow	day	time: mean (with samples weighted by snow mass) area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	agesno	landIce land		area: areacella		
1	Snow Internal Temperature	K	This temperature is averaged over all the snow in the grid cell that rests on land or land ice. When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the mass of snow on the land portion of the grid cell, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing in regions free of snow on land.		tsn	temperature_in_surface_snow	K	time: mean (with samples weighted by snow mass) area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	tsn	landIce land		area: areacella		
1	Surface Snow Melt	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Computed as the total surface melt water on the land portion of the grid cell divided by the land area in the grid cell; report as 0.0 for snow-free land regions; report as 0.0 where the land fraction is 0.		snm	surface_snow_melt_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	snm	landIce land		area: areacella		
1	Surface Snow and Ice Sublimation Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	The snow and ice sublimation flux is the loss of snow and ice mass resulting from their conversion to water vapor. Computed as the total sublimation on the land portion of the grid cell divided by the land area in the grid cell; reported as 0.0 for snow-free land regions; reported as 0.0 where the land fraction is 0.		sbl	surface_snow_and_ice_sublimation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	sbl	landIce land		area: areacella		
1	Downward Heat Flux into Snow Where Land over Land	W m ⁻²	the net downward heat flux from the atmosphere into the snow that lies on land divided by the land area in the grid cell; reported as 0.0 for snow-free land regions or where the land fraction is 0.		hfdsn	surface_downward_heat_flux_in_snow	W m-2	time: mean area: mean where land	down	real	longitude latitude time	hfdsn	landIce land		area: areacella		
3	Permafrost Layer Thickness	m	where land over land: This is the mean thickness of the permafrost layer in the land portion of the grid cell. Reported as 0.0 in permafrost-free regions.		tpf	permafrost_layer_thickness	m	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	tpf	landIce land		area: areacella		
3	Liquid Water Content of Permafrost Layer	kg m ⁻²	"where land over land", i.e., this is the total mass of liquid water contained within the permafrost layer within the land portion of a grid cell divided by the area of the land portion of the cell.	Why do you want to know mass of liquid water? Are you studying the seasonal melting/freezing cycle? Don't you care about how much frozen water is tied up as permafrost?	pflw	liquid_water_content_of_permafrost_layer	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	pflw	landIce land		area: areacella		

CMOR Table OImon: Monthly Mean Ocean Cryosphere Fields

OImon mon

(All saved on the ocean grid; unless otherwise indicated, values are averaged over only the ocean portion of each grid cell and report 0.0 where ocean fraction is 0.)

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Sea Ice Area Fraction	%	fraction of grid cell covered by sea ice.		sic	sea_ice_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	sic	seaIce ocean		area: areacello		
1	Sea Ice Thickness	m	the mean thickness of sea ice in the ocean portion of the grid cell (averaging over the entire ocean portion, including the ice-free fraction). Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice.		sit	sea_ice_thickness	m	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	sit	seaIce ocean		area: areacello		
1	Sea Ice Plus Surface Snow Amount	kg m ⁻²	the mass per unit area of sea ice plus snow in the ocean portion of the grid cell (averaging over the entire ocean portion, including the ice-free fraction). Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice.		sim	sea_ice_and_surface_snow_amount	kg m-2	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	sim	seaIce ocean		area: areacello		
1	Water Evaporation Flux from Sea Ice	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the average rate that water mass evaporates (or sublimates) from the sea ice surface (i.e., kg/s) divided by the area of the ocean (i.e., open ocean + sea ice) portion of the grid cell. This quantity, multiplied both by the ocean area of the grid cell and by the length of the month, should yield the total mass of water evaporated (or sublimated) from the sea ice. Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice. [This was computed differently in CMIP3.]		evap	water_evaporation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice over sea	up	real	longitude latitude time	evap	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Snow Depth	m	the mean thickness of snow in the ocean portion of the grid cell (averaging over the entire ocean portion, including the snow-free ocean fraction). Reported as 0.0 in regions free of snow-covered sea ice.		snd	surface_snow_thickness	m	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	snd	seaIce		area: areacello		
2	Surface Snow Area Fraction	%	Fraction of entire grid cell covered by snow that lies on sea ice; exclude snow that lies on land or land ice.		snc	surface_snow_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	snc	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Sea Ice Albedo	1	Reported as "missing" if there is no sunlight or if a region is free of sea ice.	This variable may be omitted unless the answers to the following questions are obvious: Will this vary from year to year or is it a property of "bare sea ice" and sun angle? How is the time-mean calculated?	ialb	sea_ice_albedo	1	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice		real	longitude latitude time	ialb	seaIce		area: areacello		
3	Sea Ice Salinity	psu	When computing the time-mean here, the time-samples, weighted by the mass of sea ice in the grid cell, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		ssi	sea_ice_salinity	psu	time: mean (weighted by mass of sea ice)		real	longitude latitude time	ssi	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Surface Temperature of Sea Ice	K	When computing the time-mean here, the time-samples, weighted by the area of sea ice in the grid cell, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice. Note this will be the surface snow temperature in regions where snow covers the sea ice.		tsice	surface_temperature	K	time: mean (weighted by area of sea ice)		real	longitude latitude time	tsice	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Temperature at Interface Between Sea Ice and Snow	K	When computing the time-mean here, the time-samples, weighted by the area of snow-covered sea ice in the grid cell, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of snow-covered sea ice.		tsnint	sea_ice_surface_temperature	K	time: mean (weighted by area of snow-covered sea ice)		real	longitude latitude time	tsnint	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Surface Rainfall Rate into the Sea Ice Portion of the Grid Cell	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	where sea ice over sea: this is the water mass per unit time falling as rain onto the sea ice portion of a grid cell divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell (including both ice-free and sea-ice covered fractions). Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice.		pr	rainfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice over sea		real	longitude latitude time	pr	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Surface Snowfall Rate into the Sea Ice Portion of the Grid Cell	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	where sea ice over sea: this is computed as the total mass per unit time of solid-phase precipitation falling onto the sea ice portion of a grid cell divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell (including both ice-free and sea-ice covered fractions). Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice. (Snowfall flux includes all types of solid-phase precipitation.)		prsn	snowfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice over sea		real	longitude latitude time	prsn	seaIce		area: areacello		
3	Age of Sea Ice	years	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the mass of sea ice in the grid cell, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		ageice	age_of_sea_ice	years	time: mean (weighted b mass of sea ice)		real	longitude latitude time	ageice	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Frazil Sea Ice Growth (Leads) Rate	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the rate of change of sea ice mass due to frazil sea ice formation divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell. Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice.		grFrazil	tendency_of_sea_ice_amount_due_to_frazil_ice_accumulation_in_leads	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	grFrazil	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Congelation Sea Ice Growth Rate	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the rate of change of sea ice mass due to congelation sea ice divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell. Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice.		grCongel	tendency_of_sea_ice_amount_due_to_congelation_ice_accumulation	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	grCongel	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Lateral Sea Ice Growth Rate	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the rate of change of sea ice mass due to lateral growth alone of the sea ice divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell. Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice.		grLateral	tendency_of_sea_ice_amount_due_to_lateral_growth_of_ice_floes	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	grLateral	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Snow-Ice Formation Rate	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the rate of change of sea ice mass due to transformation of snow to sea ice, divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell. Reported as 0.0 in regions free of snow-covered sea ice.		snoToIce	tendency_of_sea_ice_amount_due_to_snow_conversion	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	snoToIce	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Snow Melt Rate	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the rate of change of snow mass due to melting, divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell. Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice. Includes falling snow that melts on impact with the surface.		snoMelt	surface_snow_melt_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	snoMelt	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Rate of Melt at Upper Surface of Sea Ice	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the rate of change of sea ice mass due to melting at its upper surface, divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell. Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice. Does not include rate of change of snow mass.		tmelt	tendency_of_sea_ice_amount_due_to_surface_melting	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	tmelt	seaIce		area: areacello		
1	Rate of Melt at Sea Ice Base	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the rate of change of sea ice mass due to melting at its lower surface, divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell. Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice.		bmelt	tendency_of_sea_ice_amount_due_to_basal_melting	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time	bmelt	seaIce		area: areacello		
2	Sea Ice Heat Content	J m ⁻²	Ice at 0 Celsius is assumed taken to have a heat content of 0 J. When averaging over time, this quantity is weighted by the mass of sea ice. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice. Does not include heat content of snow.		hceice	integral_of_sea_ice_temperature_wrt_depth_expressed_as_heat_content	J m-2	time: mean (weighted by mass of sea ice)		real	longitude latitude time	hceice	seaIce		area: areacello		

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1	Downwelling Shortwave over Sea Ice	$W m^{-2}$	the downwelling shortwave flux in regions of sea ice divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.	priority was raised from 2 to 1 because snow albedo was deleted.	rsdssi	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	$W m^{-2}$	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice_over sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsdssi	seaIce	area: areacello
1	Upward Shortwave over Sea Ice	$W m^{-2}$	the upward shortwave flux in regions of sea ice divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.	priority was raised from 2 to 1 because snow albedo was deleted.	rsussi	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	$W m^{-2}$	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice_over sea	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsussi	seaIce	area: areacello
2	Downwelling Long Wave over Sea Ice	$W m^{-2}$	the downwelling longwave flux in regions of sea ice divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.		rdssi	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	$W m^{-2}$	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice_over sea	down	real	longitude latitude time	rdssi	seaIce	area: areacello
2	Upward Long Wave over Sea Ice	$W m^{-2}$	the upward longwave flux in regions of sea ice divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.		rlussi	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	$W m^{-2}$	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice_over sea	up	real	longitude latitude time	rlussi	seaIce	area: areacello
2	Surface Upward Sensible Heat Flux over Sea Ice	$W m^{-2}$	the upward sensible heat flux in regions of sea ice divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.		hfsi	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	$W m^{-2}$	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice_over sea	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfsi	seaIce	area: areacello
2	Surface Upward Latent Heat Flux over Sea Ice	$W m^{-2}$	the upward latent heat flux in regions of sea ice divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.		hfsi	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	$W m^{-2}$	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice_over sea	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfsi	seaIce	area: areacello
2	Sublimation over Sea Ice	$kg m^{-2} s^{-1}$	the upward flux of water vapor to the atmosphere due to sublimation of snow and sea ice in regions of sea ice divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.		sbsi	surface_snow_and_ice_sublimation_flux	$kg m^{-2} s^{-1}$	time: mean area: mean where sea_ice_over sea	up	real	longitude latitude time	sbsi	seaIce	area: areacello
1	X-Component of Sea Ice Mass Transport	$kg s^{-1}$	The sea ice mass transport is 0.0 in ice-free regions of the ocean. Snow is included in calculation of mass.		transix	sea_ice_x_transport	$kg s^{-1}$	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	transix	seaIce		
1	Y-Component of Sea Ice Mass Transport	$kg s^{-1}$	The sea ice mass transport is 0.0 in ice-free regions of the ocean. Snow is included in calculation of mass.		transiy	sea_ice_y_transport	$kg s^{-1}$	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	transiy	seaIce		
2	Sea Ice Mass Transport Through Fram Strait	$kg s^{-1}$			transifs	sea_ice_transport_across_line	$kg s^{-1}$	time: mean	real	time	transifs	seaIce		
2	X-Component of Atmospheric Stress On Sea Ice	$N m^{-2}$	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the area of sea ice, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		strairx	surface_downward_x_stress	$N m^{-2}$	time: mean (weighted by area of sea ice)	down	real	longitude latitude time	strairx	seaIce	
2	Y-Component of Atmospheric Stress On Sea Ice	$N m^{-2}$	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the area of sea ice, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		strairy	surface_downward_y_stress	$N m^{-2}$	time: mean (weighted by area of sea ice)	down	real	longitude latitude time	strairy	seaIce	
2	X-Component of Ocean Stress On Sea Ice	$N m^{-2}$	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the area of sea ice, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Report as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		strocnx	upward_x_stress_at_sea_ice_base	$N m^{-2}$	time: mean (weighted by area of sea ice)	real	longitude latitude time	strocnx	seaIce ocean		
2	Y-Component of Ocean Stress On Sea Ice	$N m^{-2}$	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the area of sea ice, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		strocnx	upward_y_stress_at_sea_ice_base	$N m^{-2}$	time: mean (weighted by area of sea ice)	real	longitude latitude time	strocnx	seaIce ocean		
2	Compressive Sea Ice Strength	$N m^{-1}$	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the area of sea ice, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		streng	compressive_strength_of_sea_ice	$N m^{-1}$	time: mean (weighted by area of sea ice)	real	longitude latitude time	streng	seaIce	area: areacello	
2	Strain Rate Divergence of Sea Ice	s^{-1}	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the area of sea ice, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		divice	divergence_of_sea_ice_velocity	s^{-1}	time: mean (weighted by area of sea ice)	real	longitude latitude time	divice	seaIce	area: areacello	
2	Eastward Derivative of Northward Sea Ice Velocity	s^{-1}	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the area of sea ice, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		eshrice	eastward_derivative_of_northward_sea_ice_velocity	s^{-1}	time: mean (weighted by area of sea ice)	real	longitude latitude time	eshrice	seaIce	area: areacello	
2	Northward Derivative of Eastward Sea Ice Velocity	s^{-1}	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the area of sea ice, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		nshrice	northward_derivative_of_eastward_sea_ice_velocity	s^{-1}	time: mean (weighted by area of sea ice)	real	longitude latitude time	nshrice	seaIce	area: areacello	
2	Sea Ice Ridging Rate	s^{-1}	When computing the time-mean here, the time samples, weighted by the area of sea ice, are accumulated and then divided by the sum of the weights. Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.		ridgice	tendency_of_sea_ice_area_fraction_due_to_ridging	s^{-1}	time: mean (weighted by area of sea ice)	real	longitude latitude time	ridgice	seaIce	area: areacello	

aero

CMOR Table **aero**: Monthly Mean Aerosol-Related Fields
(All Saved on the Atmospheric Grid)

aero

mon

In CMOR Table **aero**: 2-D fields on atmospheric grid

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings	
	Aerosol Optics																	
1	Ambient Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550 nm	1	AOD from the ambient aerosols (i.e., includes aerosol water). Does not include AOD from stratospheric aerosols if these are prescribed but includes other possible background aerosol types.		od550aer	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	od550aer	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Ambient Fine Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550 nm	1	od550 due to particles with wet diameter less than 1 um ("ambient" means "wetted"). When models do not include explicit size information, it can be assumed that all anthropogenic aerosols and natural secondary aerosols have diameter less than 1 um.		od550t1aer	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_pm1_ambient_aerosol	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	od550t1aer	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Ambient Aerosol Absorption Optical Thickness at 550 nm	1			abs550aer	atmosphere_absorption_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	abs550aer	aerosol		area: areacella			
2	Ambient Aerosol Optical Thickness at 870 nm	1	AOD from the ambient aerosols (i.e., includes aerosol water). Does not include AOD from stratospheric aerosols if these are prescribed but includes other possible background aerosol types.		od870aer	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	od870aer	aerosol		area: areacella			
	Aerosol Budgets																	
1	Rate of Emission and Production of Dry Aerosol Total Organic Matter	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	tendency of atmosphere mass content of organic matter dry aerosol due to net production and emission. This is the sum of total emission of POA and total production of SOA (see next two entries). "Mass" refers to the mass of organic matter, not mass of organic carbon alone.	This should only be reported if POA and SOA cannot be separately reported.	emioa	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_due_to_net_chemical_production_and_emission	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	emioa	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Emission Rate of Dry Aerosol Primary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	tendency of atmosphere mass content of primary organic aerosol due to emission: "mass" refers to the mass of primary organic matter, not mass of organic carbon alone.	In a previous message you said production referred to SOA, not POA, so I've removed "production" here and only use "emission". Is this o.k.?	emipoa	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_primary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_due_to_emission	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	emipoa	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Production Rate of Dry Aerosol Secondary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	tendency of atmosphere mass content of secondary organic matter dry aerosol due to net production: If model lumps SOA emissions with POA, then the sum of POA and SOA emissions is reported as POA emissions. "mass" refers to the mass of primary organic matter, not mass of organic carbon alone.		chepsoa	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_secondary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_due_to_net_chemical_production	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	chepsoa	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Emission Rate of Black Carbon Aerosol Mass	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			emibc	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_black_carbon_dry_aerosol_due_to_emission	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	emibc	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Dry Deposition Rate of Dry Aerosol Organic Matter	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	tendency of atmosphere mass content of organic dry aerosol due to dry deposition: This is the sum of dry deposition of POA and dry deposition of SOA (see next two entries). "Mass" refers to the mass of organic matter, not mass of organic carbon alone.	This should only be reported if POA and SOA cannot be separately reported.	dryoa	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	dryoa	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Dry Deposition Rate of Dry Aerosol Primary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			drypoa	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_primary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	drypoa	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Dry Deposition Rate of Dry Aerosol Secondary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			drysoa	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_secondary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	drysoa	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Dry Deposition Rate of Black Carbon Aerosol Mass	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			drybc	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_black_carbon_dry_aerosol_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	drybc	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Wet Deposition Rate of Dry Aerosol Organic Matter	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	tendency of atmosphere mass content of organic matter dry aerosols due to wet deposition: This is the sum of wet deposition of POA and wet deposition of SOA (see next two entries). "Mass" refers to the mass of organic matter, not mass of organic carbon alone.	This should only be reported if POA and SOA cannot be separately reported.	wetoa	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_due_to_wet_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	wetoa	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Wet Deposition Rate of Dry Aerosol Primary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			wetpoa	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_primary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_due_to_wet_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	wetpoa	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Wet Deposition Rate of Dry Aerosol Secondary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			wetsoa	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_secondary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_due_to_wet_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	wetsoa	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Wet Deposition Rate of Black Carbon Aerosol Mass	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			wetbc	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_black_carbon_dry_aerosol_due_to_wet_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	wetbc	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Total Emission of Primary Aerosol from Biomass Burning	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	tendency of atmosphere mass content of primary organic matter dry aerosol due to emission: This does not include sources of secondary aerosols from biomass burning aerosols, such as SO2 or SOA.		emibb	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_primary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_due_to_emission	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	emibb	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Total Emission Rate of SO2	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			emiso2	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_sulfur_dioxide_due_to_emission	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	emiso2	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Total Direct Emission Rate of SO4	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	expressed as a tendency of atmosphere mass content of SO4. Direct emission does not include secondary sulfate production.		emiso4	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_sulfate_dry_aerosol_due_to_emission	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	emiso4	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Total Emission Rate of DMS	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			emidms	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_dimethyl_sulfide_due_to_emission	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	emidms	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Dry Deposition Rate of SO2	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			dryso2	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_sulfur_dioxide_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	dryso2	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Dry Deposition Rate of SO4	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			dryso4	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_sulfate_dry_aerosol_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	dryso4	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Dry Deposition Rate of DMS	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		omit if DMS is not dry deposited in the model.	drydms	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_dimethyl_sulfide_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	drydms	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Wet Deposition Rate of SO4	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			wetso4	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_sulfate_dry_aerosol_due_to_wet_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	wetso4	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Wet Deposition Rate of SO2	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			wetso2	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_sulfur_dioxide_due_to_wet_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	wetso2	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Wet Deposition Rate of DMS	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹		omit if DMS is not wet deposited in the model.	wetdms	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_dimethyl_sulfide_due_to_wet_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	wetdms	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Total Emission Rate of NH3	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			eminh3	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_ammonia_due_to_emission	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	eminh3	aerosol		area: areacella			
3	Dry Deposition Rate of NH3	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			drynh3	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_ammonia_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	drynh3	aerosol		area: areacella			
1	Dry Deposition Rate of NH4	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			drynh4	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_ammonium_dry_aerosol_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	drynh4	aerosol		area: areacella			

acero

1	Wet Deposition Rate of NH4+NH3	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	wetnh4	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_ammonium_dry_aerosol_due_to_wet_deposition	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	wetnh4	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Total Emission Rate of Seasalt	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	emiss	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_seasalt_dry_aerosol_due_to_emission	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	emiss	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Dry Deposition Rate of Seasalt	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	dryss	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_seasalt_dry_aerosol_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	dryss	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Wet Deposition Rate of Seasalt	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	wetss	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_seasalt_dry_aerosol_due_to_wet_deposition	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	wetss	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Total Emission Rate of Dust	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	emidust	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_dust_dry_aerosol_due_to_emission	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	emidust	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Dry Deposition Rate of Dust	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	drydust	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_dust_dry_aerosol_due_to_dry_deposition	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	drydust	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Wet Deposition Rate of Dust	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	wetdust	tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_dust_dry_aerosol_due_to_wet_deposition	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	wetdust	acerosol	area: areacella
Aerosol Loads											
1	Load of Dry Aerosol Organic Matter	kg m ⁻²	loadoa	atmosphere_mass_content_of_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol	kg m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	loadoa	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Load of Dry Aerosol Primary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻²	loadpoa	atmosphere_mass_content_of_primary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol	kg m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	loadpoa	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Load of Dry Aerosol Secondary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻²	loadsoa	atmosphere_mass_content_of_secondary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol	kg m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	loadsoa	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Load of Black Carbon Aerosol	kg m ⁻²	loadbc	atmosphere_mass_content_of_black_carbon_dry_aerosol	kg m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	loadbc	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Load of SO4	kg m ⁻²	loadso4	atmosphere_mass_content_of_sulfate_dry_aerosol	kg m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	loadso4	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Load of Dust	kg m ⁻²	loaddust	atmosphere_mass_content_of_dust_dry_aerosol	kg m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	loaddust	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Load of Seasalt	kg m ⁻²	loadss	atmosphere_mass_content_of_seasalt_dry_aerosol	kg m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	loadss	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Load of NO3	kg m ⁻²	loadno3	atmosphere_mass_content_of_nitrate_dry_aerosol	kg m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	loadno3	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Load of NH4	kg m ⁻²	loadnh4	atmosphere_mass_content_of_ammonium_dry_aerosol	kg m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	loadnh4	acerosol	area: areacella
Surface Concentrations											
3	Surface Concentration of Dry Aerosol Organic Matter	kg m ⁻³	sconcoa	mass_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev1 time	sconcoa	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Surface Concentration of Dry Aerosol Primary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻³	sconcpoa	mass_concentration_of_primary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev1 time	sconcpoa	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Surface Concentration of Dry Aerosol Secondary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻³	sconcsao	mass_concentration_of_secondary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev1 time	sconcsao	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Surface Concentration of Black Carbon Aerosol	kg m ⁻³	sconcbc	mass_concentration_of_black_carbon_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev1 time	sconcbc	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Surface Concentration of SO4	kg m ⁻³	sconcsa4	mass_concentration_of_sulfate_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev1 time	sconcsa4	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Surface Concentration of Dust	kg m ⁻³	sconcdust	mass_concentration_of_dust_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev1 time	sconcdust	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Surface Concentration of Seasalt	kg m ⁻³	sconcss	mass_concentration_of_seasalt_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev1 time	sconcss	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Surface Concentration of NO3	kg m ⁻³	sconcn3	mass_concentration_of_nitrate_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev1 time	sconcn3	acerosol	area: areacella
3	Surface Concentration of NH4	kg m ⁻³	sconcnh4	mass_concentration_of_ammonium_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev1 time	sconcnh4	acerosol	area: areacella
Clouds and Radiation											
2	Surface Diffuse Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	rsdsdiff	surface_diffuse_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	rsdsdiff	acerosol land	area: areacella
2	Surface Diffuse Downwelling Clear Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	rsdscsdiff	surface_diffuse_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	rsdscsdiff	acerosol land	area: areacella
1	Cloud-Top Effective Droplet Radius	m	reffclwtop	effective_radius_of_cloud_liquid_water_particle_at_liquid_water_cloud_top	m	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	reffclwtop	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Cloud Droplet Number Concentration of Cloud Tops	m ⁻³	clndcl	number_concentration_of_cloud_liquid_water_particles_in_liquid_water_cloud_top	m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	clndcl	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Ice Crystal Number Concentration of Cloud Tops	m ⁻³	clndci	number_concentration_of_ice_crystals_in_ice_cloud_top	m-3	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	clndci	acerosol	area: areacella
1	Column Integrated Cloud Droplet Number	m ⁻²	clndvi	atmosphere_number_content_of_cloud_droplets	m-2	time: mean	real	longitude latitude time	clndvi	acerosol	area: areacella

In CMOR Table **acero**: 3-D aerosol-related concentrations and properties on model levels

aero

Report 1-year samples for years: 1850, 1870, 1890, ..., 1950, 1960, 1970, ..., 2000 of the historical run, and 2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, 2100 of the RCP runs. For AMIP runs, report 1-year samples every 10 years (1980, 1990, ..., 2010). For 2030 time-slice run, report 1-year sample for year 2035. For decadal runs, report 10th year only for 10-year predictions or hindcasts, and report year 10, 20, and 30 for 30-year predictions and hindcasts. Also report years 2010, 2011, and 2012 for years with hypothetical volcanic eruption in 2010. For the preindustrial control, report the years that correspond to years 1850, 1870, 1890, ..., 1950, 1960, 1970, ..., 2000 of the historical run and years 2010, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100 of the RCP runs.

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Ambient Aerosol Extinction at 550 nm	m ⁻¹	"ambient" means "wetted".	This and other fields in this table are 3-D.	ec550aer	volume_extinction_coefficient_in_air_due_to_ambient_aerosol	m-1	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	ec550aer	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of Dry Aerosol Organic Matter	kg m ⁻³		This is the sum of concentrations of primary and secondary organic aerosols (see next two table entries), and therefore should only be reported if those two components cannot be separately reported.	concoa	mass_concentration_of_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concoa	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of Dry Aerosol Primary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻³			conepoa	mass_concentration_of_primary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	conepoa	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of Dry Aerosol Secondary Organic Matter	kg m ⁻³		If the model lumps SOA with POA, then report their sum as POA.	concooa	mass_concentration_of_secondary_particulate_organic_matter_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concooa	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of Biomass Burning Aerosol	kg m ⁻³			concbb	mass_concentration_of_biomass_burning_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concbb	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of Black Carbon Aerosol	kg m ⁻³			concbc	mass_concentration_of_black_carbon_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concbc	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of Aerosol Water	kg m ⁻³	"ambient" means "wetted"		concaerh2o	mass_concentration_of_water_in_ambient_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concaerh2o	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of SO4	kg m ⁻³			conco4	mass_concentration_of_sulfate_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	conco4	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Mole Fraction of SO2	1			conco2	mole_fraction_of_sulfur_dioxide_in_air	1	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	conco2	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Mole Fraction of DMS	1			concdms	mole_fraction_of_dimethyl_sulfide_in_air	1	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concdms	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of NO3 Aerosol	kg m ⁻³			conco3	mass_concentration_of_nitrate_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	conco3	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of NH4	kg m ⁻³			concnh4	mass_concentration_of_ammonium_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concnh4	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of Seasalt	kg m ⁻³			concs	mass_concentration_of_seasalt_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concs	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Concentration of Dust	kg m ⁻³			concdust	mass_concentration_of_dust_dry_aerosol_in_air	kg m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concdust	aerosol		area: areacella		
2	Aerosol Number Concentration	m ⁻³			concn	number_concentration_of_ambient_aerosol_in_air	m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concn	aerosol		area: areacella		
3	Number Concentration of Nucleation Mode Aerosol	m ⁻³	includes all particles with diameter smaller than 3 nm		concnm	number_concentration_of_nucleation_mode_ambient_aerosol_in_air	m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concnm	aerosol		area: areacella		
2	Number Concentration Coarse Mode Aerosol	m ⁻³	includes all particles with diameter larger than 1 micron		concnm	number_concentration_of_coarse_mode_ambient_aerosol_in_air	m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	concnm	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Stratiform Cloud Droplet Effective Radius	m	Droplets are liquid. The effective radius is defined as the ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution and the time-mean should be calculated, weighting the individual samples by the cloudy fraction of the grid cell.		reffclws	effective_radius_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_particle	m	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	reffclws	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Convective Cloud Droplet Effective Radius	m	Droplets are liquid. The effective radius is defined as the ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution and the time-mean should be calculated, weighting the individual samples by the cloudy fraction of the grid cell.		reffclwc	effective_radius_of_convective_cloud_liquid_water_particle	m	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	reffclwc	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Cloud Droplet Number Concentration	m ⁻³	Cloud droplet number concentration in liquid clouds	Weighted by the liquid cloud fraction.	cdnc	number_concentration_of_cloud_liquid_water_particles_in_air	m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	cdnc	aerosol		area: areacella		
1	Ice Crystal Number Concentration	m ⁻³	Ice Crystal number concentration in ice clouds	Weighted by the ice cloud fraction.	inc	number_concentration_of_ice_crystals_in_air	m-3	time: mean			longitude latitude alevel time	inc	aerosol		area: areacella		

CMOR Table day: Daily Mean Atmosphere, Ocean and Surface Fields

day

day

(saved on the model's atmospheric or ocean grid, as appropriate)

In CMOR Table day: 2-D daily mean atmospheric and surface fields

The following daily mean variables should be collected for all simulations (for each ensemble member and the full duration of each experiment).

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Near-Surface Specific Humidity	1		normally, report this at 2 meters above the surface	huss	specific_humidity	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height2m	huss	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Daily Minimum Near-Surface Air Temperature	K		normally report this at 2 meters above the surface	tasmin	air_temperature	K	time: minimum		real	longitude latitude time height2m	tasmin	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Daily Maximum Near-Surface Air Temperature	K		normally report this at 2 meters above the surface	tasmax	air_temperature	K	time: maximum		real	longitude latitude time height2m	tasmax	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Near-Surface Air Temperature	K		normally report this at 2 meters above the surface	tas	air_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height2m	tas	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Precipitation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface; includes both liquid and solid phases from all types of clouds (both large-scale and convective)		pr	precipitation_flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	pr	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Sea Level Pressure	Pa			psl	air_pressure_at_sea_level	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	psl	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Daily-Mean Near-Surface Wind Speed	m s ⁻¹		normally report this at 10 meters above the surface	sfcWind	wind_speed	m s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height10m	sfcWind	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Square of Sea Surface Temperature	K ²	square of temperature of liquid ocean, averaged over the day.	Report on the ocean grid. This variable appears in WGOMD Table 2.2	tossq	square_of_sea_surface_temperature	K ²	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	tossq	ocean		area: areacello		
1	Sea Surface Temperature	K	temperature of liquid ocean. Note that the correct standard_name for this variable is "sea_surface_temperature", not "surface_temperature", but this was discovered too late to correct. To maintain consistency across CMIP5 models, the wrong standard_name will continue to be used.	Report on the ocean grid. This variable appears in WGOMD Table 2.2	tos	surface_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	tos	ocean		area: areacello		
1	Daily Maximum Ocean Mixed Layer Thickness Defined by Mixing Scheme	m		Report on the ocean grid. This variable appears in WGOMD Table 2.2	omldamax	ocean_mixed_layer_thickness_defined_by_mixing_scheme	m	time: maximum		real	longitude latitude time	omldamax	ocean		area: areacello		

The rest of the daily mean fields on this spreadsheet should be collected only for a single ensemble member of the following experiments.

experiment	time-period requested
pre-industrial controls	20 years, preferably corresponding to years 1866-2005 of the historical run
historical	Jan 1950 -- Dec 2005
future simulations driven by RCP concentrations or emissions	only years 2006-2100, 2181-2200, and 2281-2300
AMIP & 2030 time-slice run	all years

In CMOR Table day: 2-D daily-mean atmospheric and surface fields (All fields should be reported on the atmospheric grid except (as noted below) the sea ice fields, which should be reported on the ocean grid.)

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Moisture in Upper Portion of Soil Column	kg m ⁻²	the mass of water in all phases in a thin surface soil layer.	integrate over uppermost 10 cm	mrso5	moisture_content_of_soil_layer	kg m ⁻²	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time sdepth1	mrso5	land		area: areacella		
1	Near-Surface Relative Humidity	%	This is the relative humidity with respect to liquid water for T>0 C, and with respect to ice for T<0 C.	normally report this at 2 meters above the surface	rhus	relative_humidity	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height2m	rhus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Daily Minimum Relative Humidity	%	This is the relative humidity with respect to liquid water for T>0 C, and with respect to ice for T<0 C.	normally report this at 2 meters above the surface	rhusmin	relative_humidity	%	time: minimum		real	longitude latitude time height2m	rhusmin	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Daily Maximum Relative Humidity	%	This is the relative humidity with respect to liquid water for T>0 C, and with respect to ice for T<0 C.	normally report this at 2 meters above the surface	rhusmax	relative_humidity	%	time: maximum		real	longitude latitude time height2m	rhusmax	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Snow Area Fraction	%			snc	surface_snow_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	snc	land/ice land		area: areacella		
1	Total Cloud Fraction	%	for the whole atmospheric column, as seen from the surface or the top of the atmosphere. Includes both large-scale and convective cloud.		clt	cloud_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clt	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Temperature Where Land or Sea Ice	K	"skin" temperature of all surfaces except open ocean.		tsls	surface_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	tsls	land		area: areacella		
1	Surface Snow Amount	kg m ⁻²	the mass of surface snow on the land portion of the grid cell divided by the land area in the grid cell; reported as 0.0 where the land fraction is 0; excludes snow on vegetation canopy or on sea ice.		snw	surface_snow_amount	kg m ⁻²	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	snw	land/ice land		area: areacella		
1	Convective Precipitation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface; includes both liquid and solid phases.		prc	convective_precipitation_flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	prc	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Snowfall Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface; includes precipitation of all forms of water in the solid phase.		prsn	snowfall_flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	prsn	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Total Runoff	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	computed as the total runoff (including "drainage" through the base of the soil model) leaving the land portion of the grid cell divided by the land area in the grid cell.		mrro	runoff_flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	mrro	land		area: areacella		
1	Eastward Near-Surface Wind	m s ⁻¹		normally, report this at 10 meters above the surface	uas	eastward_wind	m s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height10m	uas	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Northward Near-Surface Wind	m s ⁻¹		normally, report this at 10 meters above the surface	vas	northward_wind	m s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time height10m	vas	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Daily Maximum Near-Surface Wind Speed	m s ⁻¹		normally, report this at 10 meters above the surface	sfcWindmax	wind_speed	m s ⁻¹	time: maximum		real	longitude latitude time height10m	sfcWindmax	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upward Latent Heat Flux	W m ⁻²			hfls	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	W m ⁻²	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfls	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upward Sensible Heat Flux	W m ⁻²			hfs	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	W m ⁻²	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rlds	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m ⁻²	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rlds	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rlus	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m ⁻²	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rlus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsds	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m ⁻²	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsds	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsus	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m ⁻²	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Outgoing Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	at the top of the atmosphere.		rlut	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux	W m ⁻²	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rlut	atmos		area: areacella		
1	X-Component of Sea Ice Velocity	m s ⁻¹	Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.	Report on ocean's grid.	usi	sea_ice_x_velocity	m s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	usi	sea/ice ocean		area: areacello		
1	Y-Component of Sea Ice Velocity	m s ⁻¹	Reported as "missing" in regions free of sea ice.	Report on ocean's grid.	usi	sea_ice_y_velocity	m s ⁻¹	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	usi	sea/ice ocean		area: areacello		
1	Sea Ice Area Fraction	%	fraction of grid cell covered by sea ice.	Report on ocean's grid.	sic	sea_ice_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	sic	sea/ice ocean		area: areacello		

1	Sea Ice Thickness	m	the mean thickness of sea ice in the ocean portion of the grid cell (averaging over the entire ocean portion, including the ice-free fraction). Reported as 0.0 in regions free of sea ice.	Report on ocean's grid.	sit	sea_ice_thickness	m	time: mean area: mean where sea	real	longitude latitude time	sit	seaIce ocean	area: areacello
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In CMOR Table day: daily mean 3-D atmospheric fields on the following pressure surfaces: 1000, 850, 700, 500, 250, 100, 50, and 10 hPa

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable			
												name	realm	frequency	cell measures
1	Air Temperature	K			ta	air_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plev8 time	ta	atmos		area: areacella
1	Relative Humidity	%	This is the relative humidity with respect to liquid water for T>0 C, and with respect to ice for T<0 C.		hur	relative_humidity	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plev8 time	hur	atmos		area: areacella
1	Specific Humidity	l			hus	specific_humidity	l	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plev8 time	hus	atmos		area: areacella
1	omega (-dp/dt)	Pa s ⁻¹	commonly referred to as "omega", this represents the vertical component of velocity in pressure coordinates (positive down)		wap	lagrangian_tendency_of_air_pressure	Pa s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plev8 time	wap	atmos		area: areacella
1	Northward Wind	m s ⁻¹			va	northward_wind	m s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plev8 time	va	atmos		
1	Eastward Wind	m s ⁻¹			ua	eastward_wind	m s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plev8 time	ua	atmos		
2	Geopotential Height	m			zg	geopotential_height	m	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plev8 time	zg	atmos		area: areacella

6hrLev

CMOR Table 6hrLev: Fields (Sampled Every 6 Hours) for Driving Regional Models

6hrLev

6hr

The 6-hourly data on model levels should be sampled as synoptic "snapshots" (not as 6-hour means) at 0Z, 6Z, 12Z, and 18Z and should be collected only for the following experiments and years:

experiment	reporting time-period	ensemble size	priority
historical	Jan 1950 - Dec 2005	1	highest
AMIP	all years	1	highest
RCP4.5 and RCP8.5	Jan 2006 - Dec 2100	1 for each expt.	highest
decadal hindcasts-forecasts runs initialized in late 2005, late 1980, and late 1990	all years	3 for each period	very low

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell_methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable				
												variable name	realm	frequency	cell_measures	flag_values
1	Air Temperature	K		on all model levels	ta	air_temperature	K			real	longitude latitude alevel time l	ta	atmos		area: areacella	
1	Eastward Wind	m s ⁻¹		on all model levels	ua	eastward_wind	m s-1			real	longitude latitude alevel time l	ua	atmos			
1	Northward Wind	m s ⁻¹		on all model levels	va	northward_wind	m s-1			real	longitude latitude alevel time l	va	atmos			
1	Specific Humidity	1		on all model levels	hus	specific_humidity	1			real	longitude latitude alevel time l	hus	atmos		area: areacella	
1	Surface Air Pressure	Pa	surface pressure, not mean sea level pressure		ps	surface_air_pressure	Pa			real	longitude latitude time l	ps	atmos		area: areacella	

6hrPlev

CMOR Table 6hrPlev: Fields (Sampled Every 6 Hours) for Storm-Track Analysis and other Advanced Diagnostic Applications

6hrPlev

6hr

The 6-hourly data on pressure levels should be sampled as "snapshots" (not as 6-hour means) at 0Z, 6Z, 12Z, and 18Z and should be collected only for the following experiments and years.

experiment	time-period requested
decadal hindcasts: forecasts (but very low priority)	all years
historical	Jan 1950 - Dec 2005
AMIP & 2030 time-slice	all years
RCP4.5 and RCP8.5	Jan 2006 - Dec 2100
preindustrial control	30 years -- preferably corresponding to years 1979-2008 of the historical run
Last glacial maximum paleo-run	last 30 years
mid-Holocene paleo- run	last 30 years

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell_methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell_measures	flag_values	flag_meanings
1	Eastward Wind	m s ⁻¹		on the following pressure levels: 850, 500, 250 hPa	ua	eastward_wind	m s-1			real	longitude latitude plev3 time1	ua	atmos				
1	Northward Wind	m s ⁻¹		on the following pressure levels: 850, 500, 250 hPa	va	northward_wind	m s-1			real	longitude latitude plev3 time1	va	atmos				
1	Air Temperature	K		on the following pressure levels: 850, 500, 250 hPa	ta	air_temperature	K			real	longitude latitude plev3 time1	ta	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Sea Level Pressure	Pa			psl	air_pressure_at_sea_level	Pa			real	longitude latitude time1	psl	atmos		area: areacella		

CMOR Table 3hr: 2-D Atmospheric and Surface Fields Sampled Every 3 Hours

3hr

3hr

All fields are saved on the atmospheric grid. Precipitation, clouds, and all flux variables are averaged over 3-hour intervals (0-3Z, 3-6Z, 6-9Z, 9-12Z, 12-15Z, 15-18Z, 18-21Z, 21-24Z). All other fields are sampled synoptically at 0Z, 3Z, 6Z, 9Z, 12Z, 15Z, 18Z, and 21Z.

The 3-hourly data should be collected only for the following experiments and years:

experiment	time-period requested
decadal hindcasts/forecasts (but very low priority)	all years
historical	Jan 1960 - Dec 2005
AMIP & future 2030 time-slice	all years
future simulations driven by RCP concentrations or emissions	Jan 2026 - Dec 2045, Jan 2081-Dec 2100, 2181-2200, and 2281-2300
pre-industrial control	30 years (ideally the years corresponding to years 121-150 of abrupt 4XCO2 run)
1 percent per year CO2	last 30 years
control SST climatology (6.2a)	all years
CO2 forcing (6.2b), anthropogenic aerosol forcing (6.4a), and sulfate aerosol forcing (6.4b)	all years
abrupt 4XCO2 (6.3)	first 5 years and years 121-150
abrupt 4XCO2 ensemble (6.3-E)	all years

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
												name					
1	Precipitation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface; includes both liquid and solid phases. This is the 3-hour mean precipitation flux.		pr	precipitation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time:mean		real	longitude latitude time	pr	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Near-Surface Air Temperature	K	This is sampled synoptically.	normally, report at 2 meters above the surface	tas	air_temperature	K	time: point		real	longitude latitude time1 height2m	tas	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upward Latent Heat Flux	W m ⁻²	This is the 3-hour mean flux.		hfls	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfls	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upward Sensible Heat Flux	W m ⁻²	This is the 3-hour mean flux.		hfs	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	This is the 3-hour mean flux.		rlds	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rlds	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	This is the 3-hour mean flux.		rlus	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rlus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	This is the 3-hour mean flux.		rsds	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsds	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	This is the 3-hour mean flux.		rsus	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Eastward Near-Surface Wind Speed	m s ⁻¹	This is sampled synoptically.		uas	eastward_wind	m s-1	time: point		real	longitude latitude time1 height10m	uas	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Northward Near-Surface Wind Speed	m s ⁻¹	This is sampled synoptically.		vas	northward_wind	m s-1	time: point		real	longitude latitude time1 height10m	vas	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Near-Surface Specific Humidity	l	This is sampled synoptically.	normally, report at 2 meters above the surface	huss	specific_humidity	l	time: point		real	longitude latitude time1 height2m	huss	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Moisture in Upper Portion of Soil Column	kg m ⁻²	the mass of water in all phases in a thin surface soil layer.	integrate over uppermost 10 cm	mrsos	moisture_content_of_soil_layer	kg m-2	time: point area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time1 sdpth1	mrsos	land		area: areacella		
1	Surface Temperature Where Land or Sea Ice	K	"skin" temperature of all surfaces except open ocean, sampled synoptically.		tsi	surface_temperature	K	time: point		real	longitude latitude time1	tsi	land		area: areacella		
1	Sea Surface Temperature	K	temperature of surface of open ocean, sampled synoptically.		tso	sea_surface_temperature	K	time: point area: mean where sea		real	longitude latitude time1	tso	ocean		area: areacella		
1	Convective Precipitation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface. This is a 3-hour mean convective precipitation flux.		prc	convective_precipitation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time:mean		real	longitude latitude time	prc	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Snowfall Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	at surface. Includes precipitation of all forms water in the solid phase. This is the 3-hour mean snowfall flux.		prsn	snowfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time:mean		real	longitude latitude time	prsn	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Total Runoff	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	the total runoff (including "drainage" through the base of the soil model) leaving the land portion of the grid cell divided by the land area in the grid cell, averaged over the 3-hour interval.		mrro	runoff_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean area: mean where land		real	longitude latitude time	mrro	land		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	This is a 3-hour mean flux.		rldscs	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rldscs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	This is a 3-hour mean flux.		rsdscs	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsdscs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	This is a 3-hour mean flux.		rsusc	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsusc	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Air Pressure	Pa	sampled synoptically to diagnose atmospheric tides, this is better than mean sea level pressure.		ps	surface_air_pressure	Pa	time: point		real	longitude latitude time1	ps	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Total Cloud Fraction	%	for the whole atmospheric column, as seen from the surface or the top of the atmosphere. Include both large-scale and convective cloud. This is a 3-hour mean.		clt	cloud_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clt	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Diffuse Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	This is a 3-hour mean flux.		rsdscs	surface_diffuse_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	rsdscs	atmos		area: areacella		

CMOR Table cfMon: CFMIP Monthly-Mean Cloud Diagnostic Fields
(All Saved on the Atmospheric Grid)

cfMon mon

For further guidance, please see [see http://cfmip.metoffice.com](http://cfmip.metoffice.com)

The spread sheet "CFMIP output" specifies the simulations and time-periods for which the cloud diagnostic fields listed on this spread sheet should be saved.

In CMOR Table cfMon: "CFMIP monthly 3D"--monthly mean 3-D fields on model levels (or half levels in the case of fluxes). Different GCMs will have different cloud tendency terms due to different model formulations. Please submit the terms which are necessary to close the stratiform cloud water budget of your model. If your model contains terms not listed here, please email mark.webb@metoffice.gov.uk to request an update to the table.

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Upwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	Includes also the fluxes at the surface and TOA.		rlu	upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rlu	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Upwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	Includes also the fluxes at the surface and TOA.		rsu	upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rsu	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Downwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	Includes also the fluxes at the surface and TOA.		rls	downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rls	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	Includes also the fluxes at the surface and TOA.		rsd	downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rsd	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Upwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	Includes also the fluxes at the surface and TOA.		rlucs	upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rlucs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Upwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	Includes also the fluxes at the surface and TOA.		rsucs	upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rsucs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Downwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	Includes also the fluxes at the surface and TOA.		rlsdc	downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rlsdc	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Downwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²	Includes also the fluxes at the surface and TOA.		rsdc	downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rsdc	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Air Temperature	K			ta	air_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	ta	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Air Temperature	K s ⁻¹			tnt	tendency_of_air_temperature	K s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tnt	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Air Temperature due to Advection	K s ⁻¹			tnta	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_advection	K s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tnta	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Air Temperature due to Diabatic Processes	K s ⁻¹			tntmp	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_model_physics	K s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tntmp	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Air Temperature Due to Stratiform Cloud and Precipitation and Boundary Layer Mixing	K s ⁻¹			tntsepbl	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_stratiform_cloud_and_precipitation_and_boundary_layer_mixing	K s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tntsepbl	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Air Temperature due to Radiative Heating	K s ⁻¹			tnttr	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_radiative_heating	K s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tnttr	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Air Temperature due to Moist Convection	K s ⁻¹			tntc	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_convection	K s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tntc	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Relative Humidity	%			hur	relative_humidity	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	hur	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Specific Humidity	1			hus	specific_humidity	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	hus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity	s ⁻¹			tnhus	tendency_of_specific_humidity	s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tnhus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity due to Advection	s ⁻¹			tnhusa	tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_advection	s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tnhusa	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity due to Convection	s ⁻¹			tnhusc	tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_convection	s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tnhusc	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity due to Diffusion	s ⁻¹			tnhusd	tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_diffusion	s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tnhusd	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity due to Stratiform Cloud Condensation and Evaporation	s ⁻¹			tnhusepbl	tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_stratiform_cloud_and_precipitation_and_boundary_layer_mixing	s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tnhusepbl	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity due to Model Physics	s ⁻¹	This includes sources and sinks from parameterized physics (e.g. convection, stratiform condensation/evaporation, etc.) and excludes sources and sinks from resolved dynamics and diffusion.		tnhusmp	tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_model_physics	s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	tnhusmp	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Eddy Viscosity Coefficients for Momentum	m ² s ⁻¹			eviscu	atmosphere_momentum_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	eviacu	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Eddy Diffusivity Coefficients for Temperature	m ² s ⁻¹			eviset	atmosphere_heat_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	eviset	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Convective Cloud Area Fraction	%			clc	convective_cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	clc	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Mass Fraction of Convective Cloud Liquid Water	1	Calculated as the mass of convective cloud liquid water in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.		clwc	mass_fraction_of_convective_cloud_liquid_water_in_air	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	clwc	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Mass Fraction of Convective Cloud Ice	1	Calculated as the mass of convective cloud ice in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.		clic	mass_fraction_of_convective_cloud_ice_in_air	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	clic	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Stratiform Cloud Area Fraction	%			cls	stratiform_cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	cls	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water	1	Calculated as the mass of stratiform cloud liquid water in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.		clws	mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alevel time	clws	atmos		area: areacella		

2	Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice	1	Calculated as the mass of stratiform cloud ice in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.	clis	mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air	1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	clis	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Updraft Convective Mass Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Calculated as the convective mass flux divided by the area of the whole grid cell (not just the area of the cloud).	mcu	atmosphere_updraft_convective_mass_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	mcu	atmos	area: areacella
2	Downdraft Convective Mass Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Calculated as the convective mass flux divided by the area of the whole grid cell (not just the area of the cloud).	med	atmosphere_downdraft_convective_mass_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	med	atmos	area: areacella
2	Shallow Convective Mass Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	The net mass flux represents the difference between the updraft and downdraft components. For models with a distinct shallow convection scheme, this is calculated as convective mass flux divided by the area of the whole grid cell (not just the area of the cloud).	smc	atmosphere_net_upward_shallow_convective_mass_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	smc	atmos	area: areacella
2	Deep Convective Mass Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	The net mass flux represents the difference between the updraft and downdraft components. This is calculated as the convective mass flux divided by the area of the whole grid cell (not just the area of the cloud).	dmc	atmosphere_net_upward_deep_convective_mass_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	dmc	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water In Air	s ⁻¹		tsclw	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclw	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water In Air Due To Cloud Microphysics	s ⁻¹		tsclwcm	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_cloud_microphysics	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwcm	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water In Air Due To Boundary Layer Mixing	s ⁻¹		tsclwbl	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_boundary_layer_mixing	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwbl	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water In Air Due To Bergeron Findeisen Process To Cloud Ice	s ⁻¹		tsclwbfpci	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_bergeron_findeisen_process_to_cloud_ice	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwbfpci	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water due to Condensation and Evaporation	s ⁻¹		tsclwce	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_condensation_and_evaporation	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwce	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water Due to Convective Detrainment	s ⁻¹		tsclwcd	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_convective_detrainment	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwcd	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water due to Homogeneous Nucleation	s ⁻¹		tsclwhon	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_homogeneous_nucleation	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwhon	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water due to Heterogeneous Nucleation	s ⁻¹		tsclwhcn	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_heterogeneous_nucleation	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwhcn	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water due to Riming	s ⁻¹		tsclwri	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_riming	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwri	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water due to Accretion to Rain	s ⁻¹		tsclwar	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_accretion_to_rain	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwar	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water due to Accretion to Snow	s ⁻¹		tsclwas	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_accretion_to_snow	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwas	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water due to Melting From Cloud Ice	s ⁻¹		tsclwmi	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_melting_from_cloud_ice	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwmi	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water due to Autoconversion	s ⁻¹		tsclwac	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_autoconversion	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwac	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water due to Advection	s ⁻¹		tsclwa	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air_due_to_advection	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclwa	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice In Air	s ⁻¹		tscli	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tscli	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice In Air Due To Cloud Microphysics	s ⁻¹		tsclciem	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_cloud_microphysics	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclciem	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice In Air Due To Boundary Layer Mixing	s ⁻¹		tsclcibl	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_boundary_layer_mixing	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclcibl	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice In Air Due To Bergeron Findeisen Process From Cloud Liquid	s ⁻¹		tsclcbfpci	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_bergeron_findeisen_process_from_cloud_liquid	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclcbfpci	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice Due Convective Detrainment	s ⁻¹		tsclclid	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_convective_detrainment	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclclid	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Homogeneous Nucleation	s ⁻¹		tsclclhon	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_homogeneous_nucleation	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclclhon	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Heterogeneous Nucleation From Cloud Liquid	s ⁻¹		tsclclhcnc	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_heterogeneous_nucleation_from_cloud_liquid_water	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclclhcnc	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Heterogeneous Nucleation From Water Vapor	s ⁻¹		tsclclhcnv	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_heterogeneous_nucleation_from_water_vapor	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclclhcnv	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Riming From Cloud Liquid	s ⁻¹		tsclclricl	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_riming_from_cloud_liquid_water	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclclricl	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Riming From Rain	s ⁻¹		tsclclrir	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_riming_from_rain	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclclrir	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Deposition and Sublimation	s ⁻¹		tsclclids	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_deposition_and_sublimation	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclclids	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Aggregation	s ⁻¹		tsclclag	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_aggregation	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclclag	atmos	area: areacella	
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Accretion to Snow	s ⁻¹		tsclclias	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_accretion_to_snow	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsclclias	atmos	area: areacella	

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2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Evaporation of Melting Ice	s ¹		tsnclemi	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_evaporation_of_melting_ice	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsnclemi	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Melting to Rain	s ¹		tsnclimr	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_melting_to_rain	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsnclimr	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Melting to Cloud Liquid	s ¹		tsncliml	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_melting_to_cloud_liquid_water	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncliml	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Icefall	s ¹		tsncliif	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_icefall	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncliif	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice due to Advection	s ¹		tsncsla	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air_due_to_advection	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncsla	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Condensed Water In Air	s ¹		tsncsw	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_condensed_water_in_air	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncsw	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Condensed Water In Air Due To Cloud Microphysics	s ¹		tsncswcm	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_condensed_water_in_air_due_to_cloud_microphysics	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncswcm	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Condensed Water In Air Due To Boundary Layer Mixing	s ¹		tsncswbl	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_condensed_water_in_air_due_to_boundary_layer_mixing	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncswbl	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Condensed Water due to Condensation and Evaporation	s ¹	condensed water includes both liquid and ice.	tsncswce	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_condensed_water_in_air_due_to_condensation_and_evaporation	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncswce	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Condensed Water due to Autoconversion to Rain	s ¹	condensed water includes both liquid and ice.	tsncswacr	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_condensed_water_in_air_due_to_autoconversion_to_rain	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncswacr	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Condensed Water due to Autoconversion to Snow	s ¹	condensed water includes both liquid and ice.	tsncswacs	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_condensed_water_in_air_due_to_autoconversion_to_snow	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncswacs	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Condensed Water due to Icefall	s ¹	condensed water includes both liquid and ice.	tsncswif	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_condensed_water_in_air_due_to_icefall	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncswif	atmos	area: areacella
2	Tendency of Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Condensed Water due to Advection	s ¹	condensed water includes both liquid and ice.	tsncswa	tendency_of_mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_condensed_water_in_air_due_to_advection	s-1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alevel time	tsncswa	atmos	area: areacella

In CMOR Table cfMon: "CFMIP monthly 4xCO2 2D" -- monthly mean 2D TOA radiative fluxes calculated by instantaneously quadrupling CO2.

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	TOA Outgoing Shortwave Radiation in 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rsu4co2	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsu4co2	atmos	area: areacella			
1	TOA Outgoing Longwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rlu4co2	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rlu4co2	atmos	area: areacella			
1	TOA Outgoing Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rsuts4co2	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsuts4co2	atmos	area: areacella			
1	TOA Outgoing Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rluts4co2	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rluts4co2	atmos	area: areacella			

In CMOR Table cfMon: "CFMIP monthly 4xCO2 3D" -- monthly mean 3-D radiative fluxes calculated by instantaneously quadrupling CO2. On model half levels, including the surface and the Top of the Atmosphere.

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Upwelling Longwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rlu4co2	upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rlu4co2	atmos	area: areacella			
1	Upwelling Shortwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rsu4co2	upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rsu4co2	atmos	area: areacella			
1	Downwelling Longwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rlu4co2	downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rlu4co2	atmos	area: areacella			
1	Downwelling Shortwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rsu4co2	downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rsu4co2	atmos	area: areacella			
1	Upwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rlucs4co2	upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rlucs4co2	atmos	area: areacella			
1	Upwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rsucs4co2	upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rsucs4co2	atmos	area: areacella			
1	Downwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rlucs4co2	downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rlucs4co2	atmos	area: areacella			
1	Downwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation 4XCO2 Atmosphere	W m ⁻²			rsucs4co2	downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude alevhalf time	rsucs4co2	atmos	area: areacella			

In CMOR Table cfMon: "CFMIP monthly inline" -- monthly mean in line ISCCP and CALIPSO/PARASOL simulator output

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	ISCCP Total Cloud Fraction	%			clisccp	cloud_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clisccp	atmos	area: areacella			
1	ISCCP Mean Cloud Albedo	1	time-means weighted by the ISCCP Total Cloud Fraction - see http://cfmip.meto.fce.com/COSP.html		albiscp	cloud_albedo	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	albiscp	atmos	area: areacella			
1	ISCCP Mean Cloud Top Pressure	Pa	time-means weighted by the ISCCP Total Cloud Fraction - see http://cfmip.meto.fce.com/COSP.html		petiscp	air_pressure_at_cloud_top	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	petiscp	atmos	area: areacella			
1	ISCCP Cloud Area Fraction	%		7 levels x 7 tau	clisccp	isccp_cloud_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude plev7 tau time	clisccp	atmos	area: areacella			
1	CALIPSO Total Cloud Fraction	%			clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clcalipso	atmos	area: areacella			
1	CALIPSO Low Level Cloud Fraction	%			clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time p840	clcalipso	atmos	area: areacella			
1	CALIPSO Mid Level Cloud Fraction	%			clmcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time p560	clmcalipso	atmos	area: areacella			
1	CALIPSO High Level Cloud Fraction	%			clhcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time p220	clhcalipso	atmos	area: areacella			
1	CALIPSO Cloud Fraction	%		40 height levels	clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alt40 time	clcalipso	atmos	area: areacella			

1	PARASOL Reflectance	1	This is reflectance as seen at the top of the atmosphere.	5 bins of solar zenith angle.	parasoRefl	toa_bidirectional_reflectance	1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude sza5 time	parasoRefl	atmos	area: areacella
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CMOR Table **cfOff**: "CFMIP monthly offline" Cloud Diagnostic Fields
(All Saved on the Atmospheric Grid)

cfOff

mon

For further guidance, please see <http://cfmip.metoffice.com>

The spread sheet "CFMIP output" specifies the simulations and time-periods for which the cloud diagnostic fields listed on this spread sheet should be saved.

CMOR Table **cfOff**: "CFMIP monthly offline" -- monthly mean CloudSat/CALIPSO/PARASOL simulator output

(Calculate monthly means by averaging the orbital curtain output from CFMIP_orbital_offline. The difference between similar variables appearing in this and the previous table is in the spatial sampling and time period requested. The previous table builds monthly means from global fields, whereas this table below uses only data along the satellite track for a short period of time (one year). This will enable studies of the impact of the satellite sampling in the comparisons.)

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	CALIPSO Cloud Fraction	%		40 height levels	cicalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude ab40 time	cicalipso	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CALIPSO Cloud Fraction Undetected by CloudSat	%	Clouds detected by CALIPSO but below the detectability threshold of CloudSat	40 height levels	cicalipso2	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude ab40 time	cicalipso2	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CloudSat Radar Reflectivity	1	CFADs (Cloud Frequency Altitude Diagrams) are joint height - radar reflectivity (or lidar scattering ratio) distributions	40 levelsx15 bins	cfadDbze94	histogram_of_equivalent_reflectivity_factor_over_height_above_reference_ellipsoid	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude ab40 dbze time	cfadDbze94	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CALIPSO Scattering Ratio	1	CFADs (Cloud Frequency Altitude Diagrams) are joint height - radar reflectivity (or lidar scattering ratio) distributions.	40 levelsx15 bins	cfadLidars532	histogram_of_backscattering_ratio_over_height_above_reference_ellipsoid	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude ab40 scatratio time	cfadLidars532	atmos		area: areacella		
1	PARASOL Reflectance	1	Simulated reflectance from PARASOL as seen at the top of the atmosphere for 5 solar zenith angles. Valid only over ocean and for one viewing direction (viewing zenith angle of 30 degrees and relative azimuth angle 320 degrees).		parasoRefI	toa_bidirectional_reflectance	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude sza5 time	parasoRefI	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CALIPSO Total Cloud Fraction	%			ctcalipso	cloud_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	ctcalipso	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CALIPSO Low Level Cloud Fraction	%			clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time p840	clcalipso	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CALIPSO Mid Level Cloud Fraction	%			clmcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time p560	clmcalipso	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CALIPSO High Level Cloud Fraction	%			chlcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time p220	chlcalipso	atmos		area: areacella		

CMOR Table cfDay: CFMIP Daily-Mean Cloud Diagnostic Fields

cfDay

day

(All Saved on the Atmospheric Grid)

For further guidance, please see <http://cfmip.metoffice.com>

The spread sheet "CFMIP output" specifies the simulations and time-periods for which the cloud diagnostic fields listed on this spread sheet should be saved.

In CMOR Table cfDay: "CFMIP daily 2D" -- daily mean 2-D fields including inline ISCCP/CloudSat/CALIPSO/ PARASOL simulator output

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell_methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell_measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Surface Air Pressure	Pa			ps	surface_air_pressure	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	ps	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Incident Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsdt	toa_incoming_shortwave_flux	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsdt	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Outgoing Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsut	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux	W m-2	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	rsut	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsdscs	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsdscs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsuscs	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsuscs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			ridscs	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	ridscs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Outgoing Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rluts	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rluts	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Outgoing Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsuts	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsuts	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Total Cloud Fraction	%	for the whole atmospheric column, as seen from the surface or the top of the atmosphere. Includes both large-scale and convective cloud.		clt	cloud_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clt	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Condensed Water Path	kg m ⁻²	calculate mass of condensed (liquid + ice) water in the column divided by the area of the column (not just the area of the cloudy portion of the column). This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.		chvvi	atmosphere_cloud_condensed_water_content	kg m-2	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	chvvi	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Ice Water Path	kg m ⁻²	calculate mass of ice water in the column divided by the area of the column (not just the area of the cloudy portion of the column). This includes precipitating frozen hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.		clivi	atmosphere_cloud_ice_content	kg m-2	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clivi	atmos		area: areacella		
1	omega (=dp/dt)	Pa s ⁻¹	at 500 hPa level; commonly referred to as "omega", this represents the vertical component of velocity in pressure coordinates (positive down)		wap500	lagrangian_tendency_of_air_pressure	Pa s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time p500	wap500	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Air Temperature	K		at 700 hPa level	ta700	air_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time p700	ta700	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Air Pressure at Convective Cloud Base	Pa			ecb	air_pressure_at_convective_cloud_base	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	ecb	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Air Pressure at Convective Cloud Top	Pa			ect	air_pressure_at_convective_cloud_top	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	ect	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Convective Precipitation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹			pre	convective_precipitation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	pre	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upward Latent Heat Flux	W m ⁻²			hfls	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfls	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upward Sensible Heat Flux	W m ⁻²			hfs	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	hfs	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rlds	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rlds	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rhus	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rhus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsds	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	down	real	longitude latitude time	rsds	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Surface Upwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rsus	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rsus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	TOA Outgoing Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²			rlut	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux	W m-2	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude time	rlut	atmos		area: areacella		
1	ISCCP Total Total Cloud Fraction	%			cltscsp	cloud_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	cltscsp	atmos		area: areacella		
1	ISCCP Mean Cloud Albedo	1	time-means are weighted by the ISCCP Total Cloud Fraction - see http://cfmip.metoffice.com/COSP.html		albiscsp	cloud_albedo	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	albiscsp	atmos		area: areacella		
1	ISCCP Mean Cloud Top Pressure	Pa	time-means are weighted by the ISCCP Total Cloud Fraction - see http://cfmip.metoffice.com/COSP.html		petiscsp	air_pressure_at_cloud_top	Pa	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	petiscsp	atmos		area: areacella		
1	PARASOL Reflectance	1	Simulated reflectance from PARASOL as seen at the top of the atmosphere for 5 solar zenith angles. Valid only over ocean and for one viewing direction (viewing zenith angle of 30 degrees and relative azimuth angle 320 degrees).		parasoRef1	toa_bidirectional_reflectance	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude sza5 time	parasoRef1	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CALIPSO Total Cloud Fraction	%			clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clcalipso	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CALIPSO Low Level Cloud Fraction	%			clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clcalipso	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CALIPSO Mid Level Cloud Fraction	%			clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clcalipso	atmos		area: areacella		
1	CALIPSO High Level Cloud Fraction	%			clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude time	clcalipso	atmos		area: areacella		

In CMOR Table cfDay: "CFMIP daily 3D" --daily mean 3-D fields on model levels plus CALIPSO and ISCCP cloud fractions

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell_methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell_measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	Eastward Wind	m s ⁻¹			ua	eastward_wind	m s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alev el time	ua	atmos				
1	Northward Wind	m s ⁻¹			va	northward_wind	m s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alev el time	va	atmos				
1	Air Temperature	K			ta	air_temperature	K	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alev el time	ta	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Specific Humidity	1			hus	specific_humidity	1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alev el time	hus	atmos		area: areacella		
1	omega (=dp/dt)	Pa s ⁻¹	commonly referred to as "omega", this represents the vertical component of velocity in pressure coordinates (positive down)		wap	lagrangian_tendency_of_air_pressure	Pa s-1	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alev el time	wap	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Geopotential Height	m			zg	geopotential_height	m	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alev el time	zg	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Relative Humidity	%	This is the relative humidity with respect to liquid water for T>0 C, and with respect to ice for T<=0 C.		hur	relative_humidity	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alev el time	hur	atmos		area: areacella		
1	Cloud Area Fraction in Atmosphere Layer	%			cl	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean		real	longitude latitude alev el time	cl	atmos		area: areacella		

cfDay

1	Mass Fraction of Cloud Liquid Water	1	Calculated as the mass of cloud liquid water in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.	clw	mass_fraction_of_cloud_liquid_water_in_air	1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev el time	clw	atmos	area: areacella	
1	Mass Fraction of Cloud Ice	1	Calculated as the mass of cloud ice in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.	cli	mass_fraction_of_cloud_ice_in_air	1	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev el time	cli	atmos	area: areacella	
1	Convective Mass Flux	$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	The net mass flux should represent the difference between the updraft and downdraft components. This is calculated as the convective mass flux divided by the area of the whole grid cell (not just the area of the cloud). Report on model half-levels (i.e., model layer bounds and not standard pressures).	mc	atmosphere_net_upward_convective_mass_flux	$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	time: mean	up	real	longitude latitude alev half time	mc	atmos	area: areacella
1	CALIPSO Cloud Fraction	%	40 levels	ckalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean	real	longitude latitude ab40 time	ckalipso	atmos	area: areacella	
1	ISCCP Cloud Area Fraction	%	7 levels x 7 tau	clisccp	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: mean	real	longitude latitude plev 7 tau time	clisccp	atmos	area: areacella	
1	Pressure on Model Levels	Pa	This field is needed only for models in which the pressure can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored already for each variable. Thus, the pressures are needed for height or theta-coordinate models, for example, but not sigma- or eta-coordinate models.	pfull	air_pressure	Pa	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev el time	pfull	atmos	area: areacella	
1	Pressure on Model Half-Levels	Pa	This field is needed only for models in which the pressure can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored already for each variable. Thus, the pressures are needed for height or theta-coordinate models, for example, but not sigma- or eta-coordinate models.	phalf	air_pressure	Pa	time: mean	real	longitude latitude alev half time	phalf	atmos	area: areacella	

CMOR Table cf3hr: CFMIP 3-Hourly Cloud Diagnostic Fields
(All Saved on the Atmospheric Grid)

cf3hr

3hr

For further guidance, please see <http://cfmip.metoffice.com>

The spread sheet "CFMIP output" specifies the simulations and time-periods for which the cloud diagnostic fields listed on this spread sheet should be saved.

In CMOR Table cf3hr: "CFMIP 3-hourly orbital offline" -- CloudSat/CALIPSO/PARASOL simulator output in orbital curtain format

(For most of these variables, extract simulator input variables from models along A-train orbits, and run COSP on these in 'offline' mode.)

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	CALIPSO Cloud Area Fraction	%		at 40 height levels	clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: point		real	location alt40 time1	clcalipso	atmos				
1	CALIPSO Cloud Fraction Undetected by CloudSat	%	Clouds detected by CALIPSO but below the detectability threshold of CloudSat	at 40 height levels	clcalipso2	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: point		real	location alt40 time1	clcalipso2	atmos				
1	CloudSat Radar Reflectivity CFAD	1	CFADs (Cloud Frequency Altitude Diagrams) are joint height-radar reflectivity (or lidar scattering ratio) distributions.	40 levels x 15 bins	cfadDbze94	histogram_of_equivalent_reflectivity_factor_over_height_above_reference_ellipsoid	1	time: point		real	location alt40 dbze time1	cfadDbze94	atmos				
1	CALIPSO Scattering Ratio CFAD	1	CFADs (Cloud Frequency Altitude Diagrams) are joint height-radar reflectivity (or lidar scattering ratio) distributions.	40 levels x 15 bins	cfadLidars52	histogram_of_backscattering_ratio_over_height_above_reference_ellipsoid	1	time: point		real	location alt40 scatratio time1	cfadLidars52	atmos				
1	PARASOL Reflectance	1	Simulated reflectance from PARASOL as seen at the top of the atmosphere for 5 solar zenith angles. Valid only over ocean and for one viewing direction (viewing zenith angle of 30 degrees and relative azimuth angle 320 degrees).		parasoRefI	toa_bidirectional_reflectance	1	time: point		real	location sza5 time1	parasoRefI	atmos				
1	CALIPSO Total Cloud Fraction	%			clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction	%	time: point		real	location time1	clcalipso	atmos				
1	CALIPSO Low Level Cloud Fraction	%			clcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: point		real	location time1 p840	clcalipso	atmos				
1	CALIPSO Mid Level Cloud Fraction	%			clmcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: point		real	location time1 p560	clmcalipso	atmos				
1	CALIPSO High Level Cloud Fraction	%			chlcalipso	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: point		real	location time1 p220	chlcalipso	atmos				
1	Longitude	degrees_east		is a function of time. Note that the CF convention and CMOR2 require that this field will be included in each file that contains a variable that is a function of the "location" dimension, so there is no need to save this field by itself.	lon	longitude	degrees_east	time: point		real	location time1	longitude	atmos				
1	Latitude	degrees_north		the above comment also applies to latitude.	lat	latitude	degrees_north	time: point		real	location time1	latitude	atmos				
1	Offset Time	day		this "offset time" should be added to the value stored in the "time dimension" to get the actual time. This actual time is the time (UTC) of the corresponding point in the satellite orbit used to extract the model data.	toffset	time	day			real	location time1	toffset	atmos				

In CMOR Table cf3hr: "CFMIP 3-hourly inline" -- 2-D fields as specified in the Amon table plus convective cloud fraction and 3-D fields on model levels (or half levels, as indicated) sampled synoptically every 3 hours (i.e., not time-mean) at 0Z, 3Z, 6Z, 9Z, 12Z, 15Z, 18Z, and 21Z.

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	(use names for Amon 2D table)			This table includes all the 2-D variables listed in the Amon table, omitting, however, the daily maximum and minimum temperatures. All variables should be reported as synoptic fields, not daily means.	include Amon 2D			time: point		real	longitude latitude time1		atmos		area: areacella		
1	Convective Cloud Fraction	%	for the whole atmospheric column, as seen from the surface or the top of the atmosphere. Includes only convective cloud.	Besides the quantities from the Amon table, this is the only other 2-D field in this table.	cltc	convective_cloud_area_fraction	%	time: point		real	longitude latitude time1	cltc	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Altitude of Model Full-Levels	m	This is actual height above mean sea level, not geopotential height		zfull	height_above_reference_ellipsoid	m	time: point		real	longitude latitude alevel time1	zfull	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Altitude of Model Half-Levels	m	This is actual height above mean sea level, not geopotential height. This is actual height above mean sea level, not geopotential height. Includes both the top of the model atmosphere and surface levels.		zhalf	height_above_reference_ellipsoid	m	time: point		real	longitude latitude alevhalf time1	zhalf	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Pressure at Model Full-Levels	Pa		provide this field for models in which the pressure can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored already for each variable. Thus, the pressures are needed for height or theta-coordinate models, for example, but not sigma- or eta-coordinate models.	pfull	air_pressure	Pa	time: point		real	longitude latitude alevel time1	pfull	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Pressure at Model Half-Levels	Pa		provide this field for models in which the pressure can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored already for each variable. Thus, the pressures are needed for height or theta-coordinate models, for example, but not sigma- or eta-coordinate models.	phalf	air_pressure	Pa	time: point		real	longitude latitude alevhalf time1	phalf	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Air Temperature	K			ta	air_temperature	K	time: point		real	longitude latitude alevel time1	ta	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Mass Fraction of Water	1	includes all phases of water		h2o	mass_fraction_of_water_in_air	1	time: point		real	longitude latitude alevel time1	h2o	atmos		area: areacella		
2	Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water	1	Calculated as the mass of stratiform cloud liquid water in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.		clws	mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_in_air	1	time: point		real	longitude latitude alevel time1	clws	atmos		area: areacella		

2	Mass Fraction of Stratiform Cloud Ice	1	Calculate as the mass of stratiform cloud ice in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. Include precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeor affects the calculation of radiative transfer in model.	clis	mass_fraction_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_in_air	1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	clis	atmos	area: areacella
2	Mass Fraction of Convective Cloud Liquid Water	1	Calculated as the mass of convective cloud liquid water in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.	clwc	mass_fraction_of_convective_cloud_liquid_water_in_air	1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	clwc	atmos	area: areacella
2	Mass Fraction of Convective Cloud Ice	1	Calculated as the mass of convective cloud ice in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.	clic	mass_fraction_of_convective_cloud_ice_in_air	1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	clic	atmos	area: areacella
2	Hydrometeor Effective Radius of Stratiform Cloud Liquid Water	m	This is defined as the in-cloud ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution (obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell).	reffclws	effective_radius_of_stratiform_cloud_liquid_water_particle	m	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	reffclws	atmos	area: areacella
2	Hydrometeor Effective Radius of Stratiform Cloud Ice	m	This is defined as the in-cloud ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution (obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell).	reffclis	effective_radius_of_stratiform_cloud_ice_particle	m	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	reffclis	atmos	area: areacella
2	Hydrometeor Effective Radius of Convective Cloud Liquid Water	m	This is defined as the in-cloud ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution (obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell).	reffclwc	effective_radius_of_convective_cloud_liquid_water_particle	m	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	reffclwc	atmos	area: areacella
2	Hydrometeor Effective Radius of Convective Cloud Ice	m	This is defined as the in-cloud ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution (obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell).	reffclic	effective_radius_of_convective_cloud_ice_particle	m	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	reffclic	atmos	area: areacella
2	Stratiform Graupel Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	report on model half-levels	grpblprof	large_scale_graupel_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	grpblprof	atmos	area: areacella
2	Convective Rainfall Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	report on model half-levels	preprof	convective_rainfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	preprof	atmos	area: areacella
2	Stratiform Rainfall Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	report on model half-levels	prlsprof	large_scale_rainfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	prlsprof	atmos	area: areacella
2	Convective Snowfall Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	convective phase: report on model half-levels	prsnconv	convective_snowfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	prsnconv	atmos	area: areacella
2	Stratiform Snowfall Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	large-scale precipitation of all forms of water in the solid phase. report on model half-levels	prlsns	large_scale_snowfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	prlsns	atmos	area: areacella
2	Hydrometeor Effective Radius of Stratiform Graupel	m	This is defined as the in-cloud ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution (obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell).	reffgrpls	effective_radius_of_stratiform_cloud_graupel_particle	m	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	reffgrpls	atmos	area: areacella
2	Hydrometeor Effective Radius of Convective Rainfall	m	This is defined as the in-cloud ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution (obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell).	reffrainc	effective_radius_of_convective_cloud_rain_particle	m	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	reffrainc	atmos	area: areacella
2	Hydrometeor Effective Radius of Stratiform Rainfall	m	This is defined as the in-cloud ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution (obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell).	reffrainns	effective_radius_of_stratiform_cloud_rain_particle	m	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	reffrainns	atmos	area: areacella
2	Hydrometeor Effective Radius of Convective Snowfall	m	This is defined as the in-cloud ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution (obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell).	reffsnwc	effective_radius_of_convective_cloud_snow_particle	m	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	reffsnwc	atmos	area: areacella
2	Hydrometeor Effective Radius of Stratiform Snowfall	m	This is defined as the in-cloud ratio of the third moment over the second moment of the particle size distribution (obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell).	reffsnws	effective_radius_of_stratiform_cloud_snow_particle	m	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	reffsnws	atmos	area: areacella
2	Stratiform Cloud Optical Depth	1	This is the in-cloud optical depth obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell.	dtaus	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_stratiform_cloud	1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	dtaus	atmos	area: areacella
2	Convective Cloud Optical Depth	1	This is the in-cloud optical depth obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell.	dtauc	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_convective_cloud	1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	dtauc	atmos	area: areacella
2	Stratiform Cloud Emissivity	1	This is the in-cloud emissivity obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell.	dems	stratiform_cloud_longwave_emissivity	1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	dems	atmos	area: areacella
2	Convective Cloud Emissivity	1	This is the in-cloud emissivity obtained by considering only the cloudy portion of the grid cell.	demc	convective_cloud_longwave_emissivity	1	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	demc	atmos	area: areacella
2	Convective Cloud Area Fraction	%		clc	convective_cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	clc	atmos	area: areacella
2	Stratiform Cloud Area Fraction	%		cls	stratiform_cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: point	real	longitude latitude alevel time1	cls	atmos	area: areacella

CMOR Table cfSites: CFMIP high frequency Cloud Diagnostic Fields
(sampled only at specified locations)

cfSites subhr

For further guidance, please see <http://cfmip.metoffice.com>

The spread sheet "CFMIP output" specifies the simulations and time-periods for which the cloud diagnostic fields listed on this spread sheet should be saved.

CMOR Table cfSites: "CFMIP Timestep Station Data" -- 2-D fields from the Amon table and 3-D fields on model levels sampled at 20 to 30 minute intervals at 73 specified locations for aquaplanet experiments and 119 specified locations for other experiments (see <http://cfmip.metoffice.com/cfmip2/pointlocations.txt>). Note that the column labeled "CMOR dimensions" indicates that these variables are a function of longitude and latitude. When writing the data to the netCDF file, however, the axis for the 119 (or 73) locations will be a simple index named "site", and CMOR defines this as a "grid axis" that has associated longitudes and latitudes. See CMOR documentation for instructions on defining a 1-dimensional grid axis of this kind.

The sampling interval should be the integer multiple of the model time-step that is nearest to 30 minutes and divides into 60 minutes with no remainder, e.g. (30->30,20->20,15->30,10->30). Outputs should be instantaneous (not time mean) and from nearest gridbox (no spatial interpolation.) Note that except for the quantities appearing in the Amon spreadsheet (first line of table below), all other fields are 3-D.

Priority	long name	units	comment	questions & notes	output variable name	standard name	unformatted units	cell methods	positive	type	CMOR dimensions	CMOR variable name	realm	frequency	cell measures	flag values	flag meanings
1	(use names from Amon 2D table)			This table includes the 2-D variables listed in the "Amon" spreadsheet, omitting, however, the daily maximum and minimum temperatures. All variables should be reported as synoptic fields, not daily means.	include Amon 2D			time: point		real	site time1		atmos				
1	Cloud Area Fraction	%	Includes both large-scale and convective cloud.		cl	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	%	time: point		real	alevel site time1	cl	atmos				
1	Mass Fraction of Cloud Liquid Water	1	Includes both large-scale and convective cloud. This is the mass of cloud liquid water in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.		clw	mass_fraction_of_cloud_liquid_water_in_air	1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	clw	atmos				
1	Mass Fraction of Cloud Ice	1	Includes both large-scale and convective cloud. This is the mass of cloud ice in the grid cell divided by the mass of air (including the water in all phases) in the grid cell. This includes precipitating hydrometeors ONLY if the precipitating hydrometeors affect the calculation of radiative transfer in model.		cli	mass_fraction_of_cloud_ice_in_air	1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	cli	atmos				
1	Convective Mass Flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	The net mass flux should represent the difference between the updraft and downdraft components. This is calculated as the convective mass flux divided by the area of the whole grid cell (not just the area of the updrafts).	Report on model half-levels (i.e., interfaces between model layers).	mc	atmosphere_net_upward_convective_mass_flux	kg m-2 s-1	time: point	up	real	alevhalf site time1	mc	atmos				
1	Air Temperature	K			ta	air_temperature	K	time: point		real	alevel site time1	ta	atmos				
1	Eastward Wind	m s ⁻¹			ua	eastward_wind	m s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	ua	atmos				
1	Northward Wind	m s ⁻¹			va	northward_wind	m s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	va	atmos				
1	Specific Humidity	1			hus	specific_humidity	1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	hus	atmos				
1	Relative Humidity	%	This is the relative humidity with respect to liquid water for T>=0 C, and with respect to ice for T<=0 C.		hur	relative_humidity	%	time: point		real	alevel site time1	hur	atmos				
1	omega (-dp/dt)	Pa s ⁻¹	commonly referred to as "omega", this represents the vertical component of velocity in pressure coordinates (positive down)		wap	lagrangian_tendency_of_air_pressure	Pa s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	wap	atmos				
1	Geopotential Height	m			zg	geopotential_height	m	time: point		real	alevel site time1	zg	atmos				
1	Upwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²		Report on model half-levels (i.e., interfaces between model layers).	rhu	upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: point	up	real	alevhalf site time1	rhu	atmos				
1	Upwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²		Report on model half-levels (i.e., interfaces between model layers).	rsu	upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: point	up	real	alevhalf site time1	rsu	atmos				
1	Downwelling Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²		Report on model half-levels (i.e., interfaces between model layers).	rld	downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: point	down	real	alevhalf site time1	rld	atmos				
1	Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²		Report on model half-levels (i.e., interfaces between model layers).	rsd	downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	time: point	down	real	alevhalf site time1	rsd	atmos				
1	Upwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²		Report on model half-levels (i.e., interfaces between model layers).	rhuks	upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: point	up	real	alevhalf site time1	rhuks	atmos				
1	Upwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²		Report on model half-levels (i.e., interfaces between model layers).	rsuks	upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: point	up	real	alevhalf site time1	rsuks	atmos				
1	Downwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	W m ⁻²		Report on model half-levels (i.e., interfaces between model layers).	rldcs	downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: point	down	real	alevhalf site time1	rldcs	atmos				
1	Downwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	W m ⁻²		Report on model half-levels (i.e., interfaces between model layers).	rsdcs	downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	W m-2	time: point	down	real	alevhalf site time1	rsdcs	atmos				
1	Tendency of Air Temperature	K s ⁻¹			tnt	tendency_of_air_temperature	K s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	tnt	atmos				
1	Tendency of Air Temperature due to Advection	K s ⁻¹			tnta	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_advection	K s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	tnta	atmos				
1	Tendency of Air Temperature due to Diabatic Processes	K s ⁻¹			tntmp	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_model_physics	K s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	tntmp	atmos				
1	Tendency of Air Temperature due to Stratiform Cloud Condensation and Evaporation	K s ⁻¹			tntscpl	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_stratiform_cloud_and_precipitation_and_boundary_layer_mixing	K s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	tntscpl	atmos				
1	Tendency of Air Temperature due to Radiative Heating	K s ⁻¹			tnttr	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_radiative_heating	K s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	tnttr	atmos				
1	Tendency of Air Temperature due to Moist Convection	K s ⁻¹			tntc	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_convection	K s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	tntc	atmos				
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity	s ⁻¹			tntus	tendency_of_specific_humidity	s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	tntus	atmos				
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity due to Advection	s ⁻¹			tntusa	tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_advection	s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	tntusa	atmos				
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity due to Convection	s ⁻¹			tntusc	tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_convection	s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	tntusc	atmos				
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity due to Diffusion	s ⁻¹			tntusd	tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_diffusion	s-1	time: point		real	alevel site time1	tntusd	atmos				

cfSites

1	Tendency of Specific Humidity due to Striform Cloud Condensation and Evaporation	s^{-1}		tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_stratiform_cloud_and_precipitation_and_boundary_layer_mixing	s-1	time: point	real	alevel site time l	tthuscpbl	atmos	
1	Tendency of Specific Humidity due to Model Physics	s^{-1}		tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_model_physics	s-1	time: point	real	alevel site time l	tthusmp	atmos	
1	Eddy Viscosity Coefficient for Momentum Variables	$m^2 s^{-1}$		atmosphere_momentum_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: point	real	alevel site time l	evu	atmos	
1	Eddy Diffusivity Coefficient for Temperature Variable	$m^2 s^{-1}$		atmosphere_heat_diffusivity	m2 s-1	time: point	real	alevel site time l	edt	atmos	
1	Pressure on Model Levels	Pa	This field is needed only for models in which the pressure can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored already for each variable. Thus, the pressures are needed for height or theta-coordinate models, for example, but not sigma- or eta-coordinate models.	pfull	air_pressure	Pa	time: point	real	alevel site time l	pfull	atmos
1	Pressure on Model Half-Levels	Pa	This field is needed only for models in which the pressure can't be calculated from the vertical coordinate information stored already for each variable. Thus, the pressures are needed for height or theta-coordinate models, for example, but not sigma- or eta-coordinate models.	phalf	air_pressure	Pa	time: point	real	alevhalf site time l	phalf	atmos
1	Longitude	degrees_east	Note that the CF convention and CMOR2 require that this field will be included in each file that contains a variable that is a function of the "site" dimension, so there is no need to save this field by itself. It is included here simply to indicate that longitudes should be stored for the site grid in each file written.	lon	longitude	degrees_east	real	site	longitude	atmos	
1	Latitude	degrees_north	the above comment also applies to latitude.	lat	latitude	degrees_north	real	site	latitude	atmos	

other output

Requested output: years requested for each expt./output table combination (see CFMIP output sheet for information on time-periods for saving the special CFMIP-focused output.

red font means output should be reported for only a single member in the case of an ensemble of simulations

blue font means this is a lower priority request

If a cell is shaded yellow/tan, none of the variables will be part of the subset of model output that will be replicated at several locations (except, as noted by * or ** -- see note at right-- this may apply only to lower priority variables)

"all*" indicates that although all years will be included in the "replicated" subset, only the high and medium priority variables will be included in the replicated subset.

"all**" indicates that although all years will be included in the "replicated" subset, only the highest priority variables will be included in the replicated subset

"decadal" prediction experiments			Oclim	Oyr	Amon	Omon		Lmon	Limon	Oimon	aero		day		6hrLev	6hrPlev	3hr
Experiment	Description	Expt. #				lon x lat x olev	other				lon x lat	lon x lat x alev	subset of fields saved for selected expts.	other			lon x lat
10-year predictions	10-year hindcasts/predictions	1.1		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	year 10		all			
30-year predictions	30-year hindcasts/predictions	1.2		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	years 10, 20, & 30		all			
10-year predictions	increased ensemble size of 1.1	1.1-E		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	year 10		all			
30-year predictions	increased ensemble size of 1.2	1.2-E		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	years 10, 20, & 30		all			
10-year predictions	additional start dates for expts. 1.1	1.1-1		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	year 10		all			
AMIP	AMIP (1979-2008)	3.3			all			all	all	all	all	years 1980, 1990, 2000, & possibly 2010	all	all	all	all	all
pre-industrial control	control run, but possibly as short as 100 years	3.1-S		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	years 20, 40, 60, 80, & 100		all			30 years corresponding to years 121-150 of abrupt 4xCO2 run
1 percent per year CO2 volcano-free hindcasts	1% per year CO2 rise imposed hindcasts but without volcanoes	6.1-S		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	year 10		all			first 5 years and years 121-150
prediction with 2010 volcano	Pinatubo-like eruption imposed	1.4		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	years 2010, 2011, 2012, and 2015		all		all	all
initialization alternatives	experiments to explore impact of different initialization procedures	1.5		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	year 10		all		all	all
chemistry-focused runs	near-term runs with enhanced chemistry/aerosol models	1.6															

experiments focusing on the "longer-term"			Oclim	Oyr	Amon	Omon		Lmon	Limon	Oimon	aero		day		6hrLev	6hrPlev	3hr
Experiment	Description	Expt. #				lon x lat x olev	other				lon x lat	lon x lat x alev	subset of fields saved for selected expts.	other			
pre-industrial control	coupled atmosphere/ocean control run	3.1		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	years corresponding to years 1850, 1870, 1890, . . . , 1950, 1960, 1970, . . . , 2000 of only 1 member of the ensemble of historical run and years 2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100 of only 1 member of the ensemble of each of the RCP cases	20 years corresponding to years 1979-2008 of historical runs	all		30 years corresponding to 1979-2008 of historical run	30 years corresponding to years 121-150 of abrupt 4xCO2 run
historical	simulation of recent past (1850-2005)	3.2	1986-2005 monthly climatology	all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	years 1850, 1870, 1890, . . . , 1950, 1960, 1970, . . . , 2000	1950-2005	all	1950-2005	1950-2005	1960-2005
AMIP	AMIP (1979-2008)	3.3			all			all	all	all	all	1980, 1990, 2000, & possibly 2010	all	all	all	all	all
historical	increase ensemble size of expt. 3.2	3.2-E		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	years 1850, 1870, 1890, . . . , 1950, 1960, 1970, . . . , 2000		all		1950-2005	1960-2005
AMIP	increase ensemble size of expt. 3.3	3.3-E			all			all	all	all	all	1980, 1990, 2000, & possibly 2010		all		all	all
mid-Holocene	consistent with PMIP, impose Mid-Holocene conditions	3.4		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		last 30 years	
last glacial maximum	consistent with PMIP, impose last glacial maximum conditions	3.5		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		last 30 years	
last millennium	consistent with PMIP, impose forcing for 850-1850	3.6		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all			
RCP4.5	future projection (2006-2100) forced by RCP4.5	4.1		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100	all	all	all	all	2026-2045, 2081-2100
RCP8.5	future projection (2006-2100) forced by RCP8.5	4.2		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100	all	all	all	all	2026-2045, 2081-2100
RCP2.6	future projection (2006-2100) forced by RCP2.6	4.3		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100	all	all			2026-2045, 2081-2100
RCP6	future projection (2006-2100) forced by RCP6	4.4		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100	all	all			2026-2045, 2081-2100
RCP4.5	extension of expt. 4.1 through 2300	4.1-L		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100	2181-2200, 2281-2300	all			2181-2200, 2281-2300
RCP8.5	extension of expt. 4.2 through 2300	4.2-L		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100	2181-2200, 2281-2300	all			2181-2200, 2281-2300

other output

RCP2.6	extension of expt. 4.3 through 2300	4.3-L		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100	2181-2200, 2281-2300	all		2181-2200, 2281-2300
ESM pre-industrial control	as in expt. 3.1, but atmospheric CO2 determined by model	5.1		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	years 1850, 1870, 1890, . . . , 1950, 1960, 1970, . . . , 2000 of the historical run and years 2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100 of the RCP run	20 years corresponding to years 1986-2005 of historical run	all		
Emission-driven historical	as in expt. 3.2, but with atmospheric CO2 determined by model	5.2		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	years 1850, 1870, 1890, . . . , 1950, 1960, 1970, . . . , 2000	1950-2005	all		1960-2005
emission-driven RCP8.5	as in expt. 4.2, but with atmospheric CO2 determined by model	5.3		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all	2010, 2020, 2040, 2060, 2080, & 2100	all	all		2026-2045, 2081-2100
ESM fixed climate 1	radiation code "sees" control CO2, but carbon cycle sees 1%/yr rise	5.4-1		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		
ESM fixed climate 2	radiation code "sees" control CO2, but carbon cycle sees historical followed by RCP4.5 rise in CO2	5.4-2		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		
ESM feedback 1	carbon cycle "sees" control CO2, but radiation sees 1%/yr rise	5.5-1		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		
ESM feedback 2	carbon cycle "sees" control CO2, but radiation sees historical followed by RCP4.5 rise in CO2	5.5-2		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		
1 percent per year CO2 control SST climatology	imposed 1%/yr increase in CO2 to quadrupling	6.1		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		last 30
CO2 forcing	An atmosphere-only run driven by prescribed climatological SST and sea ice.	6.2a			all			all	all	all	all			all		all
abrupt 4XCO2	as in expt. 6.2a, but with 4XCO2 imposed	6.2b			all			all	all	all	all			all		all
abrupt 4XCO2	impose an instantaneous quadrupling of CO2, then hold fixed	6.3			all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		first 5 years and years 121-150
abrupt 4XCO2	generate an ensemble of runs like expt. 6.3, initialized in different months, and terminated after 5 years	6.3-E			all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		all
anthropogenic aerosol forcing	as in expt. 6.2a, but with anthropogenic aerosols from year 2000 of expt. 3.2	6.4a			all			all	all	all	all			all		all
sulfate aerosol forcing	as in expt. 6.2a, but with sulfate aerosols from year 2000 of expt. 3.2	6.4b			all			all	all	all	all			all		all
Cloud response to imposed 4xCO2	consistent with CFMIP, impose AMIP (1979-2008) conditions (expt. 3.3) but with 4xCO2	6.5			all			all	all	all	all			all		
Cloud response to an imposed change in SST pattern	consistent with CFMIP, add a patterned SST perturbation to AMIP SSTs of expt. 3.3.	6.6			all			all	all	all	all			all		
aqua planet: control run	consistent with CFMIP, impose zonally uniform SSTs on a planet without continents	6.7a			all									all		
aqua planet: cloud response to imposed 4xCO2	Consistent with CFMIP requirements, impose 4xCO2 on the zonally uniform SSTs of expt. 6.7a	6.7b			all									all		
Aqua-planet: cloud response to an imposed uniform change in SST.	Consistent with CFMIP requirements, add a uniform +4K to the zonally uniform SSTs of expt. 6.7a (which is the control for this run).	6.7c			all									all		
Cloud response to an imposed uniform change in SST	Consistent with CFMIP requirements, add a uniform +4 K SST to the AMIP SSTs of expt. 3.3 (which is the "control" for this run).	6.8			all			all	all	all	all			all		
natural-only	historical simulation but with natural forcing only	7.1		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		
GHG-only	historical simulation but with greenhouse gas forcing only	7.2		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		
other-only	historical simulation but with other individual forcing agents	7.3		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		
natural-only	increase ensemble size of expt. 7.1	7.1-E		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		
GHG-only	increase ensemble size of expt. 7.2	7.2-E		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		
other-only	increase ensemble size of expt. 7.3	7.3-E		all*	all	all**	all	all	all	all	all			all		

atmosphere-only experiments			Oclim	Oyr	Amon	Omon		Lmon	Limon	Oimon	aero		day		6hrLev	6hrPlev	3hr
Experiment	Description	Expt. #				lon x lat	other				lon x lat	subset of fields saved for selected expts.					
						x elev					lon x lat x elev	other					
AMIP	AMIP (1979-2008)	3.3			all			all	all	all	all	years 1980, 1990, 2000, & possibly 2010	all	all	all	all	all
2030 time-slice	conditions for 2026-2035 imposed	2.1			all			all	all	all	all	year 2035	all	all	all	all	all
AMIP	increase ensemble size of expt. 3.3	3.3-E			all			all	all	all	all	years 1980, 1990, 2000, & possibly 2010	all	all	all	all	all
2030 time-slice	increase ensemble size of expt. 2.1	2.1-E			all			all	all	all	all	year 2035	all	all	all	all	all
Cloud response to imposed 4xCO2	consistent with CFMIP, impose AMIP (1979-2008) conditions (expt. 3.3) but with 4xCO2	6.5			all			all	all	all	all		all	all	all	all	all
Cloud response to an imposed change in SST pattern	consistent with CFMIP, add a patterned SST perturbation to AMIP SSTs of expt. 3.3.	6.6			all			all	all	all	all		all	all	all	all	all
aqua planet: control run	consistent with CFMIP, impose zonally uniform SSTs on a planet without continents	6.7a			all								all	all	all	all	all

CFMIP output

If a cell is shaded yellow/tan, none of the variables will be part of the subset of model output that will be replicated at several locations.

Requested periods for saving special CFMIP model output

Experiment Name		Experiment Description	Experiment number	appearing in cFMon table				appearing in cFOff		appearing in cFDay		appearing in cF3hr		appearing in cFSites									
				CFMIP monthly 2D (A1c, cFmip)		CFMIP monthly 4xCO2 2D		CFMIP monthly 4xCO2 3D		CFMIP monthly saline (A1B1.6a)		CFMIP monthly offline (A1c)		CFMIP daily 2D (A2a,c-f)		CFMIP daily 3D (A2b,b,d)		CFMIP 3-hourly orbital offline (A2c)		CFMIP 3-hourly saline (A4)		CFMIP time-step 4xCO2 data (A3)	
pre-industrial control	coupled atmosphere/ocean control run	3.1		1*	20*		1*	20*		1*	20*												
pre-industrial control	coupled atmosphere/ocean control run	3.1					121*	140*		121*	140*		121*	140*									
historical	simulation of recent past (1850-2005)	3.2					1979	2005		1979	2005												
AMIP	AMIP (1979-at least 2008)	3.3	1979	2008	1979	2008	1979	2008	2008	2008	1979	2008	1979	2008	2008	2008	2008	2008	1979	2008			
ESM fixed climate 1	radiation code "sees" control CO2, but carbon cycle sees 1%/yr rise	5.4-1					121	140		121	140												
ESM feedback 1	carbon cycle "sees" control CO2, but radiation sees 1%/yr rise	5.5-1					121	140		121	140												
1 percent per year CO2	impose a 1%/yr increase in CO2 to quadrupling	6.1					121	140		121	140		121	140									
control SST climatology	control run climatological SSTs & sea ice imposed.	6.2a		1	30		1	30		1	30												
CO2 forcing	as in expt. 6.2a, but with 4XCO2 imposed	6.2b					1	30		1	30												
abrupt 4XCO2	impose an instantaneous quadrupling of CO2, then hold fixed	6.3					1	20		1	20												
abrupt 4XCO2	impose an instantaneous quadrupling of CO2, then hold fixed	6.3					121	140		121	140		121	140									
abrupt 4XCO2	generate an ensemble of runs like expt. 6.3, initialized in different months, and terminated after 5 years	6.3-E					1	5		1	5												
all aerosol forcing	as in expt. 6.2a, but with aerosols from year 2000 of expt. 3.2	6.4a					1	30		1	30												
sulfate aerosol forcing	as in expt. 6.2a, but with sulfate aerosols from year 2000 of expt. 3.2	6.4b					1	30		1	30												
4xCO2 AMIP	AMIP (1979-2008) conditions (expt. 3.3) but with 4xCO2	6.5	1979	2008			1979	2008	2008	2008	1979	2008	1979	2008	2008	2008	2008				1979	2008	
AMIP plus patterned anomaly	consistent with CFMIP, patterned SST anomalies added to AMIP conditions (expt. 3.3)	6.6	1979	2008			1979	2008	2008	2008	1979	2008	1979	2008	2008	2008					1979	2008	
aqua planet control	consistent with CFMIP, zonally uniform SSTs for ocean-covered earth	6.7a	1	5	1	5	1	5		1	5	1	5								1	5	
4xCO2 aqua planet	as in expt. 6.7a, but with 4XCO2	6.7b	1	5			1	5		1	5	1	5								1	5	
aqua planet plus 4K anomaly	as in expt. 6.7a, but with a uniform 4K increase in SST	6.7c	1	5			1	5		1	5	1	5								1	5	
AMIP plus 4K anomaly	as in expt. 3.3, but with a uniform 4K increase in SST	6.8	1979	2008			1979	2008	2008	2008	1979	2008	1979	2008	2008	2008					1979	2008	

* The years specified for the pre-industrial experiment are relative to the point in the control where expts. 6.1 and 6.3 were initiated. 6.1 and 6.3 should be initiated from the same point in the control run, so that the control run sampled output can be compared directly to each of these runs, and any drift in the control can be accounted for.